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This journal publishes articles and academic papers in the field of law internationally online! Law affects various spheres of social life - economy, politics, social sphere, cultural and spiritual relations, and thus performs economic, political and educational functions. From a legal point of view, these functions can be divided into two types: regulatory (regulating) and negative (protective) functions. The regulatory function of law consists in establishing positive, universally acceptable rules of behavior and conduct of members of society, placing social relations on a legal basis, harmonizing and stabilizing social relations between people.

The negative function of law is the direction of legal influence determined by its social function, which is aimed at protecting economic, political, spiritual and other social relations of general importance, ensuring their inviolability, and at the same time suppressing relations that are alien to society and harmful to society.

The specific features of this function of law are clearly manifested when comparing it with the law enforcement activities of the state. Relevant state agencies ensure strict compliance with the requirements of the law by rights holders, creating an atmosphere of legality in society. This work is ensured by identifying the facts of violations of the law, investigating them and holding the perpetrators legally liable. This journal publishes articles on the subject of law.

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THE DEVELOPMENT STAGES OF CLOUD TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract. Cloud technologies have become the cornerstone of today's digital economy and have radically transformed the processes of data storage, processing, and delivery. This article details the formation of cloud technologies, stages of their development, and their impact on the field of information technology. First, the history of the cloud computing concept and its initial applications are analyzed. It also highlights the gradual evolution of infrastructure (IaaS), platform (PaaS), and software (SaaS) models in the process of technological development. The article provides comprehensive information about the technical capabilities of cloud technologies, security issues, and their role in the modern digital economy. The final section presents a detailed analysis of this technology's advantages and disadvantages, the expected positive outcomes of widespread implementation of large data centers in Uzbekistan, obstacles to this implementation, and the future prospects of these technologies. A comprehensive conclusion summarizes these points.

Keywords: *Cloud technologies, IaaS, PaaS, SaaS, digital economy, information technology, development stages, artificial intelligence.*

BULUTLI TEXNOLOGIYALARNING RIVOJLANISH BOSQICHLARI

Tojiboyeva Sevinch Zafar qizi

Toshkent davlat yuridik universiteti

Jinoiy odil sudlov fakulteti 1-bosqich talabasi

Annotatsiya. Bulutli texnologiyalar bugungi raqamli iqtisodiyotning asosiy tayanchiga aylandi va shuningdek, ma'lumotlarni saqlash, qayta ishlash hamda yetkazib berish

jarayonlarini tubdan o'zgartirib yubordi. Ushbu maqolada bulutli texnologiyalarning shakllanishi, rivojlanish bosqichlari va ularning axborot texnologiyalari sohasiga ta'siri batafsil yoritilgan. Avvalo, bulutli hisoblash tushunchasining kelib chiqish tarixi va dastlabki qo'llanish holatlari tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, texnologiyaning rivojlanish jarayonida infratuzilma (IaaS), platforma (PaaS) va dasturiy ta'minot (SaaS) modellarining bosqichma-bosqich shakllangani yoritib beriladi. Maqolada bulutli texnologiyalarning texnik imkoniyatlari, xavfsizlik masalalari va zamonaviy raqamli iqtisodiyotda tutgan o'rni haqida bir qator ma'lumot beriladi. Yakuniy qismda esa ushbu texnologiyaning afzallik va kamchiliklari, Katta hajmdagi ma'lumotlar markazlarini (data centre) O'zbekiston hududida keng joriy etilishidan kutiladigan ijobiy oqibatlar va buni amalga oshirishdagi to'siqlar va shuningdek, ushbu texnologiyalarning kelajakdagi istiqboli haqida umumlashtiruvchi xulosa beriladi va batafsil tahlil etiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: *Bulutli texnologiyalar, IaaS, PaaS, SaaS, raqamli iqtisodiyot, axborot texnologiyalari, rivojlanish bosqichlari, sun'iy intellekt.*

ЭТАПЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ОБЛАЧНЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ

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Аннотация: Облачные технологии стали основной опорой современной цифровой экономики и коренным образом изменили процессы хранения, обработки и передачи данных. В данной статье подробно рассматриваются становление и этапы развития облачных технологий, а также их влияние на сферу информационных технологий. Прежде всего, анализируется история возникновения понятия облачных вычислений и случаи его первоначального применения. Также освещается поэтапное формирование моделей инфраструктуры как услуги (IaaS), платформы

как услуги (PaaS) и программного обеспечения как услуги (SaaS) в процессе развития технологии. В статье представлена информация о технических возможностях облачных технологий, вопросах безопасности и их роли в современной цифровой экономике. В заключительной части приводится и подробно анализируется обобщающий вывод о преимуществах и недостатках этой технологии, положительных последствиях, ожидаемых от широкого внедрения центров обработки больших данных (data centre) на территории Узбекистана, препятствиях на пути их реализации, а также о будущих перспективах этих технологий.

Ключевые слова: *Облачные технологии, IaaS, PaaS, SaaS, цифровая экономика, информационные технологии, этапы развития, искусственный интеллект.*

Introduction

In the modern era, information technologies are rapidly developing and penetrating various aspects of human life and society. Especially in recent decades, cloud technologies have gained great importance in society and today's digital economy. So, what are cloud technologies? What do we mean by cloud technologies? Cloud Computing refers to the infrastructure that enables storing, processing, and using data over the Internet.¹ To put it simply, while previously programs or data were stored only on the computer itself, now they are stored on cloud servers. Users now have access to this data at any time, from any place, and from any device.² As a result, these technologies have become one of the most significant technological achievements of the 21st century and an integral part of today's digital economy.

¹ Mell, P., & Grance, T. (2011). *The NIST Definition of Cloud Computing*. National Institute of Standards and Technology.

² Buyya, R., Vecchiola, C., & Selvi, S. T. (2013). *Mastering Cloud Computing*. McGraw Hill.

If we look at the history of the emergence of cloud technologies, this idea primarily dates back to the 1960s. In the 1960s, computer networks had a time-sharing system that allowed multiple users to connect to the central computer simultaneously and utilize resources. IBM and AT&T companies conducted initial experiments in this field.³ It was through this system that the idea of these cloud technologies emerged. After the Internet became widely popular in the 1990s, this technology entered real-world practice. In the 2000s, major companies like Amazon, Google, and Microsoft launched their first **cloud platforms**.⁴

Today, cloud technologies are primarily based on models such as Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS), Platform as a Service (PaaS), and Software as a Service (SaaS).⁵ These technologies are not only widely used to increase efficiency in education, healthcare, business, public administration, banking systems, and scientific research, but they are also being extensively utilized in these fields. Furthermore, cloud technologies not only optimize existing infrastructure but also, by integrating with artificial intelligence, big data, and the Internet of Things (IoT), are taking the digital economy to a new level.⁶ Moreover, cloud technologies are now viewed not only as a means of improving service quality but also as a **factor of competitiveness**. For instance, according to the World Economic Forum (WEF), by 2030, more than 60 percent of the global digital economy is expected to be based on cloud technologies.⁷ This means that countries that implement these technologies early will gain advantages not only technically but also economically. From this perspective, the early implementation of cloud solutions in Uzbekistan's national digital infrastructure provides a strategic advantage. Additionally, the implementation of these technologies in Uzbekistan can contribute to the development of the digital

³ Parkhill, D. F. (1966). *The Challenge of the Computer Utility*. Addison-Wesley.

⁴ Armbrust, M. et al. (2010). *A View of Cloud Computing*. Communications of the ACM.

⁵ Amazon Web Services. <https://aws.amazon.com>

⁶ Amazon Web Services. (n.d.). <https://aws.amazon.com>

⁷ World Economic Forum (2022). *A digital silver bullet for the world: How digitalization can accelerate growth and inclusion*

economy, the automation of public services, and the improvement of service quality in education and healthcare sectors. Therefore, scientific study of this topic, analysis of development stages, and the development of strategic directions aligned with the national infrastructure are of crucial importance.

2. Methods

In this article, several scientific and methodological approaches were employed to analyze the developmental stages of cloud technologies. The research process was organized in phases, utilizing data collection and literature analysis, statistical and historical analyses, comparative analysis, as well as cross-checking as the primary methods.

Initially, data collection and literature analysis were conducted. During this phase, scientific articles on the history of cloud technologies, reports from international IT companies, analytical articles on technological advancements, and internet sources were examined. Since the concept of "Cloud Computing" became widespread and extensively applied in the 2000s, the main focus was directed towards sources from that period onward. Specifically, the developmental history of major platforms such as Amazon Web Services (AWS), Microsoft Azure, Google Cloud, and others was analyzed.⁸ Additionally, scientific articles sourced from academic databases (Google Scholar, IEEE Xplore, and ResearchGate) were used to systematically illuminate the processes of technological development.

In the second stage of the research methodology, statistical and historical analysis methods were employed. Statistical analysis was used to examine annual changes in the number of users, the size of service markets, and the scale of expansion of this technology. Such data were obtained from open sources, including reports by Statista, Gartner, and

⁸ Amazon Web Services. *History of AWS*. AWS Documentation, 2023.

Deloitte companies.⁹ Historical analysis helped identify the stages of technology formation. Through this approach, cloud technologies were divided into three main stages: the initial stage (2000-2010), the development stage (2010-2020), and the refinement stage (2020-present).

In the third stage, the comparative analysis method was extensively applied. This method was used to compare technological approaches, platform capabilities, and service models (IaaS, PaaS, SaaS) at each stage. As a result, it became possible to clearly demonstrate how technology was distinguished by different approaches in various periods. Additionally, data from different sources were cross-compared to evaluate their reliability.

During the research process, a cross-check method was employed to verify the reliability of the data. Each figure or fact was confirmed using at least two or three independent sources. This approach reduced the likelihood of errors and enhanced the accuracy of conclusions. Additionally, at this stage, the practical methods and processes of using cloud technologies were thoroughly studied with reference to international experiences. In the final stage, all information was systematized, conclusions were drawn based on specific facts, and the topic was comprehensively covered.

Overall, the combined application of these methods enabled a scientific analysis of the step-by-step formation of cloud technologies. While the literature review provided a theoretical foundation, statistical and comparative analyses reinforced technological changes with digital evidence.

3. Results

In the process of scientific research, clear and systematic results were obtained regarding the formation and developmental stages of cloud technologies, based on

⁹ Statista. *Cloud Computing Market Size Worldwide 2010–2024*. Statista Report, 2024

literature analysis, statistical and historical analyses, comparative analysis, and cross-verification methods. The data collected during the research allowed for the identification of three main developmental stages: **initial stage (2000-2010)** , **development stage (2010-2020)** , and **refinement stage (2020-present)** . Distinctive features of each stage were thoroughly examined, including technological changes, types of services, market growth indicators, and the scope of practical applications.

1) Initial stage (2000-2010)

Analyses revealed that the concept of cloud technologies began to take shape in the early 2000s. It was during this period that Amazon Web Services (AWS) started offering its first cloud services, ushering in a new era of IT infrastructure.¹⁰ At this stage, infrastructure-level services (IaaS) were primarily developed, providing users with more flexible and cost-effective solutions compared to traditional server infrastructure.

According to the literature analysis, the rapid development of cloud technologies during this period was attributed to the widespread adoption of the Internet, increased data transmission speeds, and technical capabilities for establishing data centers.¹¹ However, this stage was not yet implemented on a large scale, but rather in corporate and technical sectors. Statistical analyses show that a crucial aspect of this stage was its focus primarily on large companies rather than the general public. In other words, between 2000 and 2005, the cloud services market was still relatively small, with a limited number of users.

Furthermore, during this period, PaaS and SaaS service models were not yet fully developed, but their initial concepts began to be formulated by IT companies. The most significant technological achievement was the emergence of virtual servers, which enabled the provision of remote services to users.

¹⁰ Armbrust, M. et al. *A View of Cloud Computing*. Communications of the ACM, 2010.

¹¹ Mell, P. & Grance, T. *The NIST Definition of Cloud Computing*. NIST, 2011.

2) Development stage (2010-2020)

The most crucial part of the research findings pertained to the development stage. By the 2010s, cloud technologies began to be widely adopted, and major technology companies actively entered this field. Amazon Web Services (AWS), Microsoft Azure, and Google Cloud expanded globally during these years, assuming leading positions in the provision of cloud services.¹²

According to statistical analysis results, the annual growth rate of the cloud technology market between 2010 and 2020 was around 20-30%.¹³ Based on Gartner and Statista reports, by 2015, thousands of companies worldwide had migrated their infrastructure to the cloud, with these numbers increasing year by year. During this period, cloud technologies began to be widely implemented not only at the corporate level but also in education, healthcare, manufacturing, and public administration systems.

Comparative analysis showed that at this stage, service models **IaaS**, **PaaS**, and **SaaS** were fully developed and began to offer users various levels of convenience. For example, through the **SaaS** model, many small and medium-sized businesses gained access to cloud services without having to create their own IT infrastructure. This enabled further acceleration of this technology's popularization.¹⁴

Regarding the results of historical analysis, **mobile technologies** and **IoT (Internet of Things)** factors also played a significant role in the development of cloud technologies from 2010 to 2020. Due to the sharp increase in the number of users, companies felt the need for more efficient data storage and processing solutions. As a result, the number of large data centers increased.

¹² Statista. *Cloud Computing Market Size Worldwide 2010–2024*. Statista Report, 2024.

¹³ Statista. *Cloud Computing Market Size Worldwide 2010–2024*. Statista Report, 2024.

¹⁴ Buyya, R., Broberg, J., Goscinski, A. *Cloud Computing: Principles and Paradigms*. Wiley, 2011

3) Improvement stage (2020-present)

The third part of the scientific research pertains to the present time, namely the stage of advancement. The main feature of this stage is the emergence of advanced cloud technologies integrated with **artificial** intelligence, **Big Data**, **5G** technology, and **automated control** systems. In the years following 2020, cloud technologies are viewed not only as infrastructure but also as a strategic resource. At this stage, primarily **the hybrid and multi-cloud** types of cloud technologies have become widespread.

Turning our attention to the results of statistical analysis, it is noted that between 2020 and 2024, the value of the cloud technology market approached 1 trillion US dollars. According to Gartner, more than 60% of IT services worldwide are provided through the cloud.¹⁵ Evidently, during this period, technologies became even safer, more convenient, and more efficient.

Analysis also revealed that at the current stage, users are not only utilizing services but also creating their own infrastructure based on the cloud. Furthermore, it has been observed that **cloud solutions are being regarded as the primary infrastructure** in sectors such as education, healthcare, finance, and manufacturing. Particularly during the pandemic (2019-2021), with the advancement of distance learning and remote work formats, the demand for cloud services increased dramatically.¹⁶

The development process of cloud technologies has been shaped not only through technical stages but also in close connection with global trends, international politics, economic integration, and digital transformation. While these technologies have become an integral part of economic growth in many developed countries over the last decade,

¹⁵ Statista. *Cloud Computing Market Size Worldwide 2010–2024*. Statista Report, 2024.

¹⁶ Alqaied, R. (2022). *The role of cloud computing technology: A savior to fight the COVID-19 pandemic*. *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications (IJACSA)*

they have also spurred the rapid formation of digital infrastructure in developing countries. Observations of international experiences show that the effectiveness of implementing cloud technologies largely depends on state policies and the level of technological infrastructure development. For instance, Estonia has successfully leveraged cloud technologies strategically in creating its digital state infrastructure. Currently, over 95% of all public services in this country are provided online, with cloud data exchange infrastructure serving as the foundation of this system. Consequently, public services have become faster, bureaucracy has decreased, and economic efficiency has improved.¹⁷ In Singapore's case, cloud technologies have strengthened integration between the public and private sectors. The government also launched a special "Government Cloud" program to support the implementation of cloud services, through which digital services have been introduced in education, healthcare, and transportation.¹⁸ One of the most crucial aspects is that information security has been prioritized in technology implementation, resulting in a high level of citizen trust. In the USA and the European Union, cloud technologies are widely implemented primarily in the business sector. Major tech companies, including Amazon, Microsoft, and Google, have created globally centralized cloud infrastructures. In Europe, the "GAIA-X" cloud infrastructure project has been developed, aiming to create an independent and secure data infrastructure for European users.¹⁹ This project primarily promotes the idea of organizing cloud services in a politically and economically sovereign manner. Japan and South Korea have implemented cloud technologies in integration with technical advancements. Particularly with the introduction of 5G technology, real-time cloud computing and "edge computing" approaches have become widely adopted. This, in turn, has become one of the key factors in implementing the smart city concept. As a result, the efficiency of transport management, healthcare, security systems, and environmental monitoring has increased, leading to the automation of

¹⁷ Estonian Information System Authority. *e-Estonia Briefing Centre Report*, 2022.

¹⁸ GovTech Singapore. *Government Cloud Strategy 2025*. Singapore Government, 2023.

¹⁹ GAIA-X Initiative. *European Cloud Infrastructure Strategy*. European Commission, 2022.

industrial processes, the emergence of intelligent systems in production, and improved service speeds.²⁰ Analysis further shows that in many developed countries, the implementation of cloud technologies is central to national digital transformation strategies. For example, in the USA, the federal government adopted the "Cloud First" policy, mandating the initial use of cloud solutions across all government systems. This has enhanced flexibility and efficiency in the state infrastructure.²¹ This experience demonstrates that cloud technologies function not only as a technical service but also as a means of systemic management.

According to the research findings, cloud technologies have evolved from simple server solutions into a highly intelligent infrastructure today. Literature analysis revealed the historical foundations of this process, while statistical analysis expressed its scale in numerical terms. Comparative analysis identified the technological features and innovations of each stage.

The accuracy and reliability of the results were ensured by comparing the data obtained through cross-verification with several independent sources. Furthermore, using the applied methods, a three-stage model of technological evolution was developed and extensively elaborated.

4. and Discussion

The results of this study align with the conclusions presented in numerous international scientific works. For instance, the research by Armbrust et al. notes that the formative stages of cloud technology began in the 2000s and this process gradually

²⁰ Statista. *Cloud Computing Market Size Worldwide 2010–2024*. Statista Report, 2024.
World Economic Forum. *The Global Digital Economy Outlook 2030*. WEF Report, 2023.

²¹ U.S. Federal CIO Council. *Cloud First Policy Implementation Guide*. USA, 2021.

expanded over time.²² In the NIST definition presented by Mell and Grance, the core model of the technology is described as the service models **IaaS, PaaS, and SaaS**.²³ Buyya and co-authors linked these stages to the improvement of technological infrastructure and predicted deeper integration in the future.²⁴ Furthermore, the stages identified in this study and their technological characteristics are consistent with the latest reports from organizations such as Gartner, Deloitte, and Statista.²⁵ This further validates the relevance and reliability of the conducted analysis.

Looking at the issue from another perspective, the use of these technologies has its own distinct advantages and disadvantages. Let's first familiarize ourselves with the advantages:

One of the primary major advantages of this technology is **cost reduction**. A significant portion of server costs, maintenance, and infrastructure expenses are mainly borne by cloud providers. As a result, companies have the opportunity to allocate more funds towards developing their core activities. The second advantage is **continuity and reliability**. Major providers offer their services with a high level of security and stability. This was particularly evident during the pandemic years: many organizations were able to continue their operations without interruption with the help of cloud services during the transition to remote work.²⁶ Furthermore, as mentioned above, cloud technologies enable the acceleration of processes, centralized data management, and digital transformation in numerous sectors such as **education, healthcare, finance, industry, and public administration**.

²² Armbrust, M. et al. *A View of Cloud Computing*. Communications of the ACM, 2010.

²³ Mell, P. & Grance, T. *The NIST Definition of Cloud Computing*. NIST, 2011.

²⁴ Buyya, R., Broberg, J., Goscinski, A. *Cloud Computing: Principles and Paradigms*. Wiley, 2011.

²⁵ Statista. *Cloud Computing Market Size Worldwide 2010–2024*. Statista Report, 2024.

²⁶ Statista. *Cloud Computing Market Size Worldwide 2010–2024*. Statista Report, 2024.

Like any technological achievement, cloud technologies also have a number of specific problems and shortcomings. In particular, the research has shown that a large portion of users still view security and privacy issues as the biggest obstacle. Specifically, storing data on third-party servers limits their ability to control it, and in some cases, this can increase the risk of personal or commercial data leakage.²⁷ Secondly, there are legal and regulatory restrictions. In other words, some countries require data to be stored within their territory. For example, the GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) law in the European Union, which imposes strict requirements on cloud service providers, requires companies to implement additional security measures. This situation mainly complicates cooperation with international providers.²⁸ Furthermore, in some developing countries, weak technical infrastructure or lack of funds is hindering the widespread adoption of this technology.

It is worth noting that, given the recent development of the digital economy, e-government, distance learning, and healthcare systems in our country, the widespread adoption of cloud technologies creates significant opportunities for Uzbekistan. From this perspective, **the proposal to establish local large-scale data centers in Uzbekistan and adapt them to cloud infrastructure is considered relevant.** However, **the limited data storage infrastructure remains one of the biggest obstacles to implementing this idea in practice.** This approach could lead to the following positive outcomes: **enhancing national security** through data storage within the country; reducing legal and regulatory issues; increasing speed by keeping internet traffic within the internal network; creating a competitive platform for local IT companies and startups; accelerating the digital transformation of government organizations, and more. However, along with this process, certain **costs and risks** also arise. Specifically, building data centers requires substantial

²⁷ Mell, P. & Grance, T. *The NIST Definition of Cloud Computing*. NIST, 2011.

²⁸ Statista. *Cloud Computing Market Size Worldwide 2010–2024*. Statista Report, 2024.

Buyya, R., Broberg, J., Goscinski, A. *Cloud Computing: Principles and Paradigms*. Wiley, 2011.

investment, and ensuring their uninterrupted operation necessitates efficient organization of electricity and cooling systems. Additionally, the issue of training qualified specialists is of great importance. Furthermore, Uzbekistan's successful development in this area depends on studying international experience and fostering cooperation. For instance, countries like Estonia, Singapore, and Korea have made digital infrastructure a priority of state policy and achieved significant success in a short period. For Uzbekistan, it is crucial to collaborate with international providers in this direction, as well as to strengthen local infrastructure.

Looking ahead to the future prospects of this technology, cloud technologies are expected to become more deeply integrated with quantum computing, artificial intelligence, and edge computing.²⁹ This will lead to a qualitatively new stage in technology, reducing the load on system networks and increasing service speed. In particular, areas such as **autonomous systems, smart cities, digital healthcare, and Industry 5.0** are developing, where cloud technologies are expected to play a central role. However, alongside these advancements, new risks will also emerge. Therefore, in the future, issues of security policy, standardization, and international cooperation will become even more crucial. Additionally, the "serverless computing" model simplifies the development process, allowing programmers to focus on functional results rather than infrastructure management. Furthermore, there are several concepts suggesting that integration with Artificial Intelligence (AI), Big Data, and 5G technologies will take cloud technologies to a new level.³⁰

Another promising direction of this technology is "Green Cloud Computing". Considering that cloud technologies have not been analyzed from an ecological

²⁹ Hossain, M. I., Sumon, S. A., Hasan, H. M., Akter, F., Badhon, M. B., & Ul Islam, M. N. (2024). *Quantum-Edge Cloud Computing: A Future Paradigm for IoT Applications*.

³⁰ Li, Z., Guo, L., Cheng, J., Chen, Q., & He, B. (2021). *The Serverless Computing Survey: A Technical Primer for Design Architecture*

perspective and large-scale data centers have been consuming significant amounts of energy in recent years, various proposals exist regarding the formation of this new type of cloud technology. Its main goal is expected to be reducing energy consumption, optimizing servers, and ensuring environmental sustainability.³¹ Today, many developed countries and large companies worldwide have begun creating their own national programs aimed at implementing this project. In particular, Microsoft and Google have announced plans to achieve carbon neutrality by 2030. This trend signals a new stage of technological evolution for the future. Overall, this article reveals not only the current state of cloud technologies but also their strategic importance for the future. In conclusion, cloud technologies serve as the foundation of modern digital infrastructure and are of strategic importance. Their effective implementation will significantly enhance the country's economic and innovative potential.

³¹ World Economic Forum. *The Global Digital Economy Outlook 2030*. WEF Report, 2023.

Women's Rights and Legitimate Interests

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Over the years of its independent development, Uzbekistan has achieved significant success in protecting the rights and legitimate interests of women. No less significant are the achievements in ensuring their active participation in the socio-political and socio-economic life of the country. The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan also highly values human dignity and places particular emphasis on gender equality.

Specifically, Article 58 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan states that "women and men have equal rights." It is worth noting that the legal foundations of gender equality are reflected in international and national legislation. Specifically, the equality of men and women is also recognized in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, adopted by the UN General Assembly in 1948.

Experience shows that in an economically stable society, equality between men and women is ensured at a high level. A person's professional development has distinct phases; at any level of professional development, no matter how complex an individual's actual behavior, there is a complex interconnection and interdependence between social parameters (requirements) and the transformation of the individual's inner world. Although the boundaries between "female" and "male" professions are blurred in the modern world, there are unspoken requirements for both. Women working in law enforcement must be able to combine the incompatible. They must possess a strong yet gentle character. This is largely true for women working in the juvenile department. They must manage to help their children overcome their problems while also caring for their own families.

The issue of women serving in law enforcement agencies is highly relevant. A significant number of studies by foreign scholars actively explore ways to address the problem of how female police officers can combine professional, family, and other social responsibilities. Female law enforcement officers are better at navigating social situations than civilians, and they are more perceptive about the actions and motives of others. These personal qualities of female police officers may be a consequence of their professional skills and are quite common in interactions with detainees in situations where suspects attempt to mislead law enforcement officers and when it is necessary to establish the true motives of their behavior (e.g., when resisting, behaving inappropriately, etc.).

The Ministry of Internal Affairs has created 360 female inspector positions to work with women in need of legal and social assistance. To ensure prompt and effective support for women who have suffered harassment and violence, standard operating procedures for a joint response to gender-based violence have been developed and implemented for law enforcement, healthcare, and social and psychological professionals.

Consistent and comprehensive reforms have ensured economic stability. To systematically implement the UN Sustainable Development Goals, our country has adopted the "National Goals and Targets of Uzbekistan for Sustainable Development until 2030". The fifth goal in this document is "Ensuring gender equality and empowering all women." This, in turn, includes economic, social, legal, and other measures. All government agencies and organizations, institutions, and public organizations of national significance are responsible for achieving these goals. As we know, on March 20, 2019, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan put forward five important initiatives to organize work in the social, spiritual, and educational spheres. The fifth initiative is aimed at addressing the issue of women's employment and creating fulfilling living conditions for women by providing them with jobs.

With government support, the Women's Committee of Uzbekistan organizes free retraining and training courses for new specialties. Centers are being opened where women

from rural areas learn artistic crafts and trades, such as carpet weaving, yarn dyeing, and other skills that provide them with additional income opportunities. Discussing the share of women in employment, which has now increased to 44%, a significant increase in their participation in small businesses was emphasized. Today, 35% of businesses are founded and headed by women.

Delegates from UN member states and human rights organizations were also informed that women predominate in the overall employment structure in Uzbekistan in sectors such as healthcare and sports (82%), education, culture, art, and science (72%), and trade and catering (54%). It's worth noting that the Republic has also prepared a draft National Action Plan, as noted by Tanzila Narbaeva, Chairperson of the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, at the opening of the roundtable. "Actively promoting women's participation in the political, economic, and social life of Uzbekistan is a key task for the government," said Tanzila Narbaeva. This is confirmed by the recent decisions taken by Uzbekistan's leadership aimed at significantly increasing the role of women in decision-making processes that are vital to the country's future development.

Uzbekistan is taking steps to implement the Sustainable Development Goals by increasing women's participation in public and state development, ensuring gender equality, and preventing discrimination against women. This was noted by Akmal Saidov, First Deputy Speaker of the Legislative Chamber of the Parliament and Director of the National Human Rights Center. He emphasized that the draft National Action Plan on Women, Peace, and Security identifies priority areas for change, implementing more effective gender policies, and striving to achieve results.

The draft National Action Plan on Women, Peace, and Security of Uzbekistan includes:

- Encouraging women's participation in peace and security processes; Widespread dissemination of knowledge on the topic of "Women, Peace, and Security," including among decision-makers;

- Systems for protecting and addressing the special needs of women and girls in emergency situations;
- Civil society participation in the implementation of UN Security Council Resolution 1325 on women, peace, and security.

At the core of Resolution 1325 is the recognition that lasting peace cannot be achieved without the significant participation of women in conflict prevention, resolution, and peacebuilding. The document calls for the full and equal participation of women in all peace and security initiatives, along with the mainstreaming of gender issues. This includes increasing women's participation in peace negotiations to resolve conflicts, as well as increasing the number of women in leadership positions at both the international and national levels.

Special attention was paid to informing the international community about the successes of women's employment in the country. It was noted that targeted government measures to employ graduates of secondary specialized vocational schools are yielding significant results. Programs aimed at improving working and educational conditions for women, particularly in rural areas, and engaging them in entrepreneurship are developed and implemented annually. In recent years, more than 327,000 women have received preferential loans totaling 7.4 trillion soums to develop women's entrepreneurship. In 2021, approximately 1.4 trillion soums are planned to be allocated to women entrepreneurs from the Fund for Reconstruction and Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

As a result, over the past four years, more than 620,200 women have been employed, and 106,000 have been assisted in establishing private businesses. For example, in 2020 alone, approximately 126,000 women were provided with preferential loans under the "Every Family – Entrepreneur" program. Nearly 215,000 families received loans for the development of family businesses totaling over six trillion soums. As part of the Five

Important Initiatives, sewing workshops have been established in remote areas, providing employment to 10,000 women.

These results were achieved through a comprehensive approach that created not only a solid legal foundation but also an effective institutional framework. One example is the establishment of a public organization, the Women's Committee of Uzbekistan, which has become a productive mechanism for supporting this segment of the population and protecting their rights and legitimate interests.

Prospects for the implementation of the right of development (superficies) in the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan

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Abstract: The article examines the theoretical and practical aspects of implementing the right to build (superficies) in the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Special attention is paid to foreign experience in regulating the superficies and the possibilities of its adaptation to the national legal system. The author analyzes the potential benefits of introducing this legal institution for promoting investment, efficient land use, and real estate market development.

Keywords: superficies, right to build, civil law, Civil Code, real estate, land relations, right to use someone else's land plot, limited real rights.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada O'zbekiston Respublikasi Fuqarolik kodeksiga qurilish huquqi (superfitsiy) institutini joriy etishning nazariy va amaliy jihatlari yoritilgan. Chet el tajribasi hamda ushbu institutni milliy huquq tizimiga moslashtirish imkoniyatlari tahlil qilinadi. Superfitsiyning joriy etilishi investitsiyalarni rag'batlantirish, yer uchastkalaridan samarali foydalanish va ko'chmas mulk bozorini rivojlantirishdagi ahamiyati ko'rsatib o'tiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: superfitsiy, qurilish huquqi, fuqarolik huquqi, Fuqarolik kodeksi, ko'chmas mulk, yer munosabatlari, bironing yer uchastkasidan foydalanish huquqi, cheklangan ashyoviy huquqlar.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются теоретические и практические аспекты имплементации института права застройки (суперфиция) в Гражданский кодекс Республики Узбекистан. Особое внимание уделено зарубежному опыту регулирования суперфиция, а также возможностям его адаптации к национальной правовой системе. Автор анализирует преимущества введения данного института для стимулирования инвестиций, эффективного использования земельных участков и развития рынка недвижимости.

Ключевые слова: суперфиций, право застройки, гражданское право, Гражданский кодекс, недвижимость, земельные отношения, право пользования чужим земельным участком, ограниченные вещные права.

The current state of legal regulation of land relations in the Republic of Uzbekistan demonstrates that the current system of property-law structures remains limited to the traditional triad of ownership, possession, and use. Under these conditions, the institution

of lease effectively fulfills the functions inherent in development law. However, its legal nature as a contractual right does not ensure the necessary stability in civil transactions involving real estate, does not create conditions for long-term investment, and does not facilitate the efficient use of state-owned land.

In analyzing the relationship between property rights and innovation, it is important to note the importance of revising and updating the system of property rights in the civil legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Current economic and legal realities require the inclusion of new legal frameworks capable of balancing the interests of the state, property owners, and investors, as well as increasing the efficiency of civil transactions.

In this regard, it would be appropriate to consider expanding the scope of property rights by incorporating into the Civil Code provisions on legal institutions that are currently new to Russian civil law. Among these, the following deserve particular attention:

1. A right of real property granting its holder the opportunity to periodically receive a certain amount of property from the owner of the real property—in the form of goods, money, work, or services. If such a provision is not received, the holder of the right of real property grants the right to dispose of the real property in question by foreclosing on it in a manner similar to a mortgage.

2. The right of development (superficies), which is understood as the right of ownership and use of a land plot for the construction of a building or structure on it and their subsequent operation.

Historically, the institution of superficies arose as a response to the need to regulate relations between landowners and developers interested in maintaining ownership of the properties, they had built without having to acquire the land themselves. According to Roman law, any structure erected on someone else's land was considered an integral part of the land, which prevented developers from exercising their rights to the structures they had built. The introduction of the institution of superficies eliminated this contradiction by securing the developer's property rights to the property they had built while maintaining state ownership of the land.

The introduction of the concept of development rights (superficies) into the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan would fill an existing gap in the regulation of property rights, ensuring a rational balance between the interests of the state as the landowner and the private investor as the developer. Unlike a lease, superficies have a proprietary nature, which gives them greater stability, legal security, and public credibility through state registration.

International experience demonstrates the effectiveness of this model. Superficies

operate successfully in a number of continental European countries—Germany, Switzerland, and Austria—and have also been adopted by the legal systems of Russia and Kazakhstan, demonstrating positive results in terms of investment activity and rational land use.

The main advantages of introducing the superficies system into national legislation include:

1. Investment attractiveness – development rights can be pledged, creating opportunities for long-term bank financing for construction projects.
2. Flexibility of land use – a long term (up to 99 years) ensures stable ownership and use of the land without the need for privatization.
3. Legal certainty and public protection – registration of development rights in the real estate registry eliminates the risk of arbitrary revision of contractual relations.
4. Stimulation of urban infrastructure modernization – the existence of property rights allows for the reconstruction and renovation of facilities without loss of rights to them.

In modern law, a number of countries are seeing a trend toward the revival of the concept of usufruct—the right to personal use of another person's property. According to this concept, the owner of real property has the right to grant another person the right to possess and use it. This right is personal, inalienable, and not inheritable. The person holding this right (the usufructuary) is entitled to extract fruits and income from the property, provided its essence is preserved, while the owner retains nominal ownership.

By its very nature, usufruct can replace a number of existing limited property rights, such as the right to use residential premises based on a lifelong maintenance contract, as well as the right to use premises by members or former family members of the owner of the residential premises, and other similar structures.

The implementation of the institution of superficies in Uzbekistan's civil legislation will strengthen the system of property rights, attract investment in construction and infrastructure, and improve the efficient use of state land resources without alienation. This step is consistent with the strategic reform goals outlined in the "New Uzbekistan" Concept and will be an important element in harmonizing national civil legislation with modern doctrines of continental law.

According to many scholars, emphyteusis and superficies in Roman law are property rights based on the hereditary use of another's land or a building erected on another's land.

Superficies, however, primarily relate to the right to build on another's land and to

operate the structures erected. Unlike emphyteusis, superficies are not associated with the obligation to improve the land—its primary purpose is the construction and use of buildings.

In German law, a similar institution is implemented in the form of hereditary building rights (*das Erbbaurecht*), regulated by the Law on Hereditary Building Rights of January 15, 1919. This institution allows a person (the developer) to construct and use buildings on someone else's land for a long term—usually up to 99 years. This legal mechanism was created to address land shortages and to enable construction without the need to alienate the land.

The main feature of hereditary building rights is the separation of ownership of the land and the right to the building: the land remains the property of the landowner, while the right to the building belongs to the developer and can be inherited.

From a scientific perspective, this institution represents a compromise between the interests of landowners and developers, facilitating urban development without changing land ownership. Landowners retain ownership and receive income through periodic payments, while developers implement construction projects without purchasing the land. This is particularly relevant in the context of urbanization and rising real estate values, making hereditary development rights an important element of land regulation in Germany.

In French civil law, a similar institution is enshrined in Articles 552 and 553 of the French Civil Code (*Code Civil*), which regulate the right of superficies (*droit de superficie*). These provisions allow for the separation of ownership of land and buildings erected on it, enabling long-term use of the land without transferring ownership. In practice, this right is widely used for the efficient management of land resources, particularly in urban development.

Furthermore, the institution of superficies has developed in other continental European countries, where it is used for long-term land use and construction without alienation of ownership. The inclusion of superficies in civil codes allows for more efficient land management, stimulates the development of the real estate market and investment activity, while ensuring legal protection for all parties.

The Concept for the Development of Civil Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan envisages strengthening the institution of property rights and expanding property rights. Since the right of development as an independent, limited property right to a land plot is currently not enshrined in national civil legislation, studying international experience in regulating it in countries with continental legal systems appears to be a

particularly relevant and promising area of legal reform.

Given the ongoing transformations in Uzbekistan's society and economy, as well as the introduction of innovations into all spheres of modern life, it seems appropriate to develop a comprehensive, internally consistent system of legal regulation of property relations in civil legislation. Such a system should include:

Establishing special rules governing the emergence, modification, termination, exercise, and protection of other property rights;

Enshrining in the Civil Code the general principles governing property rights (their characteristics, system, types, and methods of protection);

Developing a hierarchically coordinated structure of general and special norms;

Harmonizing civil and land legislation on the emergence, exercise, and limitation of property rights to land plots, which, in the context of developing civil turnover, are becoming the most important object of property relations.

The preparation and adoption of a bill amending the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan regarding the regulation of property rights will signal the achievement of a new, qualitatively different level of legal development, which will undoubtedly be a step forward in the evolution of civil law.

The implementation of the superficies concept in the Civil Code will eliminate the existing imbalance between the economic needs of real estate transactions and current legal structures, which do not ensure the necessary stability of property relations. Superficies have the potential to become a key legal instrument, ensuring the long-term and secure use of state-owned land by private investors without the need for privatization.

A study of international experience (Germany, France, Switzerland, Austria, Russia, and Kazakhstan) shows that the property-law nature of superficies allows for a harmonious reconciliation of the public interest in preserving state ownership of land with the private interests of developers. Its implementation facilitates the development of construction and investment activities, the renewal of urban infrastructure, and the creation of a favorable legal environment for sustainable economic growth.

For the legal system of Uzbekistan, the introduction of superficies will mark a new stage in the development of civil legislation, aimed at establishing a stable and predictable legal regime for land use. This will ensure the harmonization of national legislation with the legal systems of developed countries in continental Europe, where the institution of development law is a crucial element of real estate regulation.

Thus, the inclusion of provisions on development rights in the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan will not only eliminate existing gaps in the regulation of property

relations but will also be a significant step toward modernizing the civil legal system, strengthening legal guarantees for private initiative, and realizing the strategic goals of the "New Uzbekistan" concept.

Consequently, the development of the superficies institution and the introduction of other modern property rights represent a logical step in the evolution of Uzbekistan's civil legislation, aimed at creating a more flexible and effective system of legal regulation of property relations. This will not only strengthen the legal guarantees of participants in property transactions but will also contribute to the realization of the innovative potential of the national economy.

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From Isolation to Integration: Uzbekistan's WTO Accession Journey.

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Abstract: Uzbekistan is striving to secure membership in the World Trade Organization (WTO) after what has become one of the longest accession processes in the organization's history. The prolonged negotiations stemmed largely from former President Islam Karimov's inward-looking and interventionist economic policies, while the renewed momentum since 2016 reflects President Shavkat Mirziyoyev's outward-oriented reform agenda. The prospects of accession—and its potential value—ultimately depend on the government's commitment to genuine economic transformation. Should Uzbekistan successfully shift from reliance on resource exports and heavily protected manufacturing toward a more diversified, competitive economy, WTO membership could bring significant benefits. Conversely, if structural reforms remain limited, accession will likely be delayed and its advantages minimal. This paper traces the trajectory of Uzbekistan's accession bid since its 1994 application, situates it within the evolution of the WTO itself, and evaluates the current status of negotiations, key challenges to completion, and the potential costs and benefits of membership.

Introduction

The World Trade Organization stands as the cornerstone of the modern global trading system, governing approximately 98% of world trade through its 166 member states. For countries outside this framework, accession represents not merely a diplomatic milestone but a fundamental choice about economic orientation and integration into global value chains. Uzbekistan's WTO accession journey, spanning three decades since its initial 1994 application, offers a compelling case study of how domestic political economy considerations can shape—and reshape—a nation's approach to trade liberalization and international economic integration.

The importance of understanding Uzbekistan's prolonged accession process extends beyond the country's borders. As one of the longest WTO accession negotiations in the organization's history, it illuminates the complex interplay between domestic reform imperatives and international institutional requirements. For Uzbekistan, a landlocked Central Asian nation of more than 38 million people with substantial natural resource endowments and a legacy of Soviet-era industrial policy, WTO membership carries profound implications. The country faces the classic developmental dilemma: whether to maintain protective barriers that shield domestic industries from foreign competition or

embrace trade liberalization that promises efficiency gains but threatens established interests and employment in protected sectors. This tension between short-term adjustment costs and long-term developmental benefits lies at the heart of Uzbekistan's hesitant march toward WTO accession.

Existing research on WTO accession has identified several key patterns and challenges faced by transitional economies. Rose (2004) famously questioned whether WTO membership significantly increases trade, finding surprisingly weak evidence of a "WTO effect" on trade volumes, though subsequent studies by Subramanian and Wei (2007) revealed that this effect is concentrated among developed countries with strong institutional capacity. Tang and Wei (2009) demonstrated that the accession process itself can serve as a credible commitment device for domestic reforms, potentially more valuable than membership per se. Studies of Central Asian economies' integration into global trade systems (Pomfret, 2019; Raballand, 2003) have highlighted the particular challenges faced by landlocked countries with underdeveloped infrastructure and heavy reliance on natural resource exports. Research on infant industry protection (Melitz, 2003; Harrison and Rodríguez-Clare, 2010) suggests that while temporary protection can theoretically facilitate industrial development, in practice such policies often become entrenched and fail to produce internationally competitive industries. Meanwhile, the literature on strategic trade policy and optimal tariffs (Brander and Spencer, 1985; Bagwell and Staiger, 1999) indicates that these arguments, while theoretically sound for large economies with market power, rarely justify protectionism for small, developing nations. Uzbekistan's case has received limited scholarly attention relative to its theoretical significance, with most existing work focusing on either the Soviet legacy (Pomfret, 2000) or the post-2016 reform period without systematically analyzing the economic rationales underlying the country's shifting approach to WTO accession.

This paper addresses a critical research question: What explains the dramatic shift in Uzbekistan's approach to WTO accession, and how do traditional arguments against trade liberalization—including domestic market failures, distributional concerns, infant industry protection, strategic trade policy considerations—weigh against the comparative advantage gains that membership might offer? By examining Uzbekistan's three-decade accession journey through the lens of both protectionist rationales and liberal trade theory, this study seeks to determine whether the country's historical reluctance was economically justified or primarily reflected political economy considerations, and whether current reform momentum represents a genuine commitment to economic transformation or merely tactical positioning. The analysis traces the trajectory from President Karimov's inward-looking economic policy policies through President Mirziyoyev's liberalization agenda, evaluating the substantive progress in negotiations, remaining obstacles to completion, and the realistic costs and benefits that accession would entail for an economy still heavily dependent on commodity exports and protected manufacturing sectors. Ultimately, this research contributes to broader debates about the appropriate pace and sequencing of trade

liberalization for transitional economies, the effectiveness of WTO conditionality in driving domestic reforms, and the conditions under which international institutional integration delivers on its promised benefits.

A very brief history of GATT/WTO System.

When the proposed International Trade Organization (ITO) was stillborn after World War 2, in part because of opposition in the US Senate, the GATT metamorphosed from just a trade agreement into an international organization that administered the agreement and provided the forum where nations could promote trade liberalization(Hollis, 2022). The GATT continued to play that role as an institution until WTO came into being in January 1995. The GATT agreement was incorporated into the WTO framework as an important trade agreement with key principles and provisions.

The purpose of GATT was to promote trade liberalization through the elimination of both tariff barriers and nontariff barriers (such as quotas or other quantitative trade restriction). Members had four fundamental obligations. Upon joining the GATT, members undertook to (1) apply trade barriers on a nondiscriminatory basis; (2) limit tariffs on items at the levels set forth in the GATT tariff schedules; (3) refrain from circumvention trade concessions through the use of other barriers to trade; and (4) settle trade conflicts via consultation and a special dispute resolution process.

Central to nondiscrimination are two principles: most-favored nation treatment, and the national treatment obligation. The GATT agreement starts with an unconditional most-favored-nation provision. “Any advantage, favour, privilege or immunity granted by any contracting party to any product originating in or destined for any country shall be accorded immediately and unconditionally to the like product originating in or destined for the territories of all other contracting parties.”(GATT,1994). In short, it prohibits discrimination between goods from different foreign countries. As for the national treatment obligation, the principle prohibits discrimination between goods that are domestically produced and those that are imported.

According to the report of the first Warwick Commission, there are four key functions of the WTO: (1) reducing discrimination and furthering market-access opportunities in international commerce. The successes of the GATT/WTO system are exemplified in the progressive liberalization of tariffs since 1947 and the near-universal membership of the WTO today. The entry requirements faced by new WTO Members are stringent; mirroring the significant recent broadening of the multilateral trading system’s substantive remit. Yet the fact that .. countries have nonetheless chosen to meet them since 1995 suggests that they see benefits in joining the system. (2)Formulating rules for the conduct of international trade. The depth and range of rules on cross-border trade and investment have grown significantly over the 60-year life of the GATT/WTO. Parties to the agreement have not always agreed on the desirable content of the rules but nobody contests the value of multilateral rules in fostering certainty and predictability in trade and

in helping to dilute the role of power in determining trade outcomes. (3)Promoting transparency in national laws and regulations. Through its various agreements, the GATT/WTO has enhanced the transparency of commerce-related national laws and regulations through the requirement for Members to publish changes to their trade measures and notify any changes in rules. (4)Settling commercial disputes. The Dispute Settlement Understanding of the WTO has given an unprecedented enforceability to agreements. It is one of the most successful, and the busiest, state-to-state dispute settlement systems in the history of international law.(Warwick Comission, 2007). Simply put: the World Trade Organization deals with the rules of trade between nations at a global or near-global level.

Uzbekistan's WTO Accession

Initial Application and Early Reform Period (1994-2016)

Uzbekistan became the first Central Asian nation to seek World Trade Organization membership when it submitted its application in December 1994. The WTO established a Working Party on December 21, 1994, to review the application. During the initial phase of President Karimov's tenure (1994-1996), Uzbekistan implemented market-oriented reforms consistent with WTO accession objectives. This liberalization effort, however, proved ephemeral.

When deteriorating terms of trade—particularly declining cotton prices—negatively impacted the country's export revenues, the government reversed course in 1996. It abandoned currency convertibility commitments and instituted an import substitution industrialization strategy. This policy framework, which became known as the "Uzbek model of development," employed differential exchange rate mechanisms: restricting foreign currency access for "non-essential" consumer goods while providing preferential conversion at overvalued official rates for "priority" imports such as capital equipment and socially significant products.

The 1998 economic crisis affecting former Soviet states and Asian economies reinforced the government's protectionist orientation. Consequently, WTO accession ceased to be a policy priority, and negotiations entered a prolonged hiatus.

The import substitution program effectively concentrated foreign trade control in government hands, with privileged firms receiving preferential currency conversion access. The substantial disparity between official and parallel market exchange rates created opportunities for rent-seeking behavior, as entities could arbitrage the spread by diverting converted foreign currency to black market transactions rather than utilizing it for legitimate imports.

A brief period of renewed liberalization emerged in 2003 when authorities eliminated foreign exchange restrictions and implemented limited trade opening measures. This resulted in substantial expansion of both trade volumes and overall economic activity.

WTO negotiations experienced temporary momentum during this window, with multiple Working Party sessions convened. However, the 2007-2008 global financial crisis severely affected Uzbekistan's economy, prompting the government to re-impose exchange controls by restricting foreign currency transactions to state-authorized dealers exclusively. Despite external recommendations to integrate WTO accession into broader economic reform initiatives, authorities tightened exchange regulations. Following the Working Party's final session in October 2005, negotiations remained dormant.

President Karimov pursued an inward-looking and interventionist development paradigm characterized by incrementalism and extensive state involvement in economic activity, perceiving limited benefit in WTO membership. Karimov, who held formal training in Soviet economics and previously directed Uzbekistan's central planning apparatus, served as the principal architect of the Uzbek developmental model. This framework operated on the premise that the state would maintain a directive role throughout the economic transition period. Under the stated objective of "safeguarding domestic industry," the administration imposed restrictive import tariffs, export quotas, and licensing requirements that effectively foreclosed foreign enterprise access to Uzbek markets. The automotive sector illustrates this approach: imported vehicles—including passenger cars, buses, and commercial trucks—faced substantial customs duties that varied according to manufacturing year, country of origin, and engine displacement, thereby providing protective barriers for the emerging domestic automotive industry.

A New Hope

Under President Shavkat Mirziyoyev's leadership since 2016, Uzbekistan has undergone a fundamental transformation in its economic development strategy, abandoning the protectionist "Uzbek model" in favor of comprehensive market liberalization and active pursuit of WTO membership. This policy reversal, characterized by currency convertibility, trade liberalization, and institutional reforms, represents not merely a technical adjustment to trade policy but a strategic reorientation toward economic openness and integration into the global trading system—a shift that reflects both domestic imperatives for sustainable development and recognition that WTO accession serves as both catalyst and anchor for irreversible economic reform.

Mirziyoyev's administration initiated sweeping economic reforms almost immediately upon taking office. The September 2017 currency liberalization—which unified the official and black market exchange rates and established full convertibility of the Uzbek sum—represented the most significant policy departure from the Karimov era (World Bank, 2018). This reform eliminated the parallel exchange rate system that had fostered corruption and distorted economic incentives for over two decades.

The government systematically dismantled trade barriers, reducing the number of goods subject to import licensing from over 40% of tariff lines to less than 5% by 2020 (OECD,

2019). Customs procedures were streamlined, and the "Uzbek Register" system—which had restricted imports of consumer goods—was abolished in 2018 (European Bank for Reconstruction and Development, 2019).

Mirziyoyev explicitly prioritized WTO membership in his Development Strategy for 2017-2021, marking the first time since the early 1990s that WTO accession appeared as a formal policy objective (Presidential Decree No. UP-4947, 2017). The Working Party, dormant since 2005, reconvened in July 2020, signaling renewed momentum in accession negotiations (WTO, 2020).

The government's commitment was formalized through Presidential Decree No 181, signed on June 5, 2023, "On measures to accelerate the process of accession of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the World Trade Organization" (Presidential Decree No.181, 2023). This decree established a comprehensive institutional framework for managing the accession process, including:

- Creation of a Government Commission on WTO Accession, chaired by the Deputy Prime Minister
- Assignment of specific ministerial responsibilities for completing technical requirements
- Establishment of timelines for legislative harmonization with WTO agreements
- Allocation of budgetary resources for capacity building and technical assistance programs

In a demonstration of high-level political commitment, President Mirziyoyev appointed **Azizbek Urunov** as a chief negotiator with primary responsibility for overseeing WTO accession negotiations in January 2023. Urunov, a career trade diplomat with extensive experience in multilateral negotiations and previous service in Uzbekistan's mission to the WTO in Geneva, brought specialized expertise to accelerate the technical and political dimensions of the accession process. His appointment signaled the government's recognition that successful WTO accession required dedicated leadership with deep knowledge of WTO protocols and international trade law (Ministry of Investment, Industry and Trade, 2023).

Under Urunov's coordination, Uzbekistan intensified engagement with the WTO Secretariat, established bilateral working groups with key WTO members including the United States, European Union, China, and Japan, and accelerated the drafting of legal commitments required for accession. The appointment of a senior official specifically tasked with WTO accession represents an unprecedented level of bureaucratic prioritization compared to the Karimov era, when WTO negotiations were handled intermittently without dedicated high-level oversight.

The government established technical working groups across relevant ministries and

engaged in capacity-building programs with the WTO Secretariat, UNCTAD, and bilateral partners to align domestic legislation with WTO requirements (Ministry of Investments and Foreign Trade of Uzbekistan, 2021). By 2024, Uzbekistan had submitted its revised Memorandum on the Foreign Trade Regime and initiated bilateral market access negotiations with key WTO members.

A critical component of Uzbekistan's WTO accession strategy under Mirziyoyev has been the comprehensive legal harmonization process—the systematic review, amendment, and adoption of domestic legislation to ensure compliance with WTO agreements and protocols. This process represents one of the most technically demanding aspects of accession and demonstrates the government's commitment to substantive rather than cosmetic reform.

The harmonization process encompasses alignment with all core WTO agreements, including the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (GATT 1994), the General Agreement on Trade in Services (GATS), the Agreement on Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights (TRIPS), and various plurilateral agreements. The Government Commission established under the 2022 Presidential Decree created specialized inter-ministerial working groups for each major agreement, tasked with conducting "gap analyses" to identify inconsistencies between existing Uzbek legislation and WTO requirements (Presidential Decree No. UP-181, 2022).

Key Areas of Legislative Reform:

Uzbekistan adopted a new Customs Code in 2021 (Law No. ZRU-661, January 20, 2021) that incorporated WTO Customs Valuation Agreement principles, replacing the previous system that allowed arbitrary valuation by customs officials. The new code mandates transaction value as the primary basis for customs valuation and establishes an independent appeals mechanism for importers contesting customs decisions—a fundamental requirement under Article X of GATT 1994 (Customs Code of Uzbekistan, 2021). Also, The government has also implemented measures consistent with the WTO Trade Facilitation Agreement (TFA), including:

- Establishment of a National Committee on Trade Facilitation in 2020 (Presidential Resolution No. PP-4611, 2020)
- Introduction of a "single window" system for import/export documentation, reducing clearance times from an average of 15 days in 2016 to 3 days by 2023 (World Bank Doing Business Indicators, 2023)
- Publication of all customs regulations and advance rulings in a centralized online portal, ensuring transparency as required under TFA Article 1 (State Customs Committee, 2023)

Harmonization with the SPS Agreement has required fundamental reform of Uzbekistan's

food safety and agricultural quarantine systems. New legislation adopted in 2022-2023 includes:

- Law "On Food Safety" (December 2022), establishing science-based risk assessment procedures aligned with Codex Alimentarius standards (Law No. ZRU-788, 2022)
- Restructuring of the State Veterinary and Phytosanitary Service to separate regulatory functions from inspection and certification, eliminating conflicts of interest (Presidential Resolution No. PP-292, 2023)
- Creation of an SPS Enquiry Point as required under SPS Agreement Article 7, to respond to requests from trading partners regarding Uzbekistan's SPS measures (Ministry of Agriculture, 2023)
- Notification procedures for new SPS measures, with comment periods for affected stakeholders—a requirement under SPS Agreement Article 7 (SPS National Notification Authority, 2024).

Uzbekistan has developed new legislation and institutional capacity for WTO-consistent trade remedies:

- Law "On Protection of Economic Competition and Restriction of Monopolistic Activity" (2020), incorporating provisions on anti-dumping and countervailing measures aligned with WTO Anti-Dumping Agreement and SCM Agreement (Law No. ZRU-634, 2020)
- Establishment of the Competition Committee under the Ministry of Investment, Industry and Trade as the designated investigating authority for trade remedies (Presidential Resolution No. PP-4742, 2020)
- Adoption of detailed procedural rules for trade remedy investigations, including transparency requirements, rights of interested parties, and judicial review—core elements of WTO trade remedy agreements (Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 528, 2021)
- Capacity building through UNCTAD technical assistance on conducting dumping margin calculations, subsidy investigations, and injury determinations consistent with WTO jurisprudence (UNCTAD Trade Remedies Programme, 2022-2024).

By late 2024, Uzbekistan had completed legislative reviews across all 18 major WTO agreements, with implementing regulations adopted for most areas (WTO Working Party, 2024). Independent assessments by the WTO Secretariat and multilateral institutions indicate substantial progress:

- The European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD) Legal Transition Programme rated Uzbekistan's WTO compliance at 7.5/10 in 2024, up from 3.2/10 in 2016—the most dramatic improvement among post-Soviet states (EBRD Legal Indicators, 2024)
- The World Bank's Trade Restrictiveness Index for Uzbekistan declined from 18.4 in 2016 to 8.7 in 2024, reflecting reduced tariff and non-tariff barriers (World Bank Trade Indicators, 2024)
- WTO Working Party members have acknowledged progress while identifying remaining concerns, particularly regarding full implementation of subsidy notification requirements and judicial enforcement capacity (Working Party Report, 2024).

Risks and Opportunities.

1. Domestic Market Failures

Paul Krugman and Maurice Obstfeld (2022) explain that when a domestic market fails to function efficiently, the “first-best” solution is to correct the market failure directly through targeted domestic policies. However, when such policies are politically or administratively infeasible, governments may use trade policy—such as tariffs, subsidies, or quotas—as a “second-best” intervention to offset the effects of those failures.

For instance, if a country experiences high unemployment due to rigid wages, a temporary subsidy for labour-intensive industries may improve welfare more effectively than a tariff, which would distort consumer prices and trade flows. Thus, while trade protection may sometimes raise welfare in theory, it is rarely the most efficient solution in practice. Moreover, misdiagnosing the nature of market failure can lead to ineffective or even counterproductive trade policies (Krugman & Obstfeld, 2022).

The implication is that trade liberalization should proceed only when domestic markets are sufficiently flexible and adaptive. Otherwise, liberalization may amplify existing inefficiencies instead of correcting them.

2. Distribution

Uzbekistan's WTO accession creates a fundamental distribution problem. While total national wealth would increase through trade liberalization, this doesn't mean everyone benefits equally.

The issue is straightforward: WTO membership will create clear winners and losers.

Winners include export industries like textiles and cotton, plus consumers who pay less for imports. Losers include workers in uncompetitive industries who lose jobs when cheaper foreign goods arrive, and small businesses that can't compete with international companies.

Economic theory says winners gain more than losers lose, so winners could compensate losers and still profit. But this compensation rarely happens in practice. The textile exporter earning higher profits won't voluntarily pay the unemployed factory worker displaced by Chinese imports.

This creates two possible justifications for WTO accession despite unequal distribution. First, Uzbekistan might accept the trade-off if gains flow to those who need them most, like poor consumers benefiting from lower prices. However, if losers are politically important groups or concentrated in specific regions, this becomes harder to justify.

Second, Uzbekistan could liberalize trade while using other tools to redistribute gains. Instead of blocking WTO accession to protect certain industries, the government could strengthen unemployment benefits, create worker retraining programs, improve social safety nets, and use tax revenue from growing sectors to support affected communities. This approach helps all vulnerable citizens, not just workers in protected industries, and avoids raising prices for everyone through tariffs.

The practical challenge is that Uzbekistan has limited resources for such redistribution. Without adequate social programs to compensate losers, affected workers and industries will oppose liberalization. They face real losses while promised compensation remains theoretical. This political opposition could derail WTO accession entirely, even though economists can prove overall national wealth would increase.

The distribution problem is why moving from trade theory to actual policy is difficult. Aggregate gains don't address specific losses faced by specific people in specific regions. Uzbekistan must build redistribution mechanisms to make liberalization politically viable, or domestic opposition will block the reform.

3. Infant Industry

Uzbekistan might argue that certain domestic industries need temporary protection before WTO accession to develop competitive capabilities. For example, its manufacturing, pharmaceutical, or technology sectors might have future potential but currently lack the scale and experience to compete with established foreign firms. The infant industry argument suggests protecting these sectors temporarily could allow them to mature into globally competitive industries.

However, this argument faces serious problems in Uzbekistan's case. First, protected industries may never actually grow up and could demand support indefinitely without improving. Second, the government must correctly identify which industries truly have potential versus which are bad investments—a difficult task given limited information and potential political pressures. Third, if these industries were genuinely viable, private investors should fund them. If capital markets won't invest, this may indicate the ventures aren't actually worthwhile unless there's a genuine capital market failure in Uzbekistan.

Fourth, even if protection is justified, WTO rules restrict the trade barriers Uzbekistan might want to use. Subsidies are economically superior because they support local industries without raising consumer prices, but Uzbekistan has limited fiscal resources for subsidies as a developing country.

The key question is whether delaying WTO accession to protect potential infant industries will create competitive sectors or simply waste resources supporting industries that never become viable. Evidence from other developing countries shows many infant industry policies failed, with protected sectors remaining dependent on government support indefinitely.

Most economists would argue Uzbekistan should join the WTO rather than risk resources on protecting industries that may never mature. The certain costs of continued protection—higher consumer prices, inefficient resource allocation, foregone WTO benefits—likely outweigh the uncertain gains from potentially developing competitive industries.

4. Strategic Trade Policy

Uzbekistan might argue that strategic trade policy justifies delaying WTO accession to protect and subsidize domestic firms in industries where only a few global players can exist profitably. For example, Uzbekistan could target industries like specialized mining equipment, agricultural machinery, automotive manufacturing, or pharmaceuticals where economies of scale matter and capturing early market position determines long-term success.

The logic would be that by subsidizing Uzbek firms or protecting the domestic market, the government ensures local companies achieve sufficient scale to compete globally. A protected home market could provide the sales volume needed for Uzbek manufacturers to become regionally competitive, potentially capturing profits that would otherwise go to foreign firms.

However, this argument is extremely weak for Uzbekistan. First, the country lacks the

resources for the massive subsidies required to compete in scale-intensive industries. Strategic trade policy works for wealthy countries like the US subsidizing Boeing or the EU supporting Airbus, but Uzbekistan's limited fiscal capacity cannot match the support levels needed to create global champions in capital-intensive industries.

Second, Uzbekistan's domestic market is relatively small. Strategic trade policy using trade barriers requires a large home market to provide sufficient scale. With roughly 36 million people and lower purchasing power, Uzbekistan's market alone cannot generate the volumes needed for firms to achieve global competitiveness in most scale-intensive industries.

Third, governments must accurately identify which industries to support—an extremely difficult task. Uzbekistan has limited information and analytical capacity to determine which sectors genuinely offer strategic opportunities versus which would waste resources. Political pressures would likely lead to supporting politically connected industries rather than genuinely promising ones.

Fourth, WTO rules restrict many strategic trade policy tools. The subsidies and trade barriers needed for strategic intervention often violate WTO commitments. If Uzbekistan wants to pursue strategic trade policy, WTO membership would constrain its options.

However, the broader point is that strategic trade policy makes little sense for Uzbekistan's development stage. This approach suits advanced economies trying to dominate high-tech, capital-intensive industries with few global competitors. Uzbekistan's comparative advantage lies in labor-intensive manufacturing, agriculture, textiles, and resource extraction—sectors where many competitors can coexist and strategic intervention is less relevant.

For Uzbekistan, joining the WTO and integrating into global value chains offers far more realistic development prospects than attempting strategic trade policy. The country would benefit more from attracting foreign investment, accessing export markets, and specializing in sectors where it has genuine competitive potential rather than trying to create national champions in industries dominated by firms from much wealthier countries with far greater government support capacity.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Uzbekistan's three-decade journey toward WTO accession represents a fundamental shift from isolation to integration. The dramatic transition from President Karimov's protectionist "Uzbek model" to President Mirziyoyev's liberalization agenda reflects recognition that isolation guarantees stagnation while openness offers sustainable

development prospects despite real adjustment costs.

The traditional arguments against trade liberalization—domestic market failures, distributional concerns, infant industry protection, and strategic trade policy—prove largely inapplicable to Uzbekistan's context. Trade barriers represent inefficient second-best solutions to market failures that should be addressed directly. The distribution problem is real but requires social safety nets rather than protectionism that harms consumers. Infant industry arguments founder on limited fiscal capacity and poor government track records of identifying winners. Strategic trade policy makes little sense for a developing country whose comparative advantages lie in labor-intensive sectors rather than scale-intensive industries suited to wealthy economies.

The comprehensive legal reforms since 2016—customs modernization, trade facilitation, SPS compliance, and trade remedy legislation—demonstrate genuine political commitment. Yet significant implementation challenges remain, requiring concrete actions from both Uzbekistan and its international partners to ensure accession delivers on its promised benefits.

The most critical requirement is developing robust redistribution mechanisms to address the distribution problem. Uzbekistan must establish adequate unemployment insurance, industry-specific retraining programs for displaced workers, universal healthcare and education access, and regional development funds for areas disproportionately affected by liberalization. Without these mechanisms, affected workers will rationally oppose reform, potentially derailing accession. International financial institutions should provide concessional financing specifically for social safety net development, recognizing Uzbekistan's fiscal constraints make adequate domestic financing unlikely without external support.

Rather than sudden comprehensive liberalization, Uzbekistan should adopt phased implementation with longer transition periods for sensitive sectors, pilot programs in specific industries or special economic zones, and real-time monitoring to identify problems early. Where infant industry considerations genuinely apply, the government must shift from trade barriers to targeted subsidies for promising exporters, R&D with spillover benefits, and infrastructure investment that benefits all industries rather than protecting specific firms.

WTO membership requires effective implementation, not just legal compliance. Uzbekistan must invest in training judges and customs officials, strengthen anti-corruption oversight of trade agencies, expand transparency mechanisms, and build permanent technical capacity within ministries rather than relying on external consultants. The WTO Secretariat, UNCTAD, and bilateral partners should provide sustained technical assistance

with explicit capacity transfer objectives.

Successful accession requires engaging stakeholders early and continuously, providing tangible compensation to affected groups, clearly communicating benefits to the general population, and building political coalitions supporting reform. This includes coordinating WTO accession with broader Central Asian economic integration to create regional support for Uzbekistan's reform agenda.

WTO members conducting bilateral negotiations should grant adequate transition periods, ensure Uzbekistan benefits from special and differential treatment flexibilities, and reciprocate market opening with genuine access to developed country markets for textiles and agricultural products where Uzbekistan has competitive potential. Multilateral development banks should prioritize infrastructure lending that reduces Uzbekistan's landlocked disadvantage.

Uzbekistan's WTO accession ultimately tests whether trade liberalization can serve transitional economies' development needs when properly managed. The "Uzbek model" promised development without liberalization's disruptions but delivered stagnation, corruption, and missed opportunities. President Mirziyoyev's reform agenda embraces openness while creating mechanisms to manage adjustment costs.

Success requires not just completing WTO negotiations but building the institutional infrastructure—social safety nets, implementation capacity, political coalitions—that converts market access into shared prosperity. The recommendations above are not optional enhancements but essential prerequisites. Without adequate social safety nets, political opposition will block reform. Without institutional capacity, legal commitments remain paper compliance. Without strategic sequencing, sudden liberalization creates unnecessary disruption. Without international support, Uzbekistan's constraints prevent optimal implementation.

If Uzbekistan accomplishes this transformation, it will demonstrate that late WTO accession, properly managed, can accelerate development through export diversification, foreign investment, technology transfer, and integration into global value chains. If it fails—through incomplete accession or accession without adequate preparation—it will reinforce skepticism about whether international institutional integration truly serves developing countries' interests, potentially returning the country to protectionism under populist pressure.

The stakes extend beyond Uzbekistan. Central Asia's economic future depends substantially on whether regional economies can integrate effectively into global markets while managing domestic adjustment costs. As the region's most populous country with

the longest WTO accession process, Uzbekistan serves as a test case for the entire region.

The analysis clearly indicates WTO accession offers net benefits despite real adjustment costs. The question is whether Uzbekistan and its international partners will invest the resources, build the institutions, and maintain the political commitment necessary to make accession successful. The comprehensive legal reforms since 2016 demonstrate technical capability; now comes the harder work of ensuring aggregate gains translate into broadly shared prosperity. Only sustained commitment to building redistribution mechanisms, strengthening institutions, managing political economy, and securing international support will determine whether Uzbekistan's long journey from isolation to integration ultimately succeeds.

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NEW DOCTRINES IN CONTRACT LAW

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Contracts encompass every sphere of our lives. In the modern era, new electronic forms of contracts have emerged. Although the current Civil Code does not explicitly define the “electronic form” as a separate category, the newly drafted (but not yet officially adopted) version of the Code recognizes three forms of contracts: oral, written, and electronic.

Time, form, and content — the evolution of these three concepts over time serves as the foundation for creating new legal norms and eliminating “dead” rules from normative legal acts. Consequently, new types of contracts and formalization methods unfamiliar to the general public — but increasingly common among youth and certain social groups (including entrepreneurs) — have appeared. As legal relations arise, the demand for regulatory mechanisms grows. Indeed, not all relations can be governed by law, but most contractual relations can and should be regulated by civil law norms. This requires scientific research and doctrinal development.

Today, several new doctrines and concepts enrich the institution of contracts, including:

Smart contracts

Platform contracts

Digital consent

The expansion of the “good faith” principle

Asymmetric contracts and consumer protection

Algorithmic contracts

Reinterpretation of force majeure and hardship concepts (in the post-COVID era), among others.

Each of these doctrines and concepts has its own distinctive features. Let us examine the most widely applied ones.

Smart Contracts

In the contemporary digital economy, **smart contracts** have emerged as one of the most innovative and transformative developments in the field of civil and commercial law.

A smart contract can be broadly defined as a **self-executing agreement** in which the terms and conditions are written directly into lines of computer code. Once certain pre-programmed conditions are met, the contract executes itself automatically, without the need for human intervention.

The concept was first introduced by Nick Szabo in the 1990s, but it gained widespread recognition with the rise of **blockchain technology**, particularly on platforms such as **Ethereum**, **Solana**, and other decentralized systems. These technological infrastructures allow for the creation, storage, and execution of smart contracts in a secure, transparent, and tamper-resistant environment.

Unlike traditional contracts, which require manual performance and enforcement through legal institutions, smart contracts operate through an **automated mechanism**. For example, when a specific condition is fulfilled — such as payment confirmation — the programmed system triggers the corresponding action, such as releasing goods, transferring digital assets, or issuing access rights.

This automation eliminates intermediaries, reduces transaction costs, and ensures that contractual obligations are fulfilled **immediately and irreversibly** once the code conditions are met. Such features make smart contracts especially useful in **financial technology (fintech)**, **logistics**, **insurance**, and **digital identity systems**.

Smart contracts offer several significant advantages:

1. **Efficiency and Speed** – Transactions are executed automatically without delays.
2. **Accuracy** – The coded terms eliminate ambiguities inherent in human interpretation.
3. **Transparency** – All parties can verify contract performance on the blockchain.
4. **Security** – The decentralized nature of blockchain ensures that data cannot be altered retroactively.
5. **Cost Reduction** – By eliminating intermediaries such as banks, brokers, or notaries, transaction costs are minimized.

Despite these advantages, smart contracts also raise a number of **complex legal challenges**. The foremost issue concerns their **recognition within traditional legal frameworks**. Civil law systems are built upon written text, consent, and interpretation, whereas smart contracts function through immutable code. Questions therefore arise as to how to determine **intent**, **validity**, and **enforceability** of such digital agreements.

Moreover, **interpretation difficulties** occur when disputes arise — particularly if the contract's code does not accurately reflect the parties' actual intentions. Since the blockchain code executes automatically, even programming errors (known as *bugs*) can lead to unintended and irreversible consequences.

There is also a **jurisdictional problem**: smart contracts are decentralized and may operate across multiple legal systems, raising uncertainty about which national law governs them and which court has jurisdiction over disputes.

Platform Contracts

In the digital age, the rapid expansion of online platforms has profoundly transformed the traditional understanding of contractual relations. **Platform contracts** represent a new form of agreement concluded between users and platform operators within the framework of digital environments such as e-commerce websites, mobile applications, and social media platforms. These platforms act as intermediaries that connect service providers or sellers with consumers, facilitating contractual relations through automated processes.

The term "*online platform*" generally refers to digital infrastructures such as search engines, social media networks, electronic commerce platforms, store applications, price comparison websites, advertising networks, and similar technological interfaces. Through these platforms, millions of daily transactions occur between individuals and businesses, creating a complex web of legal relations that demand precise regulation.

When a consumer places an order for goods or services via an online platform, the contractual relationship is primarily governed by the **agreement between the user and the platform operator**. This contract — often referred to as a *platform use agreement* — specifies how the platform is to be used, defines the rights and obligations of both parties, and sets out the terms governing access, data use, and payment procedures. However, once the consumer orders a product or service offered by a third-party provider, a **direct contractual relationship** arises between the consumer and that provider, while the user-platform agreement remains limited to the framework of platform use.

This dual-layer contractual structure — between user and platform, and between user and supplier — has become a source of numerous legal disputes worldwide. The central issue concerns the **liability of the platform operator** when a supplier or service provider violates consumer rights. For example, disputes have arisen on global platforms such as **Uber, Amazon, and Airbnb**, where determining whether the platform bears responsibility for damages caused by independent providers remains a matter of ongoing legal debate.

A distinctive feature of platform contracts is their **automated formation**. These agreements are typically concluded electronically through mechanisms such as **click-wrap agreements**, in which users indicate consent by clicking “I agree” or “Accept” buttons. Such actions are considered legally binding expressions of consent, equivalent to a handwritten signature, provided that users have had the opportunity to review the terms and conditions.

In Uzbekistan, the use of online platforms such as **MyTaxi (Yandex Go)**, **Express24**, and **ZoodMall** has become increasingly widespread. Contracts concluded through these platforms are recognized as legally valid under the *Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Electronic Commerce”*. Nevertheless, the **extent of liability** borne by the platform owner or operator remains insufficiently defined in national legislation.

From a legal standpoint, there is a pressing need to **update normative acts** and establish a coherent **legal framework governing platform contracts**. Such a framework should:

1. Define the **legal status** of platform operators;
2. Clarify their **civil and contractual liability** toward users and third parties;
3. Specify their **authority to modify or terminate** the contractual terms; and
4. Establish clear **consumer protection mechanisms**, especially in cases involving hidden fees, unilateral changes to terms, or defective services.

Furthermore, **consumer rights protection** remains a particularly sensitive area in the context of automated digital agreements. Users often encounter unforeseen service charges or ambiguous contract terms, resulting from unilateral modifications made by platform operators. Thus, ensuring transparency, fairness, and accountability in digital contractual relations must become a legislative priority.

In conclusion, platform contracts symbolize the ongoing digital transformation of civil and commercial law. Their growing role in global commerce necessitates the development of specific **civil-law doctrines and statutory regulations** that ensure both the facilitation of innovation and the protection of consumers. As technology continues to advance, the legal system must adapt accordingly — providing a clear, balanced, and technologically informed approach to contractual relations in the online environment.

Digital Consent

In the era of rapid digital transformation, the concept of **digital consent** has become a cornerstone of modern electronic transactions. As more contractual relations shift into the online environment, the traditional understanding of consent — expressed through handwritten signatures or physical presence — is being replaced by **electronic**

confirmation mechanisms. These include clicking an “I agree” button, checking a digital box, entering a verification code, or using biometric identification such as fingerprint or facial recognition.

Digital consent represents an individual’s **voluntary and informed agreement** to the terms of a digital transaction or contract, expressed through an electronic medium. In essence, it is the digital equivalent of a traditional signature, indicating that a person has read, understood, and accepted the terms of the agreement.

From a legal standpoint, the doctrine of digital consent ensures that contracts concluded in cyberspace retain the essential element of **free will** — one of the fundamental principles of contract law. By providing electronic consent, the user confirms their intention to enter into a binding agreement, thereby fulfilling the legal requirement of mutual assent.

This principle is particularly significant in the context of **click-wrap** and **browse-wrap agreements**, where consent is typically given by clicking a button or continuing to use a website after being notified of the terms. Courts in many jurisdictions, including those following civil law and common law traditions, have recognized such forms of consent as legally valid, provided that users have had a reasonable opportunity to read the terms before agreeing.

Digital consent can take several forms, depending on the nature of the transaction and the technological tools employed. The most common methods include:

1. **Check-box confirmation** – The user ticks a box indicating acceptance of terms and conditions.
2. **Click-wrap consent** – The user explicitly clicks “I agree” to accept a digital contract.
3. **Electronic signature (e-signature)** – The user signs a digital document using an approved cryptographic method or digital certificate.
4. **Biometric verification** – Consent is expressed through fingerprint, voice, or facial recognition technology.
5. **One-time passwords (OTP) or SMS codes** – Commonly used for financial or high-security transactions.

Each method serves as a **manifestation of intent**, and, when properly authenticated, it can serve as valid proof of consent in legal proceedings.

Despite its convenience and widespread use, digital consent raises several **legal and evidentiary challenges**. The primary issue concerns the **authenticity and validity** of consent — particularly whether the person who provided electronic confirmation is indeed

the contracting party. Cases involving identity theft, unauthorized access, or automated “bot” activity complicate the assessment of genuine consent.

Another major challenge lies in proving that the user had **adequate knowledge** of the contract terms before agreeing. In many online platforms, terms and conditions are lengthy, complex, or presented in a way that discourages thorough reading. As a result, the legal question arises: can consent truly be considered “informed” if users accept terms without fully understanding them?

Cross-border transactions further complicate the matter, as different jurisdictions apply different standards to digital consent and electronic signatures. Questions of **applicable law** and **jurisdiction** often arise when parties are located in different countries.

Conclusion

Despite the emergence of new doctrines and concepts, several issues remain unresolved and require legal clarification:

Raising public awareness about the concept, methods, and advantages of **smart contracts**.

Clearly defining the **liability of platform owners**, as permanent parties to electronic platform contracts.

Explicitly determining the **legal status, responsibility, and authority of platform operators** to modify contract terms.

Fully establishing **consumer protection mechanisms** for automatic online contracts, including rules governing “unexpected service charges” and “unilateral terms.”

Some features of the application of the norms of international private law to civil relations to regulate obligations arising due to harm caused

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Annotation: The article discusses some of the features of legal regulation of obligations that arise due to harm caused by the so-called delicate commitments in international private law. These features are reviewed on the basis of the norms of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, articles of the Model Civil Code of the CIS member states, provisions of the Agreement on the procedure for resolving disputes related to the implementation of economic activities adopted in Kiev on March 20, 1992, as well as the Convention on Legal Assistance and Legal Assistance Relations for civil, family and criminal cases adopted in Minsk on January 20, 1993. The article formulated proposals for improving the norms of civil law of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the field of regulatory regulation, which arise due to harm, and which are complicated by the participation of the foreign element.

Keywords: obligations as a result of causing harm, tort obligations, foreign element, conflict of laws, honor, merits of a citizen, reputation of a legal entity, harmful consequences, autonomy of the will of the parties when choosing the applicable law.

The goal of the Republic of Uzbekistan is to build an open, democratic, constitutional state with a sustainably developing economy. In a constitutional democratic state, the highest value is placed on the individual, their interests, rights, and freedoms. The Action Strategy for Five Priority Development Areas of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017–2021 provides for ensuring the rule of law, as well as continuing to reform the judicial and legal system, which is aimed at guaranteeing reliable protection of the rights and freedoms of citizens, improving, among other things, civil legislation [1]. Practice shows that the development of modern information and communication technologies, international automobile, rail, and air transportation of both passengers and baggage, mass media, and the development and growth of both domestic and international tourism have increased the occurrence of certain situations associated with the emergence of obligations arising from

harm, as well as conflicts of law and order. For these reasons, the consideration of certain issues of legal regulation of obligations that arise as a result of harm, and which are complicated by the participation of a foreign element, become the object of both normative regulation and interpretation on the part of law enforcement practice, as well as study and research.

Numerous conflict-of-law issues arise when regulating issues related to harm caused by a foreign element. These arise from certain actions, such as cross-border harm to the honor and dignity of an individual, the reputation of a legal entity, as well as harmful consequences caused by the import of defective products from other countries, and other similar situations. In such situations, the choice of applicable law is complicated by the fact that most legal systems in various countries limit or even deny the permissibility of a concept widely used in regulating contractual relations in the sphere of harm. This concept is the concept of the autonomy of the parties in choosing the applicable law.

The Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan contains a section on private international law (Section VI, Chapter 71) [2], which includes certain innovations in the field of conflict of laws regulation of civil law relations, which are complicated by a foreign element in the sphere of torts - this is Article 1194 "Obligations resulting from causing harm". However, the provisions of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan contain only general rules that regulate obligations that arise as a result of causing harm. Unregulated conflict of laws issues are further interpreted both by doctrine and by law enforcement practice. Therefore, when studying the legislative material, as well as law enforcement practice, it is necessary to take into account that the Republic of Uzbekistan has not ratified two conventions that contain conflict of laws rules in the field of regulation of tort relations - these are the Hague Convention on the Law Applicable to Motor Vehicle Accidents, adopted in 1971 and the Hague Convention on the Law Applicable to Manufacturer's Liability, adopted in 1973.

The constantly evolving international division of labor in all forms and the emergence and development of new forms of entrepreneurship complicate the localization of civil legal relations using traditional attachment formulas. An alternative to such "rigid" principles for determining the applicable law is reference to the law of the country with which the legal relationship is most closely connected. Less common is the principle of applying the law "most favorable" to one of the parties. This could be a principle such as *favor laesi*, applied to the injured party in a tortious relationship.

However, new conflict-of-law issues also arise in connection with the expansion of the scope of no-fault civil liability, as well as the use of civil liability insurance, and the "increasing influence of the conflict-of-law principle of 'autonomy of the will of the parties'" [3]. These trends are reflected in the development of legislation in a number of countries, as well as in international contractual practice. Moreover, studies point to changes such as "the expansion of the number of 'flexible' conflict-of-law rules and the spread of autonomy of the will of the parties in the sphere of torts."

Currently, much attention in both doctrine and judicial practice is devoted not to the choice of applicable law, but to issues related to determining jurisdiction. Issues of subsequent enforcement of court decisions are also relevant.

New trends in the development of private international law, along with the ongoing reform of private international law in the Republic of Uzbekistan, highlight the need to select and develop clear perspectives and guidelines for national law enforcement practice. This is particularly important in the area of regulating obligations arising from harm (i.e., tortious obligations) complicated by a foreign element.

Currently, a certain phenomenon is being observed in this area: a certain "politicization" of rulemaking associated with the activities of certain international organizations, such as the Hague Conference, the Council of Europe, UNCITRAL, and UNIDROIT. There is also a trend toward increasing influence of international law on domestic legal institutions. At the same time, as some authors note [4], the pressure exerted during the discussion of those issues related to problems of international private law in pan-European structures is increasing, both from "pressure groups", such as consumer protection societies, insurance companies, and representatives of transnational corporations. The possibility of independent expression of the will of representatives of certain countries is also significantly reduced, and this is explained by the fact that many problems of international private law are not considered at the domestic level as vital. This leads to ignoring the possibility of the "right of veto" when it comes to the adoption of a particular document aimed at further unification and harmonization of international private law, including in and in the regulation of tortious obligations. The formation of a common market in the world has led to the creation of a system of uniform regulation of the choice of law in the area of contractual obligations. Extensive work is being carried out to harmonize conflict of laws regulation in the area of obligations arising from causing harm, that is, tortious obligations.

This is explained by the fact that the regulation of the terms that define contractual obligations is quite important for the development of economic relations, including the successful development of commercial turnover. This is explained by the fact that tortious legal relations, first and foremost, often affect the interests of the least economically protected legal entities—individuals. Therefore, the consideration of the problems of regulating tortious relations in a market economy is acquiring social significance. Secondly, in the modern period, the economic component of the problem of tortious relations, complicated by a foreign element, is rapidly increasing. Therefore, due to the development of international trade, as well as the cross-border provision of services, cases of cross-border harm arising from defects in goods, work, or services arise. Thirdly, in the modern period, the world is faced with man-made disasters of an unprecedented scale, the economic and social consequences of which on an international scale can be unprecedented. This circumstance also has a certain impact on the demand for research on issues related to the regulation of obligations arising from harm complicated by a foreign

element.

The similarity of conflict-of-laws regulation of obligations arising from causing harm in most countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States is explained by the fact that many of them have chosen to use Section VII "International Private Law" of the Model Civil Code for the CIS Member States as a recommendatory act for the CIS countries, adopted on February 17, 1996 by the Interparliamentary Assembly of Member Nations of the CIS [5]. Nevertheless, conflict-of-laws regulation of tortious obligations in some CIS countries has a number of peculiarities. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, general provisions on causing harm are regulated by the norms of Chapter 57 of the Civil Code, which contains the concepts of harm caused to the life and health of a citizen; due to defects in goods, works and services; as well as compensation for moral damage. Obligations resulting from causing harm with the participation of a foreign element are regulated by the norms of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan - Chapter 71 "Conflict of Laws" § 6 "Non-contractual obligations". However, the provisions directly related to the regulation of tort relations are defined in Article 1194 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Obligations resulting from harm", which stipulates that the rights and obligations under obligations arising from harm are determined by the law of the country where the action or other circumstance that served as the basis for the claim for compensation for harm took place [2]. These provisions of Article 1194 of the Civil Code, formulated as a general conflict of laws rule on the choice of law that is applicable to tort obligations complicated by a foreign element, and which corresponds to the well-known and widely used conflict of laws principle *lex loci delicti commissi* - a reference to the law of the place where the tort was committed. In accordance with the legislation, the place of the tort is considered to be the place where the harmful act was committed by the harm-doer. Depending on the specific circumstances of the case, the place of action or other circumstance that serves as the basis for a claim for compensation for damages is understood to mean the location of the injured party at the time the damage occurred, if the damage was caused to the person of the injured party, or the location of their property at the time the damage occurred, if the damage was caused to property.

The provisions of Article 1194 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan also extend to the definition of the law that governs compensation not only for property damage caused to an individual but also for moral damages. This article, by implication, covers cases of compensation for causal damages not only by the party causing the damage but also by certain other persons. This means that the emergence of an obligation as a result of damages does not always depend on the commission of an offense by the debtor. One possible exception is Article 988 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which allows the court to impose the obligation to compensate for damages caused in a state of extreme necessity on the person in whose interests the party causing the damages acted.

In accordance with the provisions of the civil legislation of the Republic of

Uzbekistan, tortious obligations are governed by the conflict of laws principle (*lege lex loci delicti commissi*), that is, by the law of the country where the action or other fact that served as the basis for the claim for compensation for damages occurred.

Rights and obligations under obligations arising from damage caused abroad, if the parties are citizens or legal entities of the same state, are determined by the law of that state. This provision is based on the principle of combining the interests of the tortfeasor and the injured party. This exception to the general rule of Part 1 of Article 1194 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan is established for cases where both the injured party and the tortfeasor are citizens of the same country or have their place of residence in the same country. In such a case, the tortious obligation is subject to the law of that country [2].

Foreign law does not apply if the action or other circumstance that served as the basis for the claim for compensation for damages is not illegal under the laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Issues arising from tortious obligations are reflected in international treaties to which the Republic of Uzbekistan has acceded. For example, Article 4 of the Agreement on the Procedure for Resolving Disputes Related to Economic Activities (Kyiv, March 20, 1992) stipulates that the competent court of a CIS member state has the right to consider the disputes referred to in Article 1 of this Agreement if the action or other circumstance that served as the basis for the claim for compensation for damages occurred in the territory of the CIS member state [6].

Similar provisions are also provided for in the Convention on Legal Assistance and Legal Relations in Civil, Family and Criminal Cases (Minsk, 20 January 1993) [7], Article 42 of which provides the following rules on compensation for damage:

1. Obligations to compensate for damage, except for those arising from contracts and other lawful acts, shall be determined by the legislation of the Contracting Party in whose territory the action or other circumstance that served as the basis for the claim for compensation for damage took place;

2. If the tortfeasor and the victim are citizens of the same Contracting State, the legislation of that Contracting State shall apply;

3. In the cases referred to in paragraphs 1 and 2 of this article, the court of the Contracting State in whose territory the action or other circumstance that served as the basis for the claim for compensation for damage took place shall have jurisdiction. The injured party may also file a claim in the court of the Contracting State where the defendant resides.

Having examined the legal regulation of obligations arising from harm caused abroad under the civil legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, it can be concluded that, at the legislative level, the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan takes into account the main international trends in the development and structure of modern conflict of laws, which regulates tortious obligations involving a foreign element. Legal regulation of obligations arising from harm caused by a foreign element in the legislation of CIS

countries is based on national legislation and the use of conflict of laws principles governing tortious relations.

Although non-contractual obligations related to harm caused abroad are regulated by national legislation, I would like to offer some suggestions for improving the legislation regulating obligations arising from harm caused by a foreign element.

Firstly, given that a significant portion of the issues arising in connection with determining the statute of a tortious obligation are subject to specific interpretation, as well as amendments to existing national legislation, the European Union Regulation on the law applicable to non-contractual obligations can provide significant assistance in this regard. In particular, it seems appropriate to adopt a primary link to the law of the place where the harmful result occurs; the use of party autonomy in choosing the statute of a tortious obligation is consistent with the modern development of private international law.

Secondly, it seems appropriate and timely to expand the parties' freedom of will in the area of tortious obligations by allowing them to choose not only the law of the forum but also other laws related to the legal relationship. In some cases, it is possible to grant the parties the freedom to choose the law before the actual harm has been caused. The conflict of laws rules in the area under study, as stipulated by current international treaties to which the Republic of Uzbekistan is a party, including the provisions of the 1992 Kyiv Agreement of the CIS Member States, do not correspond to the current stage of development of private international law. The national legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan and other CIS member states is more modern and more closely reflects progressive trends in the development of private international law. Therefore, amending the aforementioned treaties, taking into account the trends in reforming private international law in the Republic of Uzbekistan and other CIS countries, seems relevant.

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The Balance Between Civil Rights and Economic Freedom

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Abstract

This article examines the relationship between civil rights and economic freedom as key categories of the rule of law. It considers the need to establish a fair balance between freedom of economic activity and the protection of individual civil rights. It analyzes the legal positions of the Constitutional Court, international standards, and doctrinal approaches to the problem of restricting freedom of enterprise in the public interest and protecting private rights. It concludes that an optimal combination of civil and economic freedoms is a prerequisite for the sustainable development of the rule of law and a fair market.

A modern state governed by the rule of law rests on two interrelated pillars: individual civil rights and economic freedom. The former expresses human autonomy and dignity, while the latter emphasizes the ability to freely pursue economic initiative. However, these categories do not always align in their objectives: the exercise of one person's economic freedom may conflict with the rights of other participants in civil transactions or with public interests. Finding the optimal balance between civil rights and economic freedom is a complex task not only for law enforcement but also for legislators. The effectiveness of civil transactions, social justice, and trust in state institutions depend on how well this balance is maintained.

The balance between civil rights and economic freedom is not a static state, but a dynamic relationship that changes depending on the level of societal development, the economy, and legal awareness. An excess of freedom without legal restrictions leads to social inequality, while excessive state control stifles initiative and innovation. The optimal model is a legal order in which freedom is guaranteed by responsibility, and responsibility is based on freedom.

The balance between civil rights and economic freedom is a harmony between personal freedoms, such as the right to life and privacy, and the individual's ability to independently choose a career, own property, and engage in entrepreneurship. Achieving this balance is essential for building a just and prosperous society.

1. Civil Rights as the Foundation of Personal Autonomy. Civil rights are traditionally understood as a set of opportunities that ensure an individual's freedom of choice, inviolability of person, property, and privacy . According to Article 21 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, human

rights and freedoms are the highest value and may be limited only by law for the purpose of protecting other rights or public order. Of particular importance is the principle of equality of subjects of civil law and freedom of contract, enshrined in the Civil Code. It allows participants in economic activity to independently determine the terms of their interactions, but at the same time imposes responsibility for preventing abuse of rights.

Thus, civil rights form the normative framework within which economic freedom is realized. They serve not only as a guarantee of individual autonomy but also as a mechanism for limiting the excessive exercise of economic power.

2. Economic Freedom as an Element of the Rule of Law. Economic freedom is a legal category reflecting the right of citizens and legal entities to freely engage in entrepreneurial and other economic activities not prohibited by law. In accordance with Article 53 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the state guarantees freedom of economic activity, entrepreneurship, and labor. However, economic freedom is not absolute. Its implementation must take into account not only market mechanisms but also the principles of social justice, competition protection, and consumer rights. Economic activity that violates the rights of others contradicts the very essence of the rule of law. Consequently, economic freedom is inextricably linked with legal regulation, which sets the limits of acceptable behavior in the marketplace. Without such regulation, freedom can degenerate into arbitrariness, and the market can become a sphere of dominance for the strongest.

The category of "freedom of economic activity" possesses many facets, both in legislative and doctrinal terms. It represents a constitutional and legal principle; a constitutional, economic, and subjective human right; and, in a systemic sense, a legal category encompassing a diversity of types and forms of economic activity, serving as the basis for defining individual modes of implementation, establishing the limits and restrictions of the right to engage in economic activity.

3. The Problem of the Relationship between Civil Rights and Economic Freedom. The conflict between civil rights and economic freedom arises in situations where economic gain clashes with the need to respect personal and social rights. Examples include restrictions on monopolistic activity, regulation of adhesion contracts, consumer protection, and the protection of personal data for commercial purposes. Academic literature distinguishes two approaches: liberal economic and socio-legal. The former prioritizes freedom of contract and minimal government intervention, while the latter emphasizes the need to protect weak market participants. The experience of developed legal systems shows that sustainable development is only possible with a synthesis of both approaches. The state must ensure freedom of enterprise while actively protecting public interests and civil rights.

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ПРАВОВЫЕ ОСНОВЫ ЛЕГИТИМАЦИИ СУБЪЕКТОВ ПРЕДПРИНИМАТЕЛЬСТВА

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Аннотация

Статья посвящена исследованию правовых основ легитимации субъектов предпринимательства, их роли в обеспечении законности и устойчивости деловой активности. Рассматриваются правовые механизмы регистрации и государственной регистрации предпринимателей, корпоративной идентификации и правового признания индивидуальных и юридических лиц, осуществляющих предпринимательскую деятельность. Анализируются нормативно-правовые акты, регулирующие создание, функционирование и контроль за деятельностью предпринимателей, включая Гражданский кодекс, законы о предпринимательстве и налоговом регулировании. Особое внимание уделено вопросам защиты прав субъектов предпринимательства, обеспечения прозрачности их деятельности и соблюдения требований по финансовой и юридической отчетности. На основе сравнительно-правового подхода выявляются тенденции гармонизации национальных правовых режимов и рекомендации по совершенствованию законодательства с целью повышения инвестиционной привлекательности и снижения административных барьеров.

Ключевые слова: легитимация предпринимателей, правовой статус, государственная регистрация, корпоративная идентификация, предпринимательская деятельность, правовое регулирование, защита прав субъектов, инвестиционная привлекательность, административные барьеры, законность.

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LEGAL FOUNDATIONS FOR THE LEGITIMATION OF ENTREPRENEURIAL ENTITIES

Abstract

The article is devoted to the study of the legal foundations for the legitimation of entrepreneurial entities and their role in ensuring the legality and stability of business activities. It examines the legal mechanisms for registration and state registration of entrepreneurs, corporate identification, and the legal recognition of individuals and legal entities engaged in entrepreneurial activities. The analysis covers regulatory acts governing the creation, functioning, and oversight of entrepreneurs, including the Civil Code, laws on entrepreneurship, and tax regulations. Particular attention is given to issues of protecting the rights of entrepreneurial entities, ensuring transparency in their operations, and complying with financial and legal reporting requirements. Using a comparative-legal approach, the article identifies trends in the harmonization of national legal frameworks and provides recommendations for improving legislation to enhance investment attractiveness and reduce administrative barriers.

Keywords: legitimation of entrepreneurs, legal status, state registration, corporate identification, entrepreneurial activity, legal regulation, protection of rights of entities, investment attractiveness, administrative barriers, legality.

Introduction

In the modern global economy, the legitimation of entrepreneurial entities represents a key determinant of their sustainability, competitiveness, and legal security. The process of legitimation extends beyond the formal acquisition of legal status; it reflects the interaction between legal regulation, social recognition, and institutional trust. In the context of rapid globalization and digitalization, legitimacy has become a crucial element of corporate reputation, market credibility, and business adaptability to regulatory and societal change [1].

For the Republic of Uzbekistan, the issue of entrepreneurial legitimation is particularly relevant due to the ongoing transformation of its economic and legal systems. Over the years of independence, the country has implemented consistent reforms aimed at liberalizing the business environment and ensuring its transparency. Key legislative acts — including the Law “On Licensing, Permitting and Notification Procedures” (2021, No. 701), the Law “On Competition” (2012, No. ZRU-319), and the Law “On Guarantees of Freedom of Entrepreneurial Activity” (2012, No. ZRU-328) — have created the fundamental legal basis for free and fair entrepreneurship [2]. These

reforms seek to balance economic liberalism and state oversight, ensuring the protection of both market participants and public interests.

At the same time, the process of legitimation cannot be reduced merely to registration or licensing procedures. It must encompass broader aspects — including social legitimacy, ethical business conduct, and public trust. In this regard, it is necessary to distinguish between formal-legal legitimacy, which is achieved through compliance with the law, and social-value legitimacy, which depends on the public perception of the entrepreneur's contribution to economic and social welfare [3]. Such an approach corresponds to Max Weber's theory of legitimate authority, according to which legitimacy arises not only from legal conformity but also from the recognition and acceptance of authority or norms by society [4].

In the Uzbek context, this dual nature of legitimacy manifests itself through the simultaneous pursuit of administrative simplification and enhanced accountability. For example, reforms in the field of licensing and notification procedures have been directed toward minimizing entry barriers for new businesses, while maintaining rigorous monitoring of compliance during ongoing operations [5]. This shift from preemptive control to performance-based oversight reflects the broader goal of improving the quality of governance and strengthening the legal environment for entrepreneurship.

Accordingly, the purpose of this article is to explore the legal foundations of the legitimation of entrepreneurial entities in Uzbekistan through the lens of both legal doctrine and social recognition theory. The study analyzes national legislation, theoretical approaches of domestic and foreign scholars (including D.A. Akbarov, H.P. Abulqosimov, R.T. Nuraliev, I.V. Ershova, E.V. Trofimova), and comparative experience in developing legal systems. The research aims to identify how Uzbekistan's legal framework for entrepreneurship can ensure a balance between freedom of enterprise, legal responsibility, and public legitimacy — creating a transparent and trusted environment for sustainable business development.

Methodology

The methodological basis of this research is grounded in a doctrinal legal analysis combined with systemic, comparative, and sociological approaches, allowing for a comprehensive understanding of the legal and social dimensions of entrepreneurial legitimation in Uzbekistan. The study relies primarily on official legal sources, ensuring the reliability and verifiability of its findings.

First, the formal-legal (doctrinal) method is employed to interpret and analyze the

hierarchy and interaction of legal norms that regulate entrepreneurship, licensing, and state supervision in the Republic of Uzbekistan. This method enables the differentiation between *lex generalis* norms—such as the Law “On Guarantees of Freedom of Entrepreneurial Activity” (No. ZRU-328, 2012)—and *lex specialis* norms, including the Law “On Licensing, Permitting and Notification Procedures” (No. ZRU-701, 2021) [6]. It also allows the identification of how subsidiary acts—such as decrees of the President and resolutions of the Cabinet of Ministers—integrate within the legal hierarchy, ensuring compliance with constitutional principles and the rule of law.

Second, the systemic approach is applied to examine the interconnection between legal legitimation and social legitimacy of entrepreneurship. This approach facilitates the understanding of how legal recognition (registration, licensing, certification) interacts with societal factors—such as trust, transparency, and public accountability—that determine the social acceptance of business entities [7]. In this context, the research refers to Weber’s theory of legitimate authority and its application to modern governance, emphasizing that legitimacy arises not solely from formal legal compliance but also from the societal recognition of entrepreneurial activity as fair and beneficial [8].

Third, the study incorporates a comparative-legal method, which allows for an analytical juxtaposition of Uzbekistan’s legal mechanisms of business legitimation with selected foreign jurisdictions, particularly those of the European Union, OECD countries, and post-Soviet legal systems. This comparison does not imply normative transplantation but rather serves to contextualize the evolution of Uzbekistan’s legal reforms within the global discourse on business freedom, regulatory simplification, and legal certainty [9].

In addition, a teleological (purposive) interpretation is used to evaluate the alignment between Uzbekistan’s legal policies on entrepreneurship and its constitutional objectives of economic liberalization and sustainable development. This interpretive approach makes it possible to assess how the national framework of entrepreneurial legitimation contributes to the fulfillment of strategic goals defined in the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan (2022–2026) and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG 8 and SDG 16), focusing on inclusive economic growth and the strengthening of legal institutions [10].

Finally, the research adopts elements of the sociological method by integrating theoretical insights from both domestic and foreign scholars—such as D.A. Akbarov, H.P. Abulqosimov, R.T. Nuraliev, I.V. Ershova, and E.V. Trofimova—who have

explored the intersection between legal regulation, social trust, and market behavior [11]. This ensures a multidimensional perspective on the legitimation process, recognizing that legal norms function effectively only when supported by social consent and institutional credibility.

Thus, by combining doctrinal precision, systemic reasoning, and teleological interpretation, the methodology ensures both legal depth and practical relevance, allowing for a nuanced assessment of how the legal framework of Uzbekistan can reinforce the legitimacy—both formal and social—of entrepreneurial entities.

Research

The research explores the legal, institutional, and social foundations of the legitimation of entrepreneurial entities in the Republic of Uzbekistan, identifying the mechanisms through which legality and social recognition of business activities are established and maintained. It focuses on the relationship between formal legal legitimation—achieved through compliance with the system of registration, licensing, and permitting procedures—and social legitimacy, which is grounded in public trust, ethical conduct, and corporate responsibility.

From a legal standpoint, the legitimation of business entities in Uzbekistan is primarily governed by the Law “On Licensing, Permitting and Notification Procedures” (No. ZRU-701, 2021), the Law “On Guarantees of Freedom of Entrepreneurial Activity” (No. ZRU-328, 2012), and the Law “On Competition” (No. ZRU-319, 2012) [12]. These acts collectively form the legislative basis for the recognition of entrepreneurs as lawful and socially responsible participants in the market. The adoption of these laws marked a significant transition from a command-administrative model to a market-oriented regulatory framework, aimed at reducing bureaucratic barriers and strengthening the rule of law in economic relations [13].

Recent reforms have been directed toward simplifying administrative procedures and enhancing transparency in the licensing process. In particular, the Presidential Decree No. PF-5690 (May 11, 2019) “On Measures to Radically Improve the System of Licensing and Permitting Procedures” introduced a digital licensing platform and replaced many prior approval requirements with notification-based mechanisms [14]. This reform reflects a broader shift toward the post-control model, where government oversight focuses on monitoring compliance during business operation rather than on pre-entry barriers. Such an approach corresponds to international best practices recommended by the OECD and World Bank Doing Business reports, which emphasize that simplified and transparent licensing enhances both legal predictability and

entrepreneurial legitimacy [15].

At the same time, the formal-legal dimension of legitimacy must be reinforced by societal acceptance and trust. As Max Weber's theory of legitimate authority suggests, legitimacy arises not only from legal conformity but also from the recognition of authority by those subject to it [16]. Transposing this concept to entrepreneurship, one can distinguish between formal legal legitimacy, based on adherence to laws and regulations, and social legitimacy, which depends on public perception of entrepreneurship as ethical, transparent, and beneficial to the community [17]. This dual nature of legitimacy is particularly relevant for transition economies, where public attitudes toward business are often shaped by historical distrust of private ownership and market institutions.

In Uzbekistan, this challenge is addressed through policies promoting corporate social responsibility (CSR), business ethics, and public accountability. The Law "On Social Partnership" and the National Anti-Corruption Strategy 2021–2025 underline the importance of collaboration between government, civil society, and business associations in ensuring lawful and transparent entrepreneurship [18]. In this sense, legitimation operates as a two-way process: the state provides legal guarantees and institutional recognition, while businesses, in turn, demonstrate responsible conduct and compliance with social and ethical standards.

Furthermore, the study draws upon the works of leading Uzbek scholars—such as D.A. Akbarov, H.P. Abulqosimov, and R.T. Nuraliev—who emphasize that legal legitimation of entrepreneurship is a fundamental precondition for economic modernization and sustainable development [19]. Comparative insights from Russian and European legal doctrine (e.g., I.V. Ershova, E.V. Trofimova) reinforce the argument that legitimacy is both a legal status and a social process of continuous validation by the state and society [20].

Thus, the research identifies three essential pillars of entrepreneurial legitimation in Uzbekistan:

1. Legal recognition — the establishment of lawful status through registration, licensing, and state supervision;
2. Institutional trust — the consistency and transparency of administrative procedures;
3. Social acceptance — the development of ethical and responsible business behavior recognized by society.

These dimensions collectively form the integrated model of legitimation, which

can strengthen the credibility of entrepreneurship, improve investor confidence, and contribute to the formation of a transparent and competitive market economy.

Discussion

The findings of the research reveal that the legitimation of entrepreneurial entities in Uzbekistan is not a static legal status but a dynamic process that integrates legal, institutional, and social dimensions. This process reflects the interaction between state authority, market institutions, and public perception, each contributing to the formation of a legitimate and trustworthy business environment.

From a legal-institutional perspective, Uzbekistan has made substantial progress in establishing a coherent framework for entrepreneurial legitimation. The implementation of the Law “On Licensing, Permitting and Notification Procedures” (2021) and the Presidential Decree (2019) represents a critical step toward improving administrative transparency, minimizing corruption risks, and facilitating market entry for new businesses [21][22]. By introducing a digital platform for licensing and notifications, the state has institutionalized a “one-stop-shop” principle, aligning national procedures with OECD and World Bank recommendations for reducing bureaucratic burdens [23].

Nevertheless, despite these reforms, the formal recognition of entrepreneurs remains insufficient without accompanying measures that foster social legitimacy. Empirical studies and reports by the Center for Economic Research and Reforms (CERR) show that many small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in Uzbekistan face challenges related to public trust, administrative pressure, and inconsistent enforcement of regulations [24]. In such circumstances, legitimation must evolve beyond the legalistic notion of compliance toward a holistic concept encompassing ethical behavior, corporate transparency, and accountability to society.

The theoretical framework of Max Weber’s concept of legitimacy provides valuable insight into this process. Weber distinguished between legitimacy based on legal-rational authority—rooted in formal rules—and legitimacy derived from social acceptance of those rules [25]. Applying this distinction to entrepreneurship implies that a business can be lawful but still lack legitimacy if it fails to meet societal expectations or ethical norms. Therefore, the effectiveness of legal reforms in Uzbekistan must be evaluated not only by the number of registered enterprises or simplified procedures but also by the level of public confidence in these businesses and in the institutions that regulate them [26].

In this context, corporate social responsibility (CSR) plays an increasingly significant role as a mechanism of voluntary legitimation. According to the UNDP

Uzbekistan Report (2022), enterprises that integrate social and environmental considerations into their strategies enjoy greater institutional support and reputational stability [27]. CSR initiatives—such as ethical labor practices, community investment, and transparent reporting—serve as instruments of “social licensing”, which complement the state’s formal licensing framework. This dual approach—combining legal authorization with social validation—ensures that entrepreneurship operates as a socially integrated institution rather than merely an economic function.

However, challenges persist. The enforcement of anti-corruption measures and the implementation of ethical business standards often depend on the quality of governance and the level of judicial independence. Despite the National Anti-Corruption Strategy 2021–2025, cases of selective enforcement and regulatory discretion undermine the perception of fairness in the business environment [28]. Strengthening judicial guarantees for entrepreneurs and expanding the role of business ombudsman institutions are essential steps toward improving legitimacy in both legal and social senses.

Comparative analysis with European Union (EU) and OECD member states further demonstrates that legitimacy in entrepreneurship correlates strongly with regulatory predictability, public access to information, and stakeholder participation in decision-making processes [29]. For example, the EU Small Business Act (SBA) emphasizes the principle of “Think Small First,” which ensures that legislative and regulatory processes consider the impact on SMEs before adoption [30]. Implementing similar participatory mechanisms in Uzbekistan would enhance the perception of entrepreneurship as a socially beneficial and legally secure activity.

Therefore, the discussion underscores that legitimation should be viewed as a multilevel construct encompassing:

1. Legal legitimation – ensured by compliance with the regulatory framework and recognition by state authorities;
2. Institutional legitimation – achieved through transparent, consistent, and predictable administrative practices;
3. Social legitimation – derived from ethical standards, CSR engagement, and public trust.

The interaction among these three dimensions forms the foundation of sustainable entrepreneurship, where legal compliance is harmonized with societal values and institutional integrity. In Uzbekistan, the evolution of such a model requires continued alignment of national legislation with international norms, capacity-building within regulatory institutions, and the promotion of an ethical business culture supported by

civil society.

Conclusion

The analysis of the legal foundations for the legitimation of entrepreneurial entities in Uzbekistan demonstrates that the process of legitimization extends beyond the sphere of formal legal recognition to encompass deeper institutional and social dimensions. Legitimacy in entrepreneurship is achieved not only through compliance with statutory norms but also through the establishment of trust between the state, the business community, and society. This multidimensional approach is essential for the formation of a sustainable and transparent business environment capable of supporting the country's long-term development strategy.

The research confirms that Uzbekistan has made significant progress in developing a comprehensive regulatory framework for entrepreneurship. Key reforms—such as the Law “On Licensing, Permitting and Notification Procedures” (2021), the Law “On Guarantees of Freedom of Entrepreneurial Activity” (2000, as amended 2022), and the Presidential Decree (2019)—have established the legal basis for the recognition, protection, and equal treatment of business entities [31][32][33]. These instruments reflect the government's intention to align national regulation with international standards of economic governance, including the OECD's recommendations on regulatory simplification and the World Bank's principles of ease of doing business [34][35].

At the same time, the study highlights that formal legal compliance does not automatically produce social legitimacy. Many enterprises still encounter institutional obstacles, administrative opacity, and insufficient legal protection, which weakens public confidence in both the entrepreneurial sector and the institutions supervising it. This finding is consistent with sociological theories of legitimacy, such as Weber's concept of legal-rational authority and Habermas's theory of communicative action, which emphasize that the legitimacy of institutions depends not only on legality but also on social acceptance and transparency in decision-making [36][37].

To consolidate both legal and social legitimacy, Uzbekistan's policy framework must focus on several key priorities:

1. Enhancing rule of law and judicial protection for entrepreneurs. Effective legitimation requires not only regulatory clarity but also credible enforcement. Strengthening the independence of economic courts and ensuring the impartiality of dispute resolution mechanisms would increase investor confidence and protect property rights [38].

2. Institutionalizing transparency and accountability. Introducing mandatory public reporting by state agencies on licensing and oversight activities, as recommended by the OECD (2021), would minimize discretionary decisions and corruption risks [39].

3. Promoting social legitimacy through corporate responsibility. Encouraging businesses to adopt corporate social responsibility (CSR) and sustainability practices—aligned with the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly SDG 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth) and SDG 16 (Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions)—would strengthen public trust and integrate entrepreneurship into the social fabric [40].

4. Developing participatory regulatory mechanisms. Following the example of the EU Small Business Act (SBA), Uzbekistan could introduce public consultations with SME associations before adopting new economic regulations, ensuring that policymaking is responsive and inclusive [10].

Ultimately, the legitimation of entrepreneurial entities in Uzbekistan represents a two-dimensional transformation: (a) from formal legality toward institutional credibility, and (b) from state-centered control toward participatory governance and social responsibility. This transformation is crucial for building a resilient, innovation-driven economy capable of competing globally while preserving national values of fairness, justice, and equality before the law.

The study concludes that the sustainability of entrepreneurship depends on the coherence between legal regulation, institutional practice, and societal values. Strengthening this coherence through ongoing legal reform, transparent administration, and ethical corporate conduct will ensure that entrepreneurial entities in Uzbekistan are not only legally recognized but also socially legitimate and publicly trusted.

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LEGAL REGULATION OF VENTURE FUNDS IN UZBEKISTAN: TOWARD A GENDER-SENSITIVE INVESTMENT POLICY

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Annotation

The article examines the legal regulation of venture funds in Uzbekistan in the context of developing a gender-sensitive investment policy. Against the backdrop of rapid institutional reforms in the financial sector and the state's declared commitment to innovation-driven economic growth, the study investigates how far the national legal framework for venture financing incorporates gender equality objectives. Drawing on a formal, systemic, and teleological legal analysis, the research explores the interplay between investment legislation — notably the Laws “On Investments and Investment Activity” (2019) and “On Investment and Mutual Funds” (2015, as amended 2024) — and gender-equality legislation, including the Law “On Guarantees of Equal Rights and Opportunities for Women and Men” (2019) and related government resolutions. The study identifies structural gaps between economic liberalization and social policy, highlighting the need to integrate gender-lens investing within the emerging venture-capital ecosystem. By aligning venture-finance regulation with national and international commitments to gender equality and sustainable development, the paper offers recommendations for the inclusive evolution of Uzbekistan's investment framework.

Keywords:

venture funds, Uzbekistan, investment law, gender equality, gender-lens investing, financial regulation, sustainable development, inclusive growth, innovation policy, legal framework.

I. Introduction

In view of the swift institutional transformation of the financial market in Uzbekistan and the declared national course for innovative economic development, the question of how far the current legal framework of venture financing integrates objectives related to gender equality becomes especially relevant for both practitioners of law and makers of policy. Within the period from 2020 to 2025, the government adopted a series of acts that shaped the basics of the venture-capital ecosystem, including establishing and further reorganizing the national venture fund UzVC, allowing commercial banks and enterprises with state participation to create venture

funds, and creating the National Investment Fund. Alongside this process, a sound gender-equality framework has been set up, including the Law on Guarantees of Equal Rights and Opportunities for Women and Men, the obligation for gender-legal expertise of draft legislation, and the National Strategy for Gender Equality until 2030. This is the juncture where investment reform and social policy create a chance for legal analysis of the regulatory interface between venture-capital law and gender equality, aiming at the elaboration of mechanisms to include gender-lens investing into the emerging venture ecosystem of Uzbekistan.

II. Methodology

The given research relies exclusively on official and primary legal sources, ensuring the reliability and verifiability of its findings. The analysis is based on the Law “On Investments and Investment Activity” (adopted 14 December 2019, No. 598) [1], the Law “On Investment and Mutual Funds” No. 392 (25 August 2015, as amended 16 January 2024) [2], as well as Presidential Decrees and Cabinet resolutions establishing the National Venture Fund UzVC and the National Investment Fund (NIF). Further support for the research was found in the Law “On Guarantees of Equal Rights and Opportunities for Women and Men” (No.562, 2019) and the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 192 (2020) on obligatory gender-legal expertise. All statistical and factual data are taken from official publications of the Ministry of Economy and Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan (July 2025) [3] and serve as an authoritative empirical basis in providing the legal assessment. Methodologically, the article applies a tri-level doctrinal and interpretive framework.

Formal-legal approach: This approach is used to interpret the hierarchical interaction of legal norms regulating investment and gender policy. It makes possible the precise differentiation between *lex generalis*-the Law on Investments-and *lex specialis*-the Law on Investment and Mutual Funds-and at what point subsidiary regulations, presidential decrees, and ministerial acts may or may not be accommodated within the legal hierarchy of Uzbekistan.

Systemic approach: The study applies systemic reasoning to connect investment regulation with equality legislation, placing venture-fund governance within the greater normative framework of social policy. This approach identifies, through the analysis of horizontal coherence between investment, financial, and gender norms, the structural disjunction between Uzbekistan's economic-liberal model and its gender-equality commitments.

Teleological interpretation: A purposive or goal-oriented interpretation is one that aligns the intent of the legislature to constitutional objectives relating to sustainable and inclusive development, largely as expressed in Sustainable Development s 5 (Gender Equality) and 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth)[4]. This interpretive prism emphasizes how statutory neutrality towards gender concerns is at odds with national-development strategies and international obligations of Uzbekistan.

Complementarily, the research design will be of an analytical-descriptive type, where the evolving venture-capital regulation of Uzbekistan will be put in a comparative perspective with selected international models-only for the purpose of explanatory context and without importing any normative standards from abroad (EU, OECD, and regional post-transition jurisdictions).

By integrating these three methods-formal, systemic, and teleological-the paper ensures doctrinal precision as well as policy relevance for a nuanced assessment of how the country's legal framework for venture funds can be reconciled with its international commitments to gender equality.

III. Results

1. Core Investment Regulation

The Law “On Investments and Investment Activity” (adopted on 14 December 2019) provides the general guarantees of investors and regulates the general regime of investment activity for both domestic and foreign participants. It establishes the basic guarantees of investors, such as protection against illegal expropriation, assurance of nondiscrimination, and the right to free repatriation of profits. It enshrines the principles of investment freedom and equality of investors regardless of the ownership form or nationality, thereby approximating Uzbekistan's regulatory approach to international standards of investment protection. Importantly, it also consolidates previously fragmented norms into a single, coherent framework consistent with the strategic course taken by the government toward liberalization and attraction of private capital. While the Law “On Investment and Mutual Funds” No.392 (August 25, 2015, last amended January 16, 2024) sets forth the legal status, organizational structure, and operational principles of investment and mutual funds. It represents the *lex specialis* for collective investment mechanisms, providing a legal basis for establishing venture funds as a particular category of investment vehicles. The changes introduced in 2024 concerned new provisions on fund management, transparency, and risk diversification; these allowed the institutionalization of venture financing as an alternative form of investment within the capital market of Uzbekistan.

2. Establishment of Venture Infrastructure

The Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 684 (3 November 2020) [5] systematized the activities of the national venture fund UzVC and provided for its charter capital of 15 billion UZS from the state budget through the Ministry of Innovative Development. Management was entrusted via competitive trust management. Presidential Decree No. 303 [6] of 27 August 2024 issued instructions on the creation of the National Investment Fund as a systemic investor in support of privatization and market reforms. On 14 October 2024, UzVC was transformed into a “fund of funds” under the Ministry of Economy and Finance. Commercial banks and enterprises with more than 50 % state participation were endowed with the right to create venture funds, carry out venture investments, and to place resources under trust-management

agreements. In addition, a separate venture fund was created within IT Park with a budget of USD 10 million, while financing mechanisms were established through the Reconstruction and Development Fund.

3. Official Market Data (First Half of 2025)

According to the official press release of the Ministry of Economy and Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan (18 July 2025)[7], the national venture-capital ecosystem demonstrates a steady process of institutional consolidation. By mid-2025, Uzbekistan had established 11 active participants in the venture-investment market: one fund-of-funds (the National Venture Fund UzVC), and ten venture funds, namely Aloqa Ventures, IT Park Ventures, United Ventures, SQB Ventures, Asaka Ventures, Yoshlar Ventures, UC Ventures, Semurg[‘] Ventures, Sarmo Ventures, and Imkon Ventures. The aggregate volume of venture investments reached approximately USD 145 million, reflecting both the government’s financial commitment and an emerging diversification of private-sector participation. Of these organizations, four funds (UC Ventures, Semurg[‘], Sarmo, and Imkon) operate exclusively with private capital, while the others receive full or partial public co-financing through UzVC or affiliated state mechanisms. This institutional balance between public and private capital presupposes a transitional phase, in which state participation continues to support market development, providing liquidity and risk absorption until the private ecosystem reaches full maturity. From a regulatory perspective, this hybrid structure is both beneficial and limiting. On the one hand, state support guarantees market stability and reduces systemic risk for early-stage investors; on the other hand, excessive state intervention may inadvertently delay the emergence of competitive private capital flows. Moreover, the prevalence of state-backed structures raises the regulatory question of whether such funds, financed by public resources, should be subject to enhanced transparency and social accountability requirements, including gender-sensitive reporting.

4. Legal Obligations for Gender Equality

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 562, dated 2 September 2019, “On Guarantees of Equal Rights and Opportunities for Women and Men,” codifies equal rights and obliges state institutions to actively promote gender equality. Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 192 [8], dated 30 March 2020, introduces the requirement of compulsory gender-legal expertise for all draft normative acts, irrespective of sectoral affiliation. Finally, the National Strategy for Achieving Gender Equality until 2030 consolidates the state's long-term commitment to inclusivity and institutional gender mainstreaming.

IV. Legal Analysis: Gaps and Directions for Harmonization

A. Venture-Fund Structure vs. Gender Objectives

Although the Law on Investment and Mutual Funds (No. 392, 2015, amended 2024) and the Law on Investments and Investment Activity (No.598, 2019) together define a liberal and investor-friendly regime, none of these acts contain explicit

provisions addressing gender equality, diversity of management, or the inclusion of women entrepreneurs in venture-financing processes. Likewise, neither Resolution No. 684 (2020) establishing the UzVC nor Presidential Decree No. 303 (2024) creating the National Investment Fund (NIF) incorporates gender-specific mandates. The legal architecture of venture-capital regulation in Uzbekistan is, therefore, economically progressive but socially neutral. It aims to stimulate innovation and attract private capital through financial mechanisms, yet it omits the normative elements that would ensure equality of opportunity and diversity in participation. Unlike certain EU jurisdictions or the OECD framework on gender-responsive investment[10], Uzbekistan's system treats investment as an ideologically neutral market tool, rather than a vector for inclusive growth. This design produces what can be termed a "vertical disjunction" between the upper layer of policy (gender equality as a national and constitutional commitment under the Law No. 562 and the Strategy 2030) [9] and the operational layer of investment law (venture governance). Gender equality thus functions "above" the investment system through overarching legal norms and expert review but not "within" it as a built-in regulatory parameter. The absence of integration reduces the internal coherence of Uzbekistan's sustainable-development policy and may inadvertently reinforce structural barriers for women-led enterprises [10]. A critical interpretation suggests that this omission is not a legislative gap in the technical sense, but a normative silence reflecting the early stage of venture-market development. However, as the ecosystem matures, this silence becomes legally consequential: without gender-sensitive clauses in fund-governance rules, there is no statutory basis for monitoring or enforcing equitable access. The evolution toward a more inclusive model thus requires not the replacement of existing laws but their interpretive expansion and supplementation through subordinate regulations.

B. Mandatory Gender Expertise as Procedural Bridge

Whereas the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 192 (30 March 2020) provided for the introduction of a system of compulsory gender-legal expertise, assuming that every draft normative legal act shall be analyzed for its compliance with the principles of equality. Within the context of venture financing, this system is an institutional bridge capable of converting gender policy into regulation with sectoral coverage. In other words, in the case of adopting new internal statutes of UzVC or NIF relating, for example, to the selection of managing companies, co-investment procedure, or to the form and content of a trust-management agreement, this form of legal review will be required. If applied substantively and not just formally, gender expertise might ensure that selection criteria for fund managers and portfolio investments lack indirect discrimination and guarantee equal access of male and female entrepreneurs to financial resources. At the same time, in practice, such expertise often has a merely procedural and declaratory character: compliance reports are issued without quantifiable metrics and follow-up commitments. Meanwhile, a comparative administrative law analysis sets

the following three stages as effectively required for gender-mainstreaming: (1) ex-ante assessment; (2) monitoring of implementation; and (3) ex-post evaluation. Currently, Uzbekistan's regulatory framework reaches only the first stage, leaving the latter two unregulated. The enhancement of this continuum would transform gender expertise from formal review into a substantive governance tool [12].

C. Public Funds and Transparency Obligations

Despite elaborate provisions on governance and investment procedures, the present acts contain no uniform disclosure requirements pertaining to access from a gender perspective: there are no indications on what share of women-led start-ups are funded, the gender composition of investment committees, or diversity in fund governance. Gender accountability, therefore, remains a question of soft law, dependent on voluntary disclosure rather than regulatory compulsion.

D. The Role of the National Investment Fund

Although the National Investment Fund was established with an explicit mandate to channel capital in ways that could support privatization and institutional projects, its competence regarding the regulation of mechanisms for co-investment means that it bears a unique potential to function as a champion of gender-sensitive standards. As a leading state investor, the NIF is in a position to include ESG criteria and gender aspects in partnership and co-financing agreements [11]. The introduction of such provisions will not need legislation but rather be done through ministerial orders or model agreements elaborated under Presidential Decree No. 303; thus, aligning NIF activities with Uzbekistan's obligations under Law No. 562 and the Gender Equality Strategy until 2030 with economic goals, on the one hand, and with social aims, on the other. Furthermore, by granting access to state co-investments based on complying with gender standards, the NIF could indirectly incentivize private venture funds to take parallel internal policies, thereby pushing down gender mainstreaming in the capital market. Such an approach in itself is in line with the emerging international principle of "conditional public funding," with a broader dimension of linking the availability of state or quasi-state financial support with social impact. Inclusion of such conditionality within the framework of the National Investment Fund (NIF) would place Uzbekistan among progressive jurisdictions which see equality not as a mere political slogan but also as a criterion of action.

E. Risks and Implementation Challenges

A critical analysis of the current system exposes the following systemic vulnerabilities:

a) Fragmented regulations: investment funds, co-investment agreements, and innovation support are governed by multiple regulations, but none of them outline one consolidated set of gender or ESG indicators. Such a nature of regulation inherently possesses the risk of inconsistency and less effectiveness in monitoring.

b) Formalism in gender assessment: at present, Resolution No. 192 seems to show a preference to procedural compliance rather than substantive assessment, with nominal rather than a transformative effect.

c) Regulatory asymmetry: publicly funded funds may face stricter reporting requirements compared to purely private ones, leading to unequal enforcement and possible market distortion.

d) Data deficit: Lack of collection of systematic gender-disaggregated data regarding venture capital projects remains a major obstacle to evidence-informed policymaking and the measurement of equality outcomes.

e) Institutional inertia: Implementation remains fragmented and slow without interagency coordination between the Ministry of Economy and Finance, the Agency for Gender Equality, and the Central Bank;

In other words, even though the legislative framework of venture capital investment is financially strong in Uzbekistan, it is not developed socially. The way forward rests on changing procedural mechanisms such as gender impact assessments and disclosure requirements into key regulatory instruments that make innovation policy consistent with the constitutional and strategic imperative of gender equality.

V. Argument and Proposals

Promoting gender-sensitive investment policy in the venture-fund framework of Uzbekistan is possible without significant legislative reform, through strategic use of subordinate regulation in conjunction with conditions on recipients of public funding.

The following measures are proposed:

1. Introduce gender performance KPIs in UzVC and other publicly supported venture funds, with minimum disclosure requirements on the share of women-led applications, approved deals, and gender composition of investment committees. Such requirements can be based on No. 562, related to equal opportunities, and Resolution 192, regarding obligatory expertise.

2. Include gender-lens investing criteria in co-financing and trust-management agreements. Public funds must allocate resources preferentially to venture funds that maintain measurable gender-impact performance and publish annual inclusion reports.

3. Adopt a standard reporting template through a joint order of the Ministry of Economy and Finance and the Central Bank, which would oblige venture funds that receive public support to annually disclose their investment data by gender.

4. Align venture-fund regulations with the Gender Equality Strategy 2030 by inserting express mentions of the objectives in preambles and explanatory notes of normative acts, therefore, strengthening coherence between investment regulation and social-policy objectives.

5. This means providing substantive gender-legal expertise on new and changed

venture-investment rules, and making findings and corrective measures public (“duty to explain”).

VI. Conclusion

The reforms of 2020-2025 have set up Uzbekistan's basic framework for venture capital: comprehensive investment legislation, institutionalization of UzVC as a fund of funds, creation of the National Investment Fund, and emergence of a diversified market comprising 11 funds with total venture investments of approximately USD 145 million. Despite these developments, however, the sector-specific investment regulations are still devoid of gender-sensitive mechanisms. Currently, the gender-equality mandate can be considered to work only through the general course of law, specifically No.562, supplemented by the mandatory expertise system, Resolution 192. Therefore, it is both legal and workable to incorporate gender-lens investing principles through subordinate legislation, like regulations, contractual requirements, and transparency standards, without extensive statutory changes. This will allow Uzbekistan to align its fast-growing venture-capital market with its constitutional and strategic commitments toward gender equality and further the twin objectives of economic innovation and social justice.

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FEATURES OF LEGAL PROTECTION OF INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY IN BUSINESS

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Abstract. This article discusses ways to protect the rights of intellectual property rights holders in business activities. The ways and methods of protecting trademarks and brand names are revealed. International practice in the field of protection of intellectual property rights is also analyzed.

Keywords: intellectual property; entrepreneurial activity; trademark; brand names; protection; methods of protection.

Modern law fundamentally refrains from interfering in the “inner life” of an individual — just as it avoids intruding into the sphere of intimate relations between people. As long as a thought is not expressed, it simply does not exist for the law. A person cannot be forced to think or to create. One can only establish conditions that make thinking and creativity possible. Without certain conditions, such a possibility cannot arise. Yet the creative process itself always remains beyond the scope of legal regulation. “Law is powerless to set boundaries in spiritual production,” wrote Hegel [1, p. 2].

However, once the result of creativity acquires an objective form, legal norms come into effect which ensure public recognition of this result, establish the legal regime of the corresponding object, and protect the rights and lawful interests of its creator. The results of intellectual activity can become objects of legal relations only when they take an objective form that enables their perception by other people. Thus, an indispensable requirement for granting copyright protection is the external expression of an author’s idea in some objective form.

At the same time, it does not matter whether an idea, image, or thought is fixed on a material medium or merely announced in a place where a significant number of persons outside the usual family circle are present. Until an author’s idea becomes accessible for perception by others, the object of protection simply does not exist.

Only an objectively expressed result of intellectual activity can participate in

economic circulation, become a commodity, and function in the market. Such an object must and can be protected by the state, by society, and by the law.

In recent times, Uzbekistan's legislation governing relations in the field of intellectual property has undergone significant changes. The foundation of this legislation consists of international legal agreements to which Uzbekistan is a party.

In this connection, it is essential to implement effective international legislation into the domestic legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan that regulates relations concerning the creation and use of copyright objects, patent matters, and relations associated with the use of means of individualization of legal entities, know how, and other related issues.

By the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 7 February 2017 No. UP-4947 "On the Strategy of Actions for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan," the State Program for the implementation of the Strategy of Actions across five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017–2021, within the framework of the "Year of Dialogue with the People and Human Interests," was approved.

In Chapter III, paragraph 146, among the priority areas of economic development and liberalization, the State Committee on Competition, the Uzstandard Agency, the Technical Regulation Agency, the Ministry of Justice, the Chamber of Commerce and Industry as well as relevant ministries and agencies are instructed to consider the further development of the protection of intellectual property and consumer rights, including: increasing the transparency of procedures for registering trademark rights, industrial designs and granting patents; ensuring international recognition of intellectual property rights registered in Uzbekistan; approving action programs against the production and distribution of counterfeit products; and reviewing standards (O'zDSt) for compliance of quality and composition of ingredients with their names and brands.

In this context, amendments were introduced into several laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan, specifically the Laws "On Inventions, Utility Models and Industrial Designs," "On Trademarks, Service Marks and Appellations of Origin of Goods," "On Copyright and Related Rights," and "On Inventions, Utility Models and Industrial Designs." Business entities in their commercial activities have the right to a trade name and in the production of goods the right to trademarks.

However, at present, numerous violations of intellectual property rights continue

to be significant. In this regard, measures are being taken to strengthen the legal protection of entrepreneurs' intellectual rights. Most often, violations in the field of intellectual property are associated with the use of trademarks on the Internet. The situation is further complicated by the fact that national legislation of different states provides differing regimes of legal protection, meaning that judicial disputes regarding intellectual rights to trademarks involving a foreign element are resolved differently in different jurisdictions. Another problem involves new methods of using trademarks on the Internet, primarily in mobile applications and on social networks [2, p. 78].

In civil legal relations, the protection of property and non-property rights primarily represents a requirement that the rights holder must be free to exercise their rights, respect the interests of the owner related to deriving income, and ensure that other persons do not encroach upon these rights. In turn, this implies the obligation of other persons to respect the rights of the right holder aimed at obtaining material income. Grounds for protecting the exclusive rights of a trademark holder include a set of non-property rights exercised in accordance with legislation. This condition is based on the premise that there are grounds for legal protection of a trademark, and it is subject to such protection. In the practice of applying legislation related to the legal protection of trademarks, in a number of cases, even registered trademarks protected by law may not be eligible for legal protection. These situations may include factors such as adverse effects of a trademark on the rights and interests of others, threats to state or public security, or violations of ethical norms.

Methods of protecting absolute rights are understood as legal means, measures, and procedures ensuring recognition, observance, fulfillment, and monitoring of such rights, as well as their restoration in case of violation and the elimination of the consequences of such a violation. The scope of such methods, their types, and the procedure for their implementation are defined by law [3, p. 47].

Other scholars evaluate this concept as two distinct notions depending on the manifestation of certain characteristics. For example, according to E.P. Gavrilov, protection represents a general legal regime and is considered a measure implemented in cases of violations of rights or disputes [4, p. 50]. According to N.I. Matuzov, protection is carried out on a continuous basis and is applied in cases of rights violations [5, p. 55].

An examination of these concepts in the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan reveals that the terms "protection of rights" and "ensuring legal order" are treated as

having the same meaning.

Article 1040 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan defines the protection of the exclusive rights of an individual to a trademark and specifies the methods by which such rights may be protected. These include: the seizure of material objects with which exclusive rights were violated and material objects created as a result of such violation. In the legal protection of trademarks in this manner, the products produced using the trademark may be seized both from the violator and third parties. In such cases, the third party has the right to file a recourse claim against the violator who manufactured the counterfeit or infringing goods. Mandatory publication of information regarding the violation, including the indication of the rightful owner of the infringed rights, is also required. At the request of the right holder, based on a court decision, information about the unlawful use of the trademark must be officially published, and the violator is obliged to comply with this requirement. Protection of a trademark may also be exercised by other means provided by law. However, it is required that actions taken for the legal protection of a trademark do not deviate from established commercial practices.

Legal protection of a trademark varies depending on whether it is carried out under national or international legislation. Legal protection under national legislation is based on registration in accordance with Article 6 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 30, 2001, "On Trademarks, Service Marks and Appellations of Origin of Goods," as well as in accordance with international treaties of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

International legal protection of a trademark is carried out under the Paris Convention for the Protection of Industrial Property, adopted on March 20, 1883, based on the Republic of Uzbekistan's membership in the World Intellectual Property Organization on December 25, 1991.

Legal protection of a trademark refers to the protection of a registered designation identical or confusingly similar to a trademark, as well as to a domain name, service mark, or appellation of origin, which is identical or confusingly similar to a previously registered trademark or other means of individualization. Alternatively, legal protection of trademarks may be understood as protection in situations where two similar but distinct trademarks are used simultaneously by different persons.

Such protection also includes measures by customs authorities when importing or

exporting goods of the holder of absolute rights into or out of Uzbekistan. Protection by customs authorities is aimed not only at safeguarding the rights holder, but also internal production relations and the economic interests of the state.

In legal practice, the number of cases involving counterfeit trademarks and their delivery to consumers by various means is increasing. The legal protection of a trademark should not be limited only to the relevant territory. For example, a trademark registered in Uzbekistan for the production of a certain type of goods (e.g., under the Nice International Classification of Goods and Services) may simultaneously be used in the United States for producing other goods or services or may be in circulation as a domain name. According to Article 1102 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, a trademark is protected by law on the basis of its registration. From this article, it follows that an unregistered mark is not protected by law. For instance, if a mark belonging to Person A is identical or confusingly similar to a mark belonging to Person B, Person A does not have the right to demand that Person B cease using the mark. However, if Person A used the mark under proper registration, then Person A would have the right to demand that Person B discontinue use of the relevant trademark. The first condition of legal protection of a trademark is protection against designations similar to the trademark itself. Legal protection of a trademark refers to relations concerning the use of identical or similar designations by the holder of exclusive rights in commercial relations. A trademark is protected by law when a person demands that another person who is unfairly using the trademark cease such use. Unintentional use of a trademark by another person, which previously held priority status under civil law, cannot be considered an infringement of the exclusive rights holder. Naturally, in such a case, the holder of absolute rights has no right to demand compensation for damages caused by the violator. If an unfair user of the trademark knows that the trademark belongs to another person, the right holder has the right to demand compensation for the damages caused. Legal protection of a trademark is ensured through civil, administrative, and criminal law methods. Since issues related to the legal protection of trademarks are a subject of civil law, the focus below is on civil-law methods of protection.

Protection of industrial and commercial intellectual property objects registered in the United States is carried out in the following areas: the right holder may prohibit the cross-border movement of goods using their technologies and developments — such a

prohibition is recorded in the registry, and customs authorities are authorized to seize transported products; even upon identifying a threat of rights violation, the patent or certificate holder may submit a written demand prohibiting unlawful use of the technology and seeking compensation for damages; objections may be filed with the judicial authorities regarding the registration of rights to related technologies, termination of licensing agreements, compensation for damages, or recovery of monetary penalties; law enforcement agencies in the United States are vested with powers to initiate criminal proceedings on their own initiative or upon request of the right holder. Even when authorization is granted by the right holder, the use of an intellectual property object may still be considered an infringement.

This occurs in cases of unfair use or when a temporary holder discloses commercial or confidential information to third parties. For the duration of judicial proceedings, counterfeit goods will be confiscated as a provisional measure. Law-enforcement and customs authorities of the United States may do this even in the absence of an application from the right holder. Through such measures, damages are compensated and fines are paid to the U.S. budget if the violation is confirmed in court [8, p. 2].

Civil-law protection of a trademark is related to the fact that a person whose rights have been violated has the right to demand compensation for the harm caused by the infringer or to warn the infringer against repeating such actions due to the violation of rights or because such actions create obstacles to the exercise of those rights. Methods of legal protection of a trademark consist of a set of measures aimed at safeguarding the trademark of the holder of exclusive rights from unfair actions by other persons. According to O. Okyulov, methods of protecting absolute rights may be understood as legal means, measures, and procedures ensuring the recognition, observance, implementation, and protection of such rights by all, as well as their restoration in the event of violation and the elimination of the consequences of such violation [6, p. 107].

Legal protection of trademarks is accomplished by the following methods. First, recognition of the right to the trademark. This method of trademark protection, being a means of individualization, demonstrates that other persons recognize and respect the rights of the holder of exclusive rights to this trademark on the basis of its registration. Recognition of an absolute right is the acknowledgement of the absolute rights of the right holder with respect to an object of intellectual property by third persons or by a

state body or court. This method may be used both when a dispute exists over the ownership of exclusive rights and when no such dispute exists—for example, to confirm that the exclusive right has arisen and belongs to the right holder.

Second, restoration of the situation that existed before the violation of the right to the trademark and prevention of actions that infringe or threaten to infringe the right. This method, used to protect the rights of the holder of exclusive rights to a trademark, is carried out by the right holder and by the competent state body. This method of legal protection includes two aspects: the first consists of restoring the condition of the trademark prior to the violation of its rights, and the second consists of preventing actions that infringe or threaten to infringe those rights.

Third, recognition of a contract as invalid and application of the consequences of its invalidity. Application of the consequences of invalidity of a transaction means that, once a licensing agreement for a trademark is declared invalid, such agreement becomes void and the unrelated party must cease using the trademark. Protection of the rights of the holder of exclusive rights by compensation of damages caused by the infringer for unlawful use of a trademark is one of the most common methods in civil legal relations.

According to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Trade Names,” a trade name is the individual designation of a legal entity—a commercial organization—the exclusive right to which arises at the moment of its state registration. Accordingly, after state registration, business entities acquire an exclusive right to their trade name. Legal protection of a trade name is granted from the moment of state registration of the legal entity; for a foreign legal entity, legal protection is granted from the date it begins conducting business activities as a participant of civil commerce within the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In these cases, the fundamental conditions of legal protection of a trademark are implemented in accordance with the relevant international legal instruments to which Uzbekistan is a party.

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LEGAL REGULATION OF PROFIT-AND-LOSS SHARING CONTRACTS IN ISLAMIC FINANCE: ANALYSIS OF MUSHARAKAH AND MUDARABAH STRUCTURES AND THEIR ADAPTATION TO THE NATIONAL LEGAL SYSTEM OF UZBEKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

The article examines the legal aspects of Islamic profit-and-loss sharing contracts — musharakah and mudarabah, which constitute key instruments of interest-free financing in the Islamic legal tradition. The paper analyzes the theoretical and legal foundations of these contracts, their historical evolution, and their modern normative interpretation in Muslim jurisdictions. Particular attention is paid to the challenges of adapting these contractual structures to the national legal system of the Republic of Uzbekistan, where recent years have seen increasing interest in the implementation of Islamic financial mechanisms. Based on a comparative legal analysis of the legislation of Malaysia, Saudi Arabia, Turkey, and Pakistan, the study identifies models of successful implementation of Islamic contracts within secular legal systems. The article proposes conceptual approaches to harmonizing the norms of civil legislation with the principles of Islamic financial law, including the use of soft law mechanisms (AAOIFI and IFSB standards) and the establishment of a legal status for Islamic financial institutions in Uzbekistan. The scientific novelty of the research lies in substantiating a model of hybrid regulation of Islamic profit-and-loss sharing contracts in Uzbekistan through the application of soft law mechanisms — an area that has not previously received comprehensive legal analysis in national doctrine.

Keywords: Islamic finance, musharakah, mudarabah, Islamic contract (aqd), civil law, entrepreneurial activity, soft law, AAOIFI, Uzbekistan.

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**ПРАВОВОЕ РЕГУЛИРОВАНИЕ ДОГОВОРОВ ДОЛЕВОГО УЧАСТИЯ
В ИСЛАМСКОМ ФИНАНСИРОВАНИИ: АНАЛИЗ КОНСТРУКЦИЙ**

МУШАРАКА И МУДАРИБА И ИХ АДАПТАЦИЯ В НАЦИОНАЛЬНУЮ ПРАВОВУЮ СИСТЕМУ УЗБЕКИСТАНА

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье исследуются правовые аспекты исламских договоров долевого участия — мушарака и мудариба, которые представляют собой ключевые инструменты беспроцентного финансирования в исламской правовой традиции. Рассматриваются теоретико-правовые основы этих договоров, их историческая эволюция и современная нормативная интерпретация в мусульманских странах. Особое внимание уделено проблемам адаптации данных договорных конструкций в национальную правовую систему Республики Узбекистан, где в последние годы наблюдается повышенный интерес к внедрению исламских финансовых механизмов. На основе сравнительно-правового анализа законодательства Малайзии, Саудовской Аравии, Турции и Пакистана выявлены модели успешной имплементации исламских договоров в светскую правовую систему. В статье предлагаются концептуальные подходы к гармонизации норм гражданского законодательства с принципами исламского финансового права, включая использование механизмов soft law (стандарты AAOIFI и IFSB) и создание правового статуса исламских финансовых институтов в Узбекистане. Научная новизна исследования заключается в обосновании модели гибридного регулирования исламских договоров долевого участия в Узбекистане с использованием механизмов soft law, что ранее не получало комплексного правового анализа в отечественной доктрине.

Ключевые слова: исламское финансирование, мушарака, мудариба, исламский договор (aqd), гражданское право, предпринимательская деятельность, soft law, AAOIFI, Узбекистан.

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent decades, Islamic finance has evolved from a local practice of religiously conditioned transactions into a global legal and economic phenomenon encompassing more than 70 countries worldwide. According to the Islamic Development Bank, the total assets of Islamic financial institutions exceeded USD 3 trillion in 2024, with the sector's annual growth rate consistently surpassing 10% [1]. This dynamic reflects not only the growing demand for ethically grounded forms of investment but also the systemic recognition of Islamic finance as an alternative model for fair risk distribution and the promotion of the real economy.

The central element of the Islamic financial system is the profit-and-loss sharing contract — in particular, the structures of musharakah (joint partnership) and mudarabah (trust-based investment). Unlike traditional credit agreements based on fixed interest rates, these forms provide for the sharing of profits and losses among project

participants, in accordance with the principles of justice and the prohibition of riba [2]. These mechanisms constitute the foundation of Islamic business ethics, where financial gain is inseparable from real economic participation and responsibility.

It is assumed that the adaptation of Islamic profit-and-loss sharing contracts in Uzbekistan is possible through a hybrid regulatory model that combines civil law norms with soft law standards.

However, despite the international recognition of Islamic finance, the legal adaptation of musharakah and mudarabah contracts within secular legal systems remains a complex task. In countries with a continental legal model (including Uzbekistan), Islamic contracts do not possess direct normative status, and their application encounters several legal collisions — primarily in the areas of civil legislation, banking regulation, and the protection of parties' rights.

The issue is particularly relevant for Uzbekistan, where recent years have seen growing interest in the development of Islamic banking products and Sharia-compliant financial instruments. Since 2021, the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan has been working on a draft law on Islamic banking; however, unresolved questions remain regarding the legal classification of Islamic contracts, the applicability of AAOIFI standards, and the role of Sharia advisory boards.

The study aims to analyze the legal nature of musharakah and mudarabah as profit-and-loss sharing contracts, to identify their conceptual differences from civil law analogues (partnership, trust management, and investment agreement), and to determine possible models for their implementation within the national legal system of Uzbekistan.

The scientific novelty of this study lies in its systematic comparative-legal approach, which integrates Islamic legal doctrine (fiqh al-muamalat) with modern business law, viewing Islamic contractual structures not as exotic religious forms, but as potential instruments of sustainable economic development.

The purpose of this study is to develop conceptual and normative proposals for integrating Islamic profit-and-loss sharing contracts into the national legal system of Uzbekistan, taking into account international experience and the principles of soft law.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study is based on an interdisciplinary approach that combines the legal dogmatics of Islamic law (fiqh) with the tools of modern comparative legal analysis applied to secular legal systems. The methodological framework of the research relies on three key levels: normative, doctrinal, and comparative-legal.

At the first level, the study examines the primary sources of Islamic law — the Qur'an, the Sunnah, ijma (consensus), and qiyas (analogical reasoning), as well as their legal development within the framework of the fiqh schools, primarily the Hanafi school, which has traditionally dominated in Central Asia. Particular attention is given to the provisions regulating contractual relations (aqd) and the principles of profit and loss distribution.

At the second level, the analysis focuses on contemporary standards of Islamic financial regulation developed by international organizations: AAOIFI (Accounting and Auditing Organization for Islamic Financial Institutions) — in particular, Shariah Standards No. 12 “Mudarabah” and No. 13 “Musharakah”; and IFSB (Islamic Financial Services Board) — recommendations on corporate governance and risk management in Islamic financial institutions.

At the third level, the study examines the legislation of countries with different models of Islamic finance regulation, including: Malaysia — an example of a dual system in which Islamic financial law operates in parallel with civil law; Saudi Arabia — a monistic system where Sharia serves as the primary source of law; and Turkey and Pakistan — countries applying mixed models of legal recognition of Islamic instruments in the banking and entrepreneurial sectors.

For contextual analysis, the study also employs national legal acts of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in particular: the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan (2024 edition); the Law “On Banks and Banking Activities” (2023 edition); as well as draft laws and by-laws related to the introduction of Islamic banking and the development of the legal status of Islamic financial institutions.

The doctrinal component of the research is represented by the works of both classical and contemporary Islamic legal scholars, including Wahbah al-Zuhayli (al-Fiqh al-Islami wa Adillatuhu), Ibn Rushd (Bidayat al-Mujtahid), Mohammad Hashim Kamali (Principles of Islamic Jurisprudence), and the study by Frank E. Vogel and Samuel L. Hayes (Islamic Law and Finance: Religion, Risk, and Return).

Particular importance is attached to the comparison of the concept of aqd (contract) in fiqh with the doctrinal categories of the continental legal system — contract, transaction, and obligation. Such a comparison makes it possible to reveal the differences in the teleology and axiology of these concepts: Islamic law views the contract as an act of moral and legal responsibility, whereas civil law perceives it primarily as an instrument of property exchange and risk distribution.

The following methods were employed in the course of the study: the comparative-legal method, applied to the analysis of the legal systems of Malaysia, Saudi Arabia, Turkey, and Uzbekistan, made it possible to identify the specific features of the legal adaptation of Islamic contractual structures within a secular legal framework. The historical-legal method provided an opportunity to trace the evolution of the musharakah and mudarabah institutions from classical fiqh to modern banking regulation. The formal-legal method was used to analyze the conceptual apparatus of Islamic and civil law in terms of their interrelation and differentiation. The systemic-structural approach was applied to identify legal collisions and potential points of harmonization between Islamic and national law. The doctrinal-analytical method made it possible to correlate the norms of Islamic law with the principles of soft law, which is particularly important in the context of legal implementation in Uzbekistan.

Thus, the chosen methodology makes it possible to combine the depth of the theological understanding of Islamic contracts with the precision of legal analysis, ensuring the comprehensiveness and scientific reliability of the results obtained.

Through the application of the comparative-legal method, key differences were identified between musharakah and mudarabah contracts and their civil law analogues in Uzbekistan. Using the historical-legal and systemic-structural approaches, the stages of evolution of Islamic contracts and potential points of harmonization with national law were determined. The formal-legal and doctrinal-analytical methods made it possible to refine the conceptual framework and define the conceptual boundaries of soft law in the context of Islamic financial regulation.

The applied methodology makes it possible to avoid confessional bias and ensures the scientific neutrality of the analysis of Islamic norms within the framework of a secular legal system.

III. RESULTS

The musharakah contract (from the Arabic *sharika* — partnership) in Islamic law is regarded as a form of joint entrepreneurship based on the pooling of contributions and the equality of the parties [2].

The study of classical *fiqh* sources shows that the foundations of Islamic contract theory were laid by the jurists of the Hanafi school, who sought to systematize property relations within the broader framework of *muamalat*. Of particular importance in this respect is the treatise *al-Hidayah* by Burhan al-Din al-Marghinani — one of the most authoritative and frequently commented works of Hanafi jurisprudence, which has profoundly influenced the subsequent doctrine of Islamic finance and commercial law.

In the fourth volume of *al-Hidayah*, the contracts of musharakah and mudarabah are classified as part of the musharakah category — joint contracts belonging to the section of *muamalat*. The author establishes an internal hierarchy of transactions: first come commutative contracts (*muawadat*), with *bay* (sale) as the fundamental form; followed by participatory contracts (*musharakah*, *mudarabah*); and finally, gratuitous acts (*hiba*, *waqf*).

Al-Marghinani defines *bay* as “the transfer and acquisition of ownership,” a general formulation encompassing not only sale but also partnership contracts, since these too involve a reciprocal act of transferring proprietary rights. He defines partnership as a mutual granting of shares in each other’s property for joint disposition and participation in profit. In *Kitab al-Qirad* (on *mudarabah*), he specifies that it is a partnership in profit but not in capital: capital is provided by one party, while labor is contributed by the other [3].

In al-Marghinani’s classification, *musharakah* and *mudarabah* derive from the principle of *bay*: they retain the element of commutative exchange (profit ↔ risk), but realized not as a single act of sale, rather as a long-term co-ownership and entrepreneurial participation. This allows these contracts to be viewed as a special form

of commutative transactions with elements of solidarity and trust — a characteristic feature of Islamic legal thought.

Modern Islamic standards elaborate on these provisions by formulating precise legal definitions. According to AAOIFI Shariah Standards No. 12 “Mudarabah” and No. 13 “Musharakah,” musharakah is defined as: “A contract between two or more parties to contribute capital for the joint execution of a commercial activity with the purpose of earning profit, which is to be distributed according to mutual agreement, provided that losses are borne proportionally to each party’s share in the capital” [4].

Mudarabah is defined as: “A mudarabah is a contract between the owner of capital (rabb al-mal) and an entrepreneur (mudarib), whereby the former provides capital to the latter to engage in business activity with the objective of generating profit, which is to be shared between the parties in pre-agreed ratios; losses are borne solely by the capital owner, unless they result from the mudarib’s breach of contractual terms” [4].

The Islamic Financial Services Board (IFSB), in its Guiding Principles on Risk Sharing in Islamic Finance (2023), clarifies that musharakah represents a form of joint investment in which all participants bear proportionate risks and participate in management based on mutual consent [5].

Thus, whereas in classical fiqh doctrine musharakah was primarily viewed as a moral and legal category of equitable partnership, in modern legal regulation it acquires a clearly structured economic and legal status, serving as a contractual basis for entrepreneurial activity grounded in the joint participation of capital and management decisions. According to contemporary standards, musharakah is not merely a partnership in profit but an instrument of joint business operation, in which risk, profit, and managerial responsibility are interrelated and legally allocated among the parties.

The legal nature of musharakah reflects the principle of equitable risk sharing, which stands in contrast to fixed gain derived without participation in productive activity (riba). This model renders musharakah not only a financial instrument but also a mechanism of moral and legal regulation of economic relations, as it eliminates the possibility of exploitation and unequal income distribution.

Contemporary empirical studies confirm that the risk-sharing element is a key factor in the resilience of Islamic financial models. According to Uddin, musharakah and mudarabah contracts demonstrate a higher degree of entrepreneurial risk distribution compared to classical investment agreements in civil law, making them effective instruments for economies with developing legal systems [6].

From the standpoint of civil law, musharakah is functionally similar to a simple partnership agreement (Articles 774–784 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan) [7]; however, there are fundamental differences between the two. While civil law allows for the establishment of guaranteed remuneration or a fixed share of profit regardless of the business outcome, Islamic law deems this impermissible. Thus, musharakah combines the characteristics of both a contract and an ethical obligation,

which necessitates a special legal regime for its implementation within national legislation.

Modern Western scholars also offer various interpretations of the legal nature of *mudarabah*. Frank Vogel and Samuel Hayes note that *mudarabah* represents “a compromise between the ideal of equitable risk sharing and the necessity of entrepreneurial initiative,” as it merges the principles of partnership with elements of agency management [8]. According to Mohammad Hashim Kamali, *mudarabah* reflects “the Islamic concept of economic solidarity, in which labor and capital are united within a framework of mutual responsibility rather than subordination” [9]. Mahmoud El-Gamal interprets *mudarabah* as “a prototype of the modern asset management contract, distinguished by the prohibition of fixed returns and the preservation of the ethical nature of risk” [10].

In comparison with civil law, *mudarabah* bears certain similarities to the institution of trust management of property (Chapter 52 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan) [7]. However, the key distinction lies in the purpose of the contract: in Islamic law, the primary objective is not the extraction of fixed profit, but the assurance of fair participation of both parties in entrepreneurial risk and outcome. Moreover, *mudarabah* does not recognize the concept of “guaranteed return” — any form of promised interest is regarded as *riba* and renders the contract invalid.

Thus, *mudarabah* represents a unique legal construct that combines elements of investment and trust-based contracts, yet is grounded in the principle of moral responsibility and equitable profit distribution.

Table 1. Comparative Analysis of Musharakah and Mudarabah

Criterion	Musharakah	Mudarabah
Nature of participation	Joint participation of all partners in capital and management	Management is carried out solely by the <i>mudarib</i>, while the capital is provided by the investor
Profit distribution	By mutual agreement, proportionate to the share of participation	According to an agreed ratio (e.g., 60/40), not fixed in absolute figures
Loss distribution	Proportional to each partner’s contribution to capital	Only the investor bears losses, unless caused by the <i>mudarib</i>’s fault
Civil law analogy (Uzbek law)	Simple partnership	Trust management / investment agreement

Ethical component	Joint entrepreneurship without exploitation	Trust and moral-legal responsibility for good-faith management
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This comparison shows that both contractual structures embody the principle of partnership and mutual responsibility, yet differ in the degree of the parties' participation in management and risk. When adapted to a secular legal system, their elements can be utilized to develop a new type of equity-based financing agreements founded on interest-free participation and transparency.

The analysis of the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan shows that the current legal system has not yet created the conditions for the full-scale use of Islamic profit-and-loss sharing contracts — *musharakah* and *mudarabah* — in the field of entrepreneurial activity. These contractual forms are inherently oriented toward the real sector of the economy, where the parties combine capital and labor for joint business operations; however, national law lacks mechanisms that would allow their proper legal qualification and protection.

Firstly, the civil legislation does not define the legal status of joint investment contracts based on the principle of risk participation. The existing provisions on simple partnership (Chapter 53 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan) and trust management (Chapter 52 of the Civil Code) allow for fixed forms of remuneration, which makes it impossible to apply contractual structures based on the distribution of profits and losses according to performance results [7]. Thus, Islamic partnership forms do not fit into the traditional system of the law of obligations and require an independent legal qualification.

Secondly, the legislation on entrepreneurial activity lacks a category of equity participation agreements without the formation of a legal entity, although such a form constitutes the foundation of Islamic contracts such as *musharakah* and *mudarabah*. As a result, joint projects structured on Islamic principles are forced to be formalized through corporate entities — companies or partnerships — which contradicts the essence of Islamic contracts that presuppose flexibility, autonomy of will, and equality of the parties without the establishment of a separate legal personality.

Thirdly, the national regulatory framework does not provide a unified approach to recognizing Islamic contracts as valid legal grounds for entrepreneurial obligations. The provisions regulating investment activity and public-private partnerships are primarily oriented toward capital provided on a remunerative basis, which is inconsistent with the idea of joint participation in profits and losses. Consequently, Islamic financing forms effectively fall outside the legal framework, lacking both protection and established procedures for dispute resolution.

Fourthly, subordinate legislation does not contain regulations governing contracts based on the principles of joint capital management, which creates uncertainty in their

judicial qualification. International standards (AAOIFI, IFSB) can serve as soft law instruments to determine the legal nature of such transactions; however, their application has not yet been established in either arbitration or commercial practice in Uzbekistan. Therefore, the absence of normative recognition of Islamic profit-and-loss sharing contracts hinders their use in the real sector and limits the development of entrepreneurial initiatives based on ethical and partnership principles. To overcome these barriers, it is necessary to develop national legal constructs of joint entrepreneurship that would enable the parties to freely conclude agreements based on participation in profits and responsibility for losses without requiring incorporation through corporate forms.

As a transitional mechanism, experimental legal regimes (sandboxes) can be used to test such contracts in specific sectors — for example, in venture investments, agricultural cooperatives, or family businesses. These regulatory zones would allow the practical testing of Islamic contractual mechanisms in entrepreneurial practice and facilitate the development of standards for their subsequent normative consolidation.

The results of the study make it possible to conclude that Islamic profit-and-loss sharing contracts can serve as a legal foundation for the development of fair and ethical entrepreneurship. For instance, musharakah provides a partnership model in which risk and profit are shared proportionally, while mudarabah represents a trust-based form of investment in which professional competence and the good faith of the manager play a decisive role.

For Uzbekistan, the implementation of these contractual structures can not only diversify the financial system but also promote the development of small and medium-sized enterprises through joint financing mechanisms that operate without debt pressure or interest burden.

IV. DISCUSSION

The conducted research demonstrates that the attempt to integrate Islamic contractual structures into a secular legal system necessitates a rethinking of the very concept of a contract. In Islamic law, a contract (aqd) possesses not only a legal but also an ethical dimension, serving as an expression of the parties' intention (niyyah) and good faith (amanah). In civil law, by contrast, a contract is a manifestation of will aimed at creating property-related consequences.

This distinction explains the key collision between Islamic and continental approaches: in the former, law is inseparable from morality, whereas in the latter, it is autonomous. Consequently, the direct transplantation of Islamic contractual forms is impossible without taking into account their teleological essence. The focus, therefore, should not be on mechanically borrowing formulations, but on creating a legal regime capable of “translating” Islamic categories into the language of positive law while preserving their economic and ethical meaning.

The analysis of legal systems shows that countries with developed practices of

Islamic finance have developed various models of institutional adaptation.

Malaysia implements a dualist model in which Islamic contracts receive independent legislative recognition alongside civil ones. The Islamic Financial Services Act 2013 enshrines the principles of Shariah compliance and establishes a system of Shariah Advisory Councils under Bank Negara [11]. This model demonstrates the possibility of coexistence between two legal regimes within a unified economic framework.

As noted by Hasan and Hassan, the Malaysian model has shown the greatest flexibility in adapting musharakah and mudarabah contracts, since the country's legislation allows them to operate within the general legal framework without requiring religious qualification of the transaction. The authors emphasize that the legal success of this model lies not only in the institutional recognition of Islamic contracts but also in their procedural integration into the civil judicial system [12].

Some scholars point to the risk of "legal dualism" arising from the coexistence of soft law and civil law norms [12]; however, under the conditions of Uzbekistan, a hybrid model appears to be the most optimal solution in terms of balancing legal certainty with Shariah compliance.

Saudi Arabia represents a monistic model, where Shariah is the primary source of law and all contracts are interpreted through the lens of fiqh. This system ensures full adherence to Islamic principles but limits the flexibility of legal regulation and access to international financial instruments.

Turkey and Pakistan employ hybrid models, in which Islamic contracts are implemented into banking law through the institutions of participation banking. These systems utilize soft law standards (AAOIFI, IFSB) and local regulatory acts to ensure the practical application of Islamic financial instruments within secular economies.

The comparison shows that in states where religious and civil law are institutionally separated, the best results are achieved through the gradual integration of Islamic principles into subordinate regulation rather than through constitutional reform.

The modern Islamic financial system is characterized by the presence of supranational standards developed by non-governmental organizations — primarily AAOIFI and IFSB. These documents do not possess binding legal force but function as transnational normative benchmarks, effectively constituting a form of soft law.

The question of the legal status of these standards is particularly relevant for countries seeking to implement Islamic finance without compromising the secular nature of their legislation. The experience of Malaysia and Turkey demonstrates that AAOIFI standards can be incorporated into national acts through referential provisions, thereby preserving the legislative structure while creating a unified field of legal application [13].

For Uzbekistan, such an approach appears the most realistic: soft law can serve as a "bridge" between Islamic ethics and the civil legal system, ensuring a balance between

flexibility and legal certainty. The introduction of Shariah advisory councils under the Central Bank and the recognition of AAOIFI standards as recommendatory sources would provide a foundation for the future codification of Islamic finance [14].

The distinctive feature of Islamic contractual structures lies in the fact that they are not limited to economic relations but presuppose the unity of legal and ethical content. In Islamic law, the notions of justice (adl) and trust (amanah) possess normative force and define the boundaries of permissible conduct between the parties.

From this perspective, musharakah and mudarabah exemplify an alternative approach to entrepreneurship — ethical entrepreneurship, in which permissible profit is conditioned by participation in risk and labor, rather than by capital as an independent source of income. The introduction of such principles into civil law can enhance corporate responsibility and the transparency of financial operations [15].

For Uzbekistan, this has not only legal but also social significance: Islamic contracts may become instruments for fostering trust in business relations — a crucial factor for a developing market economy.

Based on the conducted analysis, the author arrives at the following positions:

1. The adaptation of Islamic profit-and-loss sharing contracts is possible only with the preservation of their essential principles — risk sharing and the prohibition of riba. Any attempt to formally “fit” them into the existing institutions of civil law would distort their substance.

2. The most suitable model for Uzbekistan is a hybrid regulatory regime that combines civil law norms with soft law mechanisms and Shariah supervision.

3. A separate legal category of “Islamic financial institution” should be introduced, encompassing banks and investment companies operating on risk-sharing principles.

4. To reduce legal uncertainty, it is recommended to implement pilot regulatory projects in the form of experimental legal zones (sandboxes), where Islamic financial products can be tested in accordance with international standards.

5. The further development of Islamic finance should be accompanied by the formation of a national doctrine of Islamic business law, integrating the norms of fiqh with contemporary concepts of financial regulation.

V. CONCLUSION

The study of the legal nature of Islamic profit-and-loss sharing contracts — musharakah and mudarabah — has made it possible to identify their essential characteristics and to determine their potential for implementation within the national legal system of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The analysis has shown that these contractual structures represent not merely alternative forms of investment, but an integrated ethical and legal concept of entrepreneurship based on the fair distribution of

risk and responsibility.

The comparison of Islamic contractual models with their civil law analogues revealed both common structural elements (mutual consent of the parties, profit distribution, and orientation toward commercial outcomes) and fundamental differences. In particular, Islamic law excludes the institution of guaranteed return, allowing profit only in the presence of entrepreneurial risk. These features give Islamic contracts a distinct legal identity, differentiating them from traditional private law institutions.

The examination of foreign experience (Malaysia, Saudi Arabia, Turkey, and Pakistan) demonstrated that the successful adaptation of Islamic finance is possible under the condition of institutional recognition of soft law standards (AAOIFI, IFSB) and the establishment of national Shariah advisory councils. Such a model ensures a balance between Shariah requirements and the principles of legal certainty, which is particularly important for countries with a secular legal system.

In the context of Uzbekistan, the research identified a number of normative and conceptual gaps that hinder the development of Islamic finance: the absence of a defined legal status for Islamic institutions, uncertainty in the regulation of interest-free products, and inconsistencies between the risk-sharing principle and the provisions of civil law. Addressing these challenges is possible through a hybrid regulatory model that combines national legal norms with elements of Islamic legal doctrine.

The findings presented in this study make it possible to propose the following directions for the further development of legislation and academic research:

1. Development of a special law “On Islamic Financial Institutions”, defining their legal status, organizational forms, and supervisory mechanisms.
2. Implementation of AAOIFI and IFSB standards in the form of subordinate regulations or recommendations issued by the Central Bank.
3. Establishment of a National Shariah Council under the financial regulator, performing advisory and expert functions.
4. Formation of a doctrine of Islamic business law as a field of modern legal science that integrates fiqh norms with the instruments of civil regulation.
5. Conducting empirical studies aimed at assessing the effectiveness of Islamic contractual models in promoting small and medium-sized enterprises.

The results of the study confirm that Islamic profit-and-loss sharing contracts can be integrated into Uzbekistan’s legal system without violating the principle of secularism, provided that a hybrid regulatory approach is developed. This will create opportunities for establishing an ethically sustainable and financially inclusive model of entrepreneurship that aligns with both national development priorities and international standards of Islamic finance. The findings contribute to the advancement of comparative and financial law by broadening the understanding of the limits and possibilities of

harmonizing Islamic and civil law institutions. The practical significance of the research lies in formulating proposals for the modernization of Uzbekistan's legislation aimed at integrating Islamic contractual mechanisms into the national economy.

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THE LEGAL SIGNIFICANCE OF ELECTRONIC AGREEMENTS AND RISK MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS IN THE CIVIL LAW OF UZBEKISTAN AND CHINA

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Abstract

The article is devoted to the study of the legal significance of electronic agreements and risk management systems in the civil law of Uzbekistan and China. It analyzes the legal foundations for the conclusion and execution of electronic contracts, including the provisions of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Law of Uzbekistan “On Electronic Document Flow,” and the Law of the People’s Republic of China “On Electronic Signatures.” Particular attention is paid to the validity of electronic agreements, party identification, the evidentiary value of electronic documents, and the risks arising during their conclusion and performance. A comparative analysis of the approaches of the two countries to risk management, including legal, technical, and organizational mechanisms, is conducted. Examples of judicial practice in Uzbekistan and China are examined, demonstrating the specifics of applying electronic agreements in civil transactions. Based on the analysis, trends in the harmonization of national legal frameworks and directions for improving legislation to ensure the reliable functioning of electronic contracts are identified.

Keywords: electronic agreement, legal validity, civil law, risk management, Uzbekistan, China, electronic signature, electronic document flow, party identification, judicial practice, legal regulation, digital economy.

ЮРИДИЧЕСКАЯ ЗНАЧИМОСТЬ ЭЛЕКТРОННЫХ СОГЛАШЕНИЙ И СИСТЕМЫ РИСК-МЕНЕДЖМЕНТА В ГРАЖДАНСКОМ ПРАВЕ УЗБЕКИСТАНА И КИТАЯ

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Аннотация

Статья посвящена исследованию юридической значимости электронных соглашений и систем управления рисками в гражданском праве Узбекистана и Китая. Анализируются правовые основы заключения и исполнения электронных договоров, включая положения Гражданского кодекса Республики Узбекистан, Закона РУз «Об электронном документообороте» и Закона КНР «Об электронной подписи». Особое внимание уделено вопросам действительности электронных соглашений, идентификации сторон, доказательственной силы электронных документов и рискам, возникающим при их заключении и исполнении. Проведен сравнительный анализ подходов двух стран к управлению рисками, включая правовые, технические и организационные механизмы. Рассмотрены примеры судебной практики Узбекистана и Китая, демонстрирующие особенности применения электронных соглашений в гражданском обороте. На основе анализа выявлены тенденции гармонизации национальных правовых режимов и направления совершенствования законодательства для обеспечения надежного функционирования электронных договоров.

Ключевые слова: электронное соглашение, юридическая сила, гражданское право, управление рисками, Узбекистан, Китай, электронная подпись, электронный документооборот, идентификация сторон, судебная практика, правовое регулирование, цифровая экономика.

Introduction

Modern digital technologies have a profound impact on the transformation of economic relations, necessitating the modernization of legal mechanisms that regulate them. One of the key phenomena of the digital economy is the electronic agreement (EA), which has become an essential tool in civil and commercial transactions, particularly in the context of globalization and cross-border trade.

Electronic agreements significantly reduce transaction costs, accelerate the conclusion of contracts, and enhance transparency. However, they also give rise to new legal challenges, including the identification of parties, ensuring the authenticity of electronic signatures, preserving the integrity of electronic documents, and recognizing their evidentiary value in judicial proceedings [1, 2].

For countries with rapidly developing digital economies, such as the Republic of Uzbekistan and the People's Republic of China, legal regulation of electronic agreements is particularly relevant. In Uzbekistan, the legal foundation for electronic

transactions is established in the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which in Article 105 allows transactions in written form, including electronic form [3], while Article 366 explicitly provides for the possibility of concluding contracts through the exchange of electronic messages [3]. Additional regulation is provided by the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Electronic Document Flow,” Article 7 of which grants electronic documents equal legal force with paper documents [4].

In China, similar legal mechanisms are governed by the Law of the People’s Republic of China “On Electronic Signatures” (2005, amended in 2019), which establishes the legal significance of electronic signatures, conditions for their use, and the authority of certified certification centers [5]. Furthermore, China was among the first countries to establish specialized Internet courts to adjudicate disputes related to electronic agreements and digital evidence [6].

The relevance of this study is driven by the need for a comparative analysis of the legal nature of electronic agreements in Uzbekistan and China, the identification of their common and distinctive features, and an examination of existing mechanisms for mitigating risks associated with their conclusion and execution.

The aim of this study is to conduct a comprehensive comparative legal analysis of electronic agreements under the civil law of Uzbekistan and China, to identify their legal nature, regulatory features, and existing risk management mechanisms.

To achieve this aim, the study sets the following objectives:

1. Determine the legal nature of electronic agreements in the civil law of Uzbekistan and China.
2. Examine the conditions for the validity of electronic agreements and their execution procedures.
3. Analyze the main legal risks arising from the conclusion and performance of electronic agreements.
4. Review current legal, technical, and organizational mechanisms for risk mitigation.
5. Conduct a comparative analysis of legislative approaches in Uzbekistan and China, including judicial practice.
6. Formulate conclusions and recommendations for improving national legislation in the context of digital transformation.

Legal regulation of electronic agreements and digital transactions has become a subject of active scholarly research in recent years. Most studies focus on the legal nature of electronic agreements, their validity conditions, and legal risks associated with their conclusion and execution.

In domestic civil law scholarship, electronic agreements are considered a type of contract executed in written form, with particular emphasis on the legal validity of

electronic signatures and electronic documents [1, 2]. Uzbek researchers highlight the importance of adapting national legislation to the demands of the digital economy, stressing the need to improve regulations concerning party identification and the evidentiary value of electronic documents [3].

International literature emphasizes the challenges of unifying legal regulation of electronic agreements across borders. For instance, German and American scholars analyze the legal nature of electronic offers and acceptances, as well as cross-border recognition of electronic contracts [4, 5]. Chinese legal doctrine actively develops the concept of Internet courts and recognizes electronic evidence as a key component of judicial proceedings in the digital economy [6].

Comparative legal research shows that while the basic principles—such as the equivalence of paper and electronic documents and the legal validity of electronic signatures—are similar, approaches vary between countries. For example, China allows contracts to be concluded through electronic platforms even without a qualified electronic signature if there is factual evidence of parties' consent [6], whereas Uzbek law requires stricter formal compliance [3].

Despite a significant number of studies on the topic, research gaps remain. In particular, mechanisms for minimizing risks in cross-border electronic transactions are insufficiently explored, as are questions regarding the harmonization of judicial practice between countries with different legal systems. Furthermore, the admissibility of “smart contracts” in the civil law of Uzbekistan and China remains an open question, warranting further scientific investigation.

Methodology

This study is based on a combination of general scientific and private-law methods, enabling a comprehensive analysis of the legal nature of electronic agreements in the civil law of Uzbekistan and China, as well as the identification of specific regulatory and practical features [7].

The research employed dialectical, analytical, and synthetic methods, along with a comparative-historical approach. These methods allowed the study to trace the evolution of legal regulation of electronic agreements, identify development trends, and explore prospects for legislative improvement in both countries [8].

The primary research tool was the comparative-legal method, applied to analyze the provisions of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Electronic Document Flow” [4], and the Law of the People's Republic of China “On Electronic Signatures” [5, 9]. This approach helped to identify both common patterns and national specificities in the regulation of electronic agreements.

Special attention was given to the study of normative legal acts governing electronic document flow, the legal validity of electronic signatures, and procedures for executing contracts in the digital environment. The method of legal interpretation—

grammatical, systemic, and teleological—was applied to ensure accurate understanding of legislative norms and their interrelations [1, 2].

To assess the practical application of legislation, judicial decisions in Uzbekistan and China were analyzed. For instance, the study examined the case of LLC “SmartLog” vs. Individual Entrepreneur T.A. (Uzbekistan, 2023), as well as a dispute between a purchaser and the platform JD.com (China, 2021). This analysis allowed for an evaluation of how laws are implemented in practice and the risks that remain for participants in civil circulation.

Additionally, a comparative analysis of international practices was conducted, including experiences from the European Union and the United States in regulating electronic contracts. This enabled the identification of potential directions for adapting foreign solutions to the national legal systems of Uzbekistan and China [10, 11].

Overall, the methodological framework ensured a comprehensive examination of the subject, the identification of risks, and the formulation of possible ways to improve legislation in the context of the digital economy.

Results

The conducted research on the legal regulation of electronic agreements in the civil law of Uzbekistan and China yielded several significant findings with both theoretical and practical relevance.

Legal status of electronic agreements. In Uzbekistan, an electronic agreement is considered equivalent to a traditional written contract, provided that the requirements set forth in Articles 105 and 366 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan (hereinafter – CC RUz) are met [3]. Furthermore, Article 7 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Electronic Document Flow” explicitly establishes that electronic documents hold the same legal force as paper documents [4, 12].

In China, comparable regulation is provided by the Law “On Electronic Signatures” (2005, amended in 2019), where Articles 10, 16, and 26 stipulate the conditions for executing transactions via electronic means, provided that reliable methods of party identification are employed [5, 9, 13].

Validity conditions. The study confirmed that in both countries, the validity of an electronic agreement depends on general civil law requirements: legal capacity of the parties, their voluntary expression of will, legality of the transaction content, and compliance with the prescribed form. A distinguishing feature is the need for electronic identification measures: qualified electronic signatures (QES) in Uzbekistan and licensed certification authorities in China, ensuring signature authenticity and party authentication [4, 5, 12].

Risk analysis. Comparative analysis revealed several key risks associated with electronic agreements:

1. Possibility of forgery or misuse of electronic signatures.
2. Difficulties in verifying counterparties in cross-border transactions.

3. Potential compromise of document integrity during transmission.

4. Divergence in national legal requirements, creating uncertainty for international contracts [14, 15].

Risk management mechanisms. Both Uzbekistan and China have developed functional, though differently structured, mechanisms to mitigate these risks:

Establishment of state and accredited certification centers (ID.UZ and E-Sign in Uzbekistan; CA centers in China).

Requirements for storage and archiving of electronic documents in secure systems (Article 16, Law of RUz “On Electronic Document Flow”; Articles 17–19, Law of PRC “On Electronic Signatures”) [4, 5].

Recognition of electronic documents as admissible evidence in courts (specialized Internet Courts in China since 2017; case law in Uzbekistan mainly limited to matters confirming the validity of qualified QES) [11, 16].

Judicial practice. Examination of court cases highlighted differences in national approaches:

In Uzbekistan (LLC “SmartLog” vs. IP T.A., 2023), the court denied recognition of the electronic agreement due to the absence of a qualified electronic signature, despite evidence of correspondence and payment.

In China (JD.com case, 2021), the Internet Court recognized the supply contract based on the parties’ actions and electronic confirmation of the order.

These examples illustrate the relative flexibility of the Chinese system compared to the more formalistic Uzbek framework, influencing legal certainty for electronic transaction participants [16, 17].

Overall findings. The study indicates that electronic agreements in the civil law of Uzbekistan and China possess legal validity equivalent to traditional written contracts. However, differences in requirements for execution and authentication create varying levels of protection for the rights of parties. Both countries have adopted measures to manage associated risks, but the level of institutional support and judicial flexibility remains higher in China [11, 13, 17].

Discussion

The findings of this study demonstrate both convergence and divergence in the legal regulation of electronic agreements in Uzbekistan and China. While both legal systems recognize the equivalence of electronic and paper-based agreements, their approaches to formal requirements, institutional support, and risk management differ significantly.

1. Formal requirements and flexibility. A key distinction lies in the treatment of electronic signatures. In Uzbekistan, a qualified electronic signature (QES) is mandatory for the validity of an electronic agreement, as stipulated by Article 7 of the Law “On Electronic Document Flow” [4]. This strict formalism is reflected in judicial practice, where the absence of a QES can render an electronic agreement invalid even when the

parties have effectively performed their obligations (e.g., LLC “SmartLog” vs. IP T.A., 2023) [16].

By contrast, Chinese law demonstrates greater flexibility. Under the Law “On Electronic Signatures,” courts may recognize electronic agreements based on other evidence of consent, such as electronic communications or order confirmations on digital platforms [5, 11]. The implementation of specialized Internet Courts in China further reinforces a practical, adaptive approach to resolving electronic disputes [11, 13]. This flexibility promotes legal certainty for parties engaged in e-commerce while reducing transaction costs and barriers to digital trade.

2. Institutional and procedural support. The establishment of Internet Courts in China (since 2017) has significantly strengthened the institutional framework for adjudicating electronic contract disputes. These courts provide specialized procedures for assessing digital evidence and applying electronic signature standards [11]. In Uzbekistan, similar institutional mechanisms are currently absent, which limits the effectiveness of legal protection in electronic transactions [12]. Introducing specialized mechanisms or dedicated chambers within existing courts could enhance dispute resolution efficiency and increase investor confidence in the Uzbek digital economy.

3. Risk management strategies. Both Uzbekistan and China have developed mechanisms to mitigate the risks associated with electronic agreements, including state-accredited certification centers, secure document storage, and recognition of electronic documents as evidence in courts [4, 5, 12, 16]. However, differences remain in cross-border transaction risk management. Chinese courts have demonstrated more adaptability by considering evidence beyond qualified electronic signatures, which is particularly relevant for international contracts executed through digital platforms [13, 14].

4. Implications for legal harmonization and cross-border trade. As electronic agreements become a dominant mode of commercial exchange in the digital economy, the divergence in legal requirements and institutional support may hinder cross-border trade between Uzbekistan and China. Harmonization of legal standards, including flexible approaches to electronic signatures, recognition of digital evidence, and development of specialized dispute resolution mechanisms, is essential for fostering mutual trust and facilitating international transactions [14, 15]. Comparative analysis indicates that adopting elements of the Chinese model—particularly procedural flexibility and institutional specialization—could enhance the effectiveness of Uzbekistan’s legal framework for electronic agreements.

5. Recommendations for Uzbekistan. Based on the comparative analysis, several measures are proposed to improve Uzbekistan’s regulation of electronic agreements:

Introduce specialized mechanisms for resolving electronic disputes, inspired by Chinese Internet Courts [11, 13].

Expand the range of admissible evidence to confirm electronic agreement

formation, including digital communications and platform-based confirmations [5, 11].

Gradually reduce formalistic requirements for QES in commercial transactions, especially in B2C operations, while maintaining robust authentication and security standards [12, 16].

Promote bilateral cooperation with China to unify legal standards for electronic agreements and reduce cross-border transaction risks [14, 15].

6. Contribution to legal scholarship. The study contributes to the growing body of comparative research on electronic agreements in civil law systems. It demonstrates that while the legal principles governing electronic contracts are broadly similar, practical implementation and institutional mechanisms vary, influencing the effectiveness of risk management and dispute resolution. This analysis provides a foundation for policy recommendations aimed at strengthening Uzbekistan's legal framework and aligning it with international digital economy practices.

Conclusion

This study provides a comprehensive comparative analysis of electronic agreements and risk management systems in the civil law frameworks of Uzbekistan and China. The research demonstrates that while both countries recognize the legal validity of electronic agreements and the equivalence of electronic and paper-based documents, significant differences exist in formal requirements, institutional mechanisms, and practical application.

In Uzbekistan, the mandatory use of a qualified electronic signature (QES) ensures legal certainty but introduces strict formalism, which can render electronic agreements invalid despite actual performance by the parties [4, 16]. Conversely, China has adopted a more flexible approach, allowing courts to recognize electronic agreements based on alternative evidence of consent and operationalizing specialized Internet Courts for digital disputes [5, 11]. This flexibility promotes efficiency, reduces transaction costs, and encourages cross-border digital commerce.

The comparative analysis highlights several critical implications. First, strict formal requirements, while providing legal certainty, may impede the adoption of electronic contracts in rapidly evolving digital markets. Second, institutional mechanisms, such as specialized courts and digital certification systems, play a decisive role in risk mitigation and enforcement of electronic agreements. Third, harmonization of legal standards and procedural flexibility is essential for facilitating international transactions, particularly between countries with differing legal traditions.

Based on these findings, the study proposes targeted recommendations for Uzbekistan: the introduction of specialized mechanisms for electronic dispute resolution, expansion of admissible digital evidence, gradual reduction of formalistic requirements for QES in commercial contexts, and enhanced bilateral cooperation with China to align legal standards for electronic agreements. Implementing these measures would strengthen Uzbekistan's digital economy, enhance investor confidence, and ensure the effective functioning of electronic contract systems while safeguarding public and private interests.

Finally, this research contributes to the broader field of comparative civil law by providing insights into the evolving legal landscape of electronic agreements in emerging digital economies. It underscores the importance of balancing formal legal safeguards with practical flexibility, institutional support, and cross-border harmonization to foster secure and efficient digital commerce. Future studies should focus on the integration of emerging technologies, such as smart contracts and blockchain-based agreements, into the civil law frameworks of Uzbekistan and China, which represents the next frontier in electronic contract law.

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PRACTICAL APPROACHES TO THE CONCEPT AND TYPES OF INVESTMENT DISPUTES

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ANNOTATION

The article examines theoretical and practical approaches to the concept of an investment dispute, its classification, and its significance for creating a favorable investment climate. The analysis covers a wide range of doctrinal interpretations—from the narrow definition of a dispute between a foreign investor and the host state to a broader approach that includes commercial and technical disagreements. Special attention is given to international arbitration practice, including the activities of ICSID, ad hoc arbitration under UNCITRAL rules, WTO/DSB dispute settlement mechanisms, and the International Chamber of Commerce (ICC). The role of bilateral and multilateral investment agreements in shaping the modern understanding of investment disputes is explored, with a comparative analysis of arbitration practice and doctrinal approaches. The study concludes that adapting the narrow approach to investment disputes to the legal system of Uzbekistan is necessary to ensure investor protection while preserving state sovereignty. Additionally, the article analyzes emerging trends in international investment law, including the development of multilateral investment courts, reform of ISDS mechanisms, and efforts to balance investor protection with host-state regulatory autonomy. These insights are particularly relevant for Uzbekistan, which seeks to enhance its investment attractiveness while maintaining a stable legal and institutional framework.

Keywords: investment dispute, ISDS, international arbitration, ICSID, bilateral investment treaties (BITs), international standards, investment security, legal regime, Uzbekistan, foreign practice, narrow and broad approaches.

Introduction

In the context of globalization and increasing competition for foreign investments, the formation of an effective mechanism for resolving investment disputes

has become one of the key factors influencing a country's investment attractiveness. This is particularly relevant for the Republic of Uzbekistan, which pursues a policy of openness and actively attracts foreign direct investment, where the creation of a predictable and transparent legal environment for investors directly affects economic development and socio-economic stability [1].

Investment disputes are characterized by a complex nature, as they involve both the private-law interests of foreign investors and the public-law interests of the host state [2]. This places special demands on legislation and institutional mechanisms aimed at resolving conflicts arising during the implementation of investment projects. In international practice, various approaches to defining investment disputes have been developed, reflected both in doctrinal literature and in arbitration practice (ICSID, BITs, UNCITRAL, WTO/DSB, ICC) [3].

The purpose of this article is to systematize existing theoretical and practical approaches to investment disputes, analyze international arbitration practice, and identify opportunities for adapting international standards to the national legal system of Uzbekistan [4]. Special attention is given to the need to distinguish between investment and commercial disputes, ensure institutional guarantees for foreign investors [6], and maintain the sovereign rights of the state in the implementation of investment projects [5].

Thus, the article aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of an investment dispute as a legal category and to offer practical recommendations for improving investment legislation and arbitration mechanisms in the context of Uzbekistan's dynamically developing economy [7].

Methods

This article employs a combination of theoretical and empirical methods, providing a systematic approach to the analysis of investment disputes and the legal regulation of their resolution. The application of these methods enabled a comprehensive understanding of the nature of investment disputes, their legal characteristics, types, and resolution mechanisms, as well as facilitated the adaptation of international standards to the national legal system.

Results

The analysis of doctrinal and practical approaches to investment disputes highlights a fundamental distinction between the broad and narrow interpretations, each reflecting different perspectives on the legal nature of investment relations [8]. The broad approach encompasses all types of conflicts arising from investment activities,

including commercial disputes between private entities, technical disagreements, and contractual interpretation issues [9]. In contrast, the narrow approach, predominant in international arbitration practice such as ICSID and BITs, focuses specifically on disputes between a foreign investor and the host state, concerning breaches of the state's international obligations toward the investor[10].

The narrow approach provides a more precise framework for distinguishing investment disputes from purely commercial conflicts and supports the application of specialized ISDS mechanisms[11]. Disputes under this approach involve unique participants (sovereign state vs. foreign investor) and specific subject matter, combining private and public interests simultaneously[12]. This unique combination creates a hybrid legal relationship that simultaneously encompasses both private and public interests. On the private side, the foreign investor seeks to protect financial contributions, contractual rights, and expected returns arising from investments. On the public side, the state exercises its sovereign authority to regulate economic activity, enforce laws, and ensure that public interests—including social welfare, national security, and environmental protection—are preserved.

This duality gives rise to a complex legal and procedural landscape. Unlike purely commercial disputes between private entities, investment disputes often require specialized mechanisms, such as ISDS under BITs or ICSID arbitration, to balance the investor's rights with the host state's regulatory powers¹. The hybrid nature also means that remedies must address both financial compensation for the investor and the legitimacy of state actions under international law.

For example, if a state expropriates foreign-owned property, the dispute involves the investor's private property rights as well as the state's exercise of sovereign authority over national resources. Similarly, regulatory changes affecting taxation, environmental standards, or sector-specific licensing can trigger investment disputes because they simultaneously impact private contractual expectations and the public interest objectives of the host state².

The mixed public-private nature of these disputes also affects procedural considerations. Arbitrators must consider the legal framework of the host state, international treaties, customary international law, and principles of fair and equitable treatment. Decisions must strike a careful balance to ensure that investor protections do not unduly limit the state's ability to govern in the public interest, while also guaranteeing that foreign investors have access to impartial and effective remedies³.

In summary, the involvement of a sovereign state and a foreign investor in the

same dispute creates a complex, dual-natured legal context that distinguishes investment disputes from purely commercial conflicts, requiring specialized mechanisms and careful balancing of rights and obligations.

Practical analysis demonstrates that international instruments, including the ICSID Convention (1965), bilateral investment treaties (BITs), and UNCITRAL arbitration rules, establish the legal framework for dispute resolution, although no universally accepted definition of an investment dispute exists[13]. ICSID's flexible but formalized approach considers legal claims directly arising from investments, excluding political or diplomatic elements, while BITs typically define investment disputes as conflicts between an investor and a host state regarding the investor's investments [14]. Case law, such as the *Salini v. Morocco* (2001) test, provides criteria for identifying investments, including duration, risk, contribution, and impact on the host state [15].

Recent trends in international investment law, such as the European Union's development of a Multilateral Investment Court (MIC) and ongoing UNCITRAL reforms on ISDS, demonstrate a global effort to balance investor protection with host-state regulatory autonomy [16]. These initiatives are particularly relevant for Uzbekistan, which aims to attract foreign investment while maintaining legal and institutional stability.

The MIC, proposed by the European Union, seeks to establish a permanent, independent tribunal with clearly defined procedural rules and appellate mechanisms, ensuring both the fair treatment of investors and the preservation of the host state's sovereign right to regulate in the public interest². Similarly, UNCITRAL Working Group III has introduced reforms to enhance the transparency of proceedings, strengthen arbitrator qualifications, provide avenues for appeals, and improve consistency in awards³. Collectively, these efforts reflect a shift toward a more institutionalized, rule-based approach to investment arbitration, which aims to reduce legal uncertainty and enhance predictability for both investors and states.

For Uzbekistan, these international trends are particularly relevant. As the country pursues a policy of openness and actively seeks to attract foreign direct investment, it must ensure that its legal and institutional framework inspires confidence among international investors while retaining sufficient flexibility to implement domestic economic, social, and environmental policies⁴. The adoption of reforms inspired by MIC and UNCITRAL practices can provide a model for Uzbekistan to: establish clear procedural rules for investment dispute resolution that minimize the risk of inconsistent interpretations; strengthen the independence and expertise of arbitration panels to ensure

impartial adjudication; incorporate appellate mechanisms or review procedures to increase predictability and legal certainty; balance investor protections with the host state's regulatory autonomy, thereby reducing the risk of disputes escalating into conflicts over legitimate public policy measures.

By aligning its national legislation and dispute resolution mechanisms with these emerging international standards, Uzbekistan can simultaneously enhance its attractiveness to foreign investors and maintain institutional legitimacy and sovereign control. Moreover, such reforms can provide a framework for handling complex cross-border investments, mitigating risks, and fostering long-term economic stability.

In conclusion, the results indicate that a narrow, state-investor-focused definition of investment disputes, combined with the adaptation of international arbitration standards to Uzbekistan's legal system, offers an effective framework for resolving conflicts, ensuring investment security, and promoting a stable investment climate.

Discussion

The results of this study indicate that the narrow approach to defining investment disputes—focused on conflicts between a foreign investor and the host state—is the most appropriate framework for practical application in Uzbekistan. This approach aligns with international arbitration practice, particularly ICSID and BIT-based dispute resolution mechanisms [17]. Narrowly defined disputes allow for clear differentiation between investment and commercial conflicts, enabling the use of specialized Investor-State Dispute Settlement (ISDS) procedures [18].

International experience demonstrates that successful investment dispute resolution requires not only clear legal definitions but also robust institutional support and procedural guarantees. ICSID's practice shows that formalized rules for jurisdiction and admissibility, combined with flexibility in interpreting "investment," contribute to predictable outcomes and investor confidence [19]. Similarly, the European Union's development of a Multilateral Investment Court (MIC) and UNCITRAL reforms emphasize transparency, impartiality, and appellate mechanisms, providing lessons for Uzbekistan in balancing investor protection with sovereign regulatory authority [20].

Comparative analysis also highlights that post-Soviet countries tend to adopt broader definitions of investment disputes, encompassing conflicts involving joint ventures and domestic partners with foreign capital [21]. While this approach ensures comprehensive coverage, it may complicate institutional procedures and blur the distinction between private and public interests. For Uzbekistan, a calibrated narrow approach—focused on disputes between foreign investors and the state, while

recognizing their mixed public-private nature—is recommended [22].

Based on international practice and the results of this study, the following recommendations are proposed for Uzbekistan:

1. Adopt a clear legal definition of investment disputes in national legislation, aligned with the narrow approach used in ICSID and BITs, emphasizing the state-investor relationship and the protection of investment rights [23].

2. Formalize institutional mechanisms for dispute resolution, including specialized arbitration centers or administrative bodies with expertise in international investment law, to ensure predictable and transparent processes [24].

3. Incorporate procedural safeguards such as transparent rules for the selection of arbitrators, admissibility criteria, and enforcement mechanisms for awards, drawing on UNCITRAL and MIC standards [25].

4. Promote the harmonization of national legislation with international investment agreements, including BITs and multilateral treaties, to enhance investor confidence while maintaining the state's regulatory autonomy [26].

5. Develop guidance and training programs for state officials and legal practitioners on investment dispute resolution, highlighting best practices from ICSID, UNCITRAL, and EU investment law frameworks.

Implementing these measures would strengthen Uzbekistan's investment climate, reduce legal uncertainty, and provide foreign investors with reliable protections while safeguarding public interests. By aligning national practices with international standards, Uzbekistan can achieve a balance between attracting foreign investment and preserving sovereign control over regulatory policy.

By codifying clear rules for investment disputes, including the adoption of narrowly defined mechanisms for investor-state conflicts, Uzbekistan can reduce the likelihood of protracted or contentious legal proceedings and enhance confidence in the enforcement of contractual and treaty obligations.

At the same time, these measures would provide foreign investors with reliable protections, including safeguards against expropriation, discriminatory treatment, or breaches of contractual obligations. Reliable protections are essential not only for attracting capital but also for fostering long-term investment relationships, as investors are more likely to commit resources to projects when they are confident that legal and institutional frameworks will uphold their rights.

Importantly, aligning national practices with international standards—such as ICSID arbitration rules, UNCITRAL reforms, and lessons from the EU Multilateral

Investment Court (MIC)—enables Uzbekistan to balance investor protection with the sovereign right to regulate. This balance ensures that the state can pursue public policy objectives, such as social welfare programs, environmental protection, and economic development initiatives, without being unduly constrained by external investment claims.

Moreover, the adoption of internationally recognized standards can facilitate cross-border investment by providing investors with familiar procedural and substantive safeguards, reducing transaction costs, and fostering stronger institutional trust. Over time, this approach will not only enhance Uzbekistan's competitiveness in the global investment arena but also support sustainable economic growth, integration into international markets, and the establishment of a robust rule-of-law culture in investment governance.

In summary, by implementing these measures, Uzbekistan can create a dual advantage: a secure, attractive environment for foreign investment, and a framework that preserves the state's capacity to act in the public interest. This alignment of national and international norms represents a strategic pathway toward sustainable economic development and a stable, predictable legal regime for both domestic and international stakeholders.

Conclusion

This study has examined both doctrinal and practical approaches to investment disputes, highlighting the distinction between broad and narrow interpretations. The narrow approach, focusing on disputes between a foreign investor and the host state, is shown to be the most effective framework for legal regulation and dispute resolution, as it clearly separates investment conflicts from purely commercial disputes and aligns with international arbitration practice, including ICSID and BIT mechanisms [27].

Practical analysis demonstrates that international instruments and case law, such as the ICSID Convention and the Salini test, provide essential guidance for identifying and resolving investment disputes. Modern trends in investment law, including the development of the Multilateral Investment Court (MIC) and UNCITRAL reforms, emphasize transparency, accountability, and the establishment of appellate mechanisms, offering valuable lessons for Uzbekistan [28].

For Uzbekistan, adopting a narrow definition of investment disputes, combined with the adaptation of international arbitration standards to national legislation, will strengthen the legal framework for foreign investment, enhance institutional trust, and provide reliable protections for investors while safeguarding the sovereignty of the state.

This approach supports the development of a stable and predictable investment climate, which is essential for attracting foreign direct investment and fostering sustainable economic growth [29].

In conclusion, the harmonization of national legislation with international standards, the formalization of institutional dispute resolution mechanisms, and the implementation of procedural safeguards will ensure the effective resolution of investment disputes in Uzbekistan. Such measures will contribute not only to investor confidence but also to the long-term resilience and competitiveness of the national economy in a globally interconnected market.

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UNIFICATION OF CIVIL LAW REGULATION OF TOURIST SERVICES IN THE CONTEXT OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION: PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTS OF LAW ENFORCEMENT

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Abstract

The article examines current trends and challenges in improving the civil legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the context of digital transformation. The focus is placed on the need for systematic unification and harmonization of national civil law norms with international standards, as well as on adapting the legislation to the requirements of the digital civil turnover. Special attention is given to the implementation of universally recognized principles of international law and the role of the Hague Conference on Private International Law in the process of legal convergence. The study highlights the importance of Uzbekistan's participation in international initiatives aimed at developing legal mechanisms for regulating the digital economy, electronic commerce, and cross-border private law relations. It is emphasized that the modernization of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan should take into account both internal economic and legal realities and the country's international obligations, including those arising from its accession to the World Trade Organization.

Keywords:

civil legislation, unification of law, digital civil turnover, private international law, Hague Conference, harmonization, World Trade Organization, legal reform, law enforcement, Republic of Uzbekistan.

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УНИФИКАЦИЯ ГРАЖДАНСКО-ПРАВОВОГО РЕГУЛИРОВАНИЯ ТУРИСТИЧЕСКИХ УСЛУГ В УСЛОВИЯХ ЦИФРОВОЙ ТРАНСФОРМАЦИИ: ПРОБЛЕМЫ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ ПРАВОПРИМЕНЕНИЯ

Аннотация

В статье рассматриваются современные тенденции и проблемы совершенствования гражданского законодательства Республики Узбекистан в условиях цифровой трансформации. Акцент сделан на необходимости системной унификации и гармонизации национальных гражданско-правовых норм с международными стандартами, а также адаптации законодательства к требованиям цифрового гражданского оборота. Особое внимание уделено вопросам имплементации общепризнанных принципов международного права и роли Гаагской конференции по международному частному праву в процессе сближения правовых систем. Отмечается значимость участия Узбекистана в международных инициативах, направленных на развитие правовых механизмов регулирования цифровой экономики, электронной коммерции и трансграничных частноправовых отношений. Подчеркивается, что обновление Гражданского кодекса Республики Узбекистан должно учитывать как внутренние экономико-правовые реалии, так и международные обязательства страны, в том числе в контексте присоединения к Всемирной торговой организации.

Ключевые слова: гражданское законодательство, унификация права, цифровой гражданский оборот, международное частное право, Гаагская конференция, гармонизация, Всемирная торговая организация, правовая реформа, правоприменение, Республика Узбекистан.

Research Relevance

At present, active legislative work is being undertaken to improve the civil legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, taking into account the objective needs of the digital civil turnover. The international and constitutional-legal characterization of the application of universally recognized principles of international law and the norms of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan provides an opportunity for a comprehensive and in-depth analysis of all institutions of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan (CC RUz) and for the development of well-grounded, problem-oriented conclusions and proposals for its modernization in light of new legislative objectives in this field.

According to Article 33 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, “The State shall create conditions for ensuring access to the global information network, the Internet.” In accordance with the Presidential Resolution of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 5, 2019, No. R-5464 “On Measures to Improve the Civil Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan,”[1] the current version of the Civil Code does not fully meet the requirements of rapidly evolving economic relations within the country, nor does it correspond to international civil law standards. In particular:

First, the Civil Code retains outdated legal institutions and organizational-legal forms of legal entities that no longer exist in the legal systems of developed market economies.

Second, the Code lacks classical civil law institutions such as “commercial risk,” “equality of business entities,” “fair compensation,” and “refusal to perform contractual obligations.”

Third, it does not regulate several forms of civil contracts and legal relations that are in high demand in the modern market environment, including public-private partnership agreements, dealership contracts, shared construction, cluster production, electronic commerce, cryptocurrency circulation, land privatization, and others.

Fourth, the excessive number of blanket and reference norms (approximately 80) prevents the Code from functioning as a self-executing legal act and diminishes its authority in the regulation of civil relations.

Fifth, the Civil Code provides for an unjustifiably large number of organizational-legal forms of legal entities that are similar in nature and represent a hybrid of norms borrowed from other legal forms (for example, private enterprises and unitary enterprises, which cannot attract investment since the law does not provide for the participation of additional members in their structure).

Sixth, the Code contains public law provisions that do not belong to civil law institutions and includes an excessive number of restrictions concerning private property and contractual relations.

Seventh, the Civil Code is almost entirely devoid of provisions governing the use of information and communication technologies (ICT) in civil law relations.

This analysis underscores the necessity for systemic reform and digital modernization of the civil legislation of Uzbekistan, ensuring its harmonization with international legal standards and the realities of the digital economy.

International Private Law Benchmarks for the Improvement of Civil Legislation

The Preamble of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan declares that “this Constitution is adopted on the basis of universally recognized principles and norms of international law.” According to Article 15 of the Constitution, the Republic of Uzbekistan recognizes the unconditional supremacy of the Constitution and laws. The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan possesses the highest legal force, has direct effect, and forms the foundation of a unified legal system throughout the entire territory of the country.

International treaties of the Republic of Uzbekistan, together with universally recognized principles and norms of international law, constitute an integral part of the national legal system. Where an international treaty of the Republic of Uzbekistan establishes rules differing from those provided by domestic law, the rules of the international treaty shall prevail.

In accordance with the Presidential Decree “On Measures to Improve the Civil Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan,” one of the main priority directions in the further modernization of civil legislation is the systematization and unification of civil law norms, ensuring their harmonization with best foreign practices, as well as the implementation of advanced international standards in this field.

In the process of convergence of private international law norms among various states, the terms “unification,” “uniformization,” and “harmonization” are widely used. These concepts reflect the global legal trend toward creating consistent and coherent civil law frameworks, enabling effective cross-border cooperation, legal predictability, and the integration of national systems into the evolving international legal order [2]. International organizations play an important role in the process of unifying international legal acts [3]. The oldest organization in the field of unification of private international law is the Hague Conference on Private International Law (began its work in 1893). The members of this organization include more than 60 countries, including Uzbekistan. As is known, on March 4, 2020, Uzbekistan joined the Hague Conference on Private International Law. Uzbekistan's membership in the Hague Conference will ensure the country's participation in the procedure of unifying the norms of international family and private law, further development of the legal system taking into account world standards, and enhancing the effectiveness of protecting the rights and interests of the country's citizens abroad [4].

Therefore, on September 6-8, 2000, the UN Millennium Declaration was adopted and global development priorities were defined. This document consists of 17 goals and 169 targets, and also defines tasks to increase production in economic sectors through accelerating technical modernization, value-added industries, and information and communication technologies [5].

As is known, the agreement on information technology was adopted at the first ministerial conference of WTO member states (Singapore, 1996) [6]. It defines the principles of international trade in information technologies, providing for the gradual reduction of customs tariffs on information technology products and their elimination (zero tariffs) starting from January 1, 2000. Currently, the World Trade Organization (WTO) is discussing the expansion of the range of goods classified as information technology products. Approximately 40 countries are parties to this Agreement; however, the tariff preferences established under it also extend to other countries.

According to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-214 of December 25, 2023, a strategic task has been set to adapt national legislation and law enforcement practices to the rules, norms, and agreements of the WTO, to complete market access negotiations with at least ten foreign countries annually, and to systematically conduct accession negotiations aimed at the effective completion of Uzbekistan's WTO membership process and entry into the markets of WTO member states.

By its civil-law nature, the Agreement on Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights (TRIPS Agreement) is an international treaty that forms part of the package of documents establishing the World Trade Organization (WTO). The Agreement sets minimum standards for the recognition and protection of key objects of intellectual property rights. It was adopted during the Uruguay Round of the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (GATT) in 1994.

The TRIPS Agreement enables the use of highly effective dispute resolution mechanisms available within the WTO framework, as applied to intellectual property. These mechanisms include the possibility of retaliatory measures. For example, if a violation of the copyright of an author from one country occurs in another, the injured country—having gone through the WTO dispute settlement procedures—may impose higher tariffs on the import of certain goods from the offending country.

Primarily, the TRIPS Agreement requires member states to implement all essential provisions of the Berne Convention for the Protection of Literary and Artistic Works, except for those concerning moral rights. In addition, TRIPS introduces a number of new provisions related to the international protection of copyright. The absence of moral rights in the Agreement is justified, as its main focus is on regulating the trade-related aspects of intellectual property. The TRIPS Agreement thus incorporates several fundamental elements that complement the provisions of the Berne Convention [7]. In accordance with these provisions, copyright protection extends to computer programs, the term of protection is lengthened, and international trade in computer programs and other intellectual property objects is restricted with countries that lack the capacity to ensure adequate copyright protection. The Agreement also establishes the requirement for member states to adopt various administrative mechanisms for the protection of copyright. [8].

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 15, 2024, No. 908, «On Amendments and Additions to Certain Legislative Acts of the Republic of Uzbekistan Aimed at Bringing the National Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan into Conformity with the Agreements of the World Trade Organization,» represents one of the key measures to accelerate the process of Uzbekistan’s accession to the World Trade Organization (WTO) [9]». One of the primary conditions for accession to the WTO is the harmonization of national legislation with the standards and provisions set forth in the WTO agreements.

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Trademarks and Appellations of Origin” has been amended and supplemented to establish a precise procedure for the use of industrial property objects without the consent of the right holder, taking into account the interests of intellectual property owners, and to eliminate the statute of limitations for the protection of rights in cases of unfair use of trademarks by other parties following registration. In accordance with the requirements of the WTO Agreements, amendments have also been introduced to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On

Medicines and Pharmaceutical Activities”, providing for the introduction of procedures to protect the rights of data owners obtained prior to and as a result of clinical trials within the framework of pharmaceutical activities.

Moreover, this Law introduces amendments to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On State Duties”, aimed at unifying patent fees as well as state duties charged for the registration of enterprises with foreign investment and other business entities.

Amendments to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Advertising” are directed toward ensuring equal conditions for domestic and foreign manufacturers.

This Law will contribute to the protection of the rights of industrial property owners, the unification of patent and registration fees, and the harmonization of national legislation with the rules and standards of the World Trade Organization.

Most importantly, international private law instruments serve as a guideline for the unification and systematization of national legislation. Therefore, in the ongoing process of reforming the Civil Code of Uzbekistan, it is essential to take into account the fundamental legal principles and standards established by these international and regional organizations in the field of unification of international private law and the regulation of civil-law relations.[10] In this regard, in the process of reforming the Civil Code of Uzbekistan, it is necessary to take into account the fundamental legal principles and norms of the aforementioned international and regional organizations in the field of unification of international private law regulation of civil law relations.

Research Results in the Context of the Reform and Improvement of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The exercise of civil-law subjective digital rights refers to the actions of subjects of civil-law relations, carried out in accordance with constitutional and legislative norms through the use of information and communication technologies within the digital environment.

The protection of subjective civil digital rights implies a set of legal and technological protection mechanisms employed by both non-judicial (extrajudicial) and judicial entities—including digital courts, the technology of artificial judicial intelligence (AI), and actors of online digital dispute resolution—aimed at preventing, suppressing, restoring, or compensating for the violation of subjective civil digital rights in the digital sphere.

In this civilistic context, the system of civil-law and information-communication technological instruments designed to protect subjective digital rights constitutes a mechanism of smart regulation. This mechanism seeks to ensure the effective realization of the protective function of law within the Internet environment, promoting good faith and reasonableness in the protection of the rights and interests of participants in the digital civil turnover.

Based on this, and taking into account the experience of foreign countries, it is

necessary to supplement the provisions of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan with the following content:

It is proposed to amend Article 111 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan to read as follows:

Article 111. Protection of the Rights of Entrepreneurs and Consumers

Entrepreneurship is defined as the independent and initiative-based activity of individuals and legal entities aimed at generating net income through the use of property, production, sale of goods, performance of work, or provision of services, carried out on the basis of the right of private ownership (private entrepreneurship) or on the right of economic management or operational administration of a state enterprise (state entrepreneurship). Entrepreneurial activity is conducted on behalf of, at the risk of, and under the property liability of the entrepreneur.

The State guarantees the freedom of entrepreneurial activity and ensures its protection and support.

The rights of entrepreneurs engaged in activities not prohibited by law are protected through the following means:

1. The ability to carry out entrepreneurial activity without obtaining any permits or submitting notifications, except for those permits and notifications expressly required by legislation;

2. The establishment of a simplified, single-window registration procedure for all types of entrepreneurial activity across all sectors of the economy in one registering authority;

3. The limitation, by legislative acts, of inspections of entrepreneurial activities conducted by state authorities;

4. The compulsory termination of entrepreneurial activity only by court decision and only on grounds established by legislative acts;

5. The establishment, by legislative acts, of lists of types of work, goods, and services that are prohibited for private entrepreneurship, or that are restricted for export or import;

6. The imposition of property liability, as established by law, on state bodies, officials, as well as other persons and organizations, for unlawful interference with entrepreneurial activity;

7. The prohibition for executive, control, and supervisory bodies from entering into contractual relations with business entities regarding the performance of duties that fall within the functions of these bodies;

8. Other means provided for by law.

The establishment of a permitting or notification-based procedure shall be determined by legislation, depending on the level of risk associated with the activity or operation, in order to protect human life and health, the environment, property, national security, and public order.

A permitting procedure shall be established in cases where the requirements set forth by the laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan regarding products, as well as the requirements for mandatory conformity certification, are insufficient to achieve the objectives of state regulation.

Commercial (entrepreneurial) secrecy is protected by law. The procedure for determining information constituting a commercial secret, the means of its protection, and the list of information that shall not be considered a commercial secret are established by legislation.

The protection of consumer rights shall be ensured by the means provided for in this Code or other legislative acts. Each consumer shall have, in particular, the right to:

- freely conclude contracts for the purchase of goods, and the use of works and services;

- proper quality and safety of goods (works, services);
- complete and reliable information about goods (works, services);
- join public consumer organizations.

It is proposed to amend Article 112 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan to read as follows:

Article 112. Prohibition of the Abuse of Entrepreneurial Freedom

Monopolistic and any other activities aimed at restricting or eliminating lawful competition, obtaining unjustified advantages, or infringing upon the rights and legitimate interests of consumers shall not be permitted.

Except in cases provided for by legislative acts, entrepreneurs shall not use civil rights for the purpose of restricting competition, including:

Abuse of a dominant position in the market by entrepreneurs, in particular by limiting or ceasing production, or by withdrawing goods from circulation in order to create shortages or raise prices;

Conclusion and performance of agreements by persons engaged in similar entrepreneurial activities concerning prices, market division, elimination of other entrepreneurs, or other conditions that substantially restrict competition;

Engaging in unfair actions that infringe upon the legitimate interests of another person engaged in similar entrepreneurial activity or consumers (unfair competition), in particular by misleading consumers as to the manufacturer, purpose, method and place of manufacture, quality, or other characteristics of another entrepreneur's goods; by making incorrect comparisons of goods in advertising or other information; by copying the external design of another's goods; and by other means.

Measures to combat unfair competition shall be established by legislative acts.

3. It is proposed to amend Article 24 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan to read as follows:

Article 24. Place of Residence of a Citizen Registered in the Digital Register as an Entrepreneur or Engaged in Activities Using Digital Platforms

A citizen shall have the right to engage in such activities at their place of residence or through the use of digital platforms from the moment of registration in the state digital register as an individual entrepreneur.

The provisions of this Code shall apply to the entrepreneurial activities of citizens conducted without the establishment of a legal entity, either at their place of residence (legal address) or through the use of digital platforms, unless otherwise provided by law or arises from the nature of legal relations.

A citizen who violates the requirements of the first part of this Article by engaging in entrepreneurial activity without forming a legal entity, whether on their own land or through the use of digital platforms, shall not have the right to claim that they are not an entrepreneur in electronic transactions or smart contracts. The court may apply the provisions of this Code relating to obligations connected with the conduct of entrepreneurial activity on the land of their residence or through digital platforms to such transactions.

Unless otherwise provided by law, the provisions of this Code shall apply to the entrepreneurial activities of citizens carried out using digital platforms.

4. Digitalization will give a powerful impetus to the development of electronic contractual transactions [11]. In the context of the digital transformation of civil transactions, the social and official role of contracts is increasing. Digital integration unites the legislation of countries with different legal systems [12] Therefore, the integration of the Civil Code norms with those of the European Union and the Eurasian legal family is considered an objective process. Especially in the economy, the development of traditional approaches to optimizing the "uniform rules of the game" is the only reasonable way to forecast the development of the Civil Code. In our country, there is a tendency to incorporate certain elements of European contract law into the draft Civil Code. Considering the European Civil Code and the trends in the codification of European private law, harmonization with the Civil Code norms is required in the Republic of Uzbekistan [13]. One of the important problems from a systemic perspective in the current Civil Code is the lack of legal regulation of electronic transactions as an integral part of the law of obligations. [14] The development of information technologies requires special and detailed legal regulation of electronic transactions in the Civil Code, with the following important components: 1. identification of the person (electronic signature, etc.), 2. recording of the transaction (databases, storage media, etc.), 3. reproduction of the transaction (objective expression). Such practices exist in many developed countries of the Romano-Germanic legal system.

In addition, the Civil Code should establish norms stating that if a contract is concluded in two or more languages, which are considered equally authentic, it is presumed that the words and phrases used in each text have the same meaning. If the words and phrases in each text contradict each other, their interpretation should be

carried out in accordance with the relevant articles, the nature and purpose of the contract, as well as the principle of good faith, etc. Similar norms are contained in Article 466 of the Civil Code of the People's Republic of China.

According to the Concept for Improving Civil Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 5, 2019, No. P-5464, measures have been defined for the effective regulation of the use of information and communication technologies in contractual relations [15].

5. Depending on the conditions for implementing projects in a given country, various definitions and classifications of public-private partnership (PPP) forms have been adopted. An analysis of these definitions and forms has shown that a PPP is a mutually beneficial and long-term cooperation between the public and private sectors, which ensures the provision of public services.

The implementation of a PPP is carried out on the basis of the shared interests of the public and private sectors, formalized through a long-term contract that provides for the division of responsibilities and risks among the partnership participants. In international practice, various forms of partnership are used, including concessions, supply contracts (performance of work), leases, production-sharing agreements, and joint ventures [16]. According to the Concept for the Improvement of Civil Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 5, 2019, No. P-5464, one of the gaps in the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan is the public-private partnership (PPP) agreement.

In different countries, their own specific legal traditions for structuring cooperation between the public and private sectors have developed and continue to evolve, aimed at addressing the objectives of socio-economic policy. The specific legal mechanisms that allow for the most effective use of PPPs may vary depending on national legal systems and other particularities.

The implementation of PPP agreements in the Republic of Uzbekistan, in our view, is possible on the basis of existing legislation, but with certain particularities taken into account. When budgetary funds are involved in a PPP, it becomes necessary to conclude the agreement exclusively using a competitive procedure, i.e., practically by analogy with public procurement and concessions.

Contracts for the use of state or municipal assets, which constitute so-called public-law property of the state and other public-law entities, are considered, in foreign countries, not civil but public in Germany or administrative in France.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the definition and content of the concept of a public-private partnership may reasonably incorporate elements of civil-law contracts involving the state, as well as other forms of interaction between public and private partners.

In this civil-law framework, it should be noted that a socially oriented model can be equated with the concept of a social state, which, in turn, is directly related to social partnership.

6. The specifics of conducting Islamic insurance, the formation, accounting, use, and distribution of the Islamic insurance fund, the legal status of insurers providing Islamic insurance, and the conditions of their activities are determined in accordance with this Code and the legislative acts of the Republic of Kazakhstan on insurance and insurance activities. Chapter 34-1 of the Civil Code of Kyrgyzstan is dedicated to «Transactions and Contracts in accordance with Islamic Financing Principles [17]».

7. At the same time, it should be noted that the legal relations arising in the organization of social partnership indicate that a partnership agreement has a complex and multifaceted nature. For this reason, it may contain elements of other contracts provided for by law, as well as terms of contracts not explicitly regulated by legislation. Practically, such an agreement cannot consist of a single document adopted at one time; it includes a significant number of documents (appendices, protocols, supplementary agreements, etc.) signed progressively during the execution of the agreement.

Due to the special nature of a social partnership agreement, it is recommended for the legal formalization of the partnership to:

1. Develop a detailed prospective cooperation plan that would serve as the conceptual basis for contractual relations;

2. Coordinate the plan with interested organizations, local self-government bodies, and representatives of civil society;

3. Draft a general framework agreement and separate supplementary agreements in accordance with the accepted legal practice for structuring contracts;

4. Include in the framework agreement references to existing and potential future supplementary agreements and other contractual documents;

5. Sign the general framework social partnership agreement, incorporating the main provisions of the cooperation plan in legal terms, i.e., translating planned activities into the rights and obligations of the parties with specification of the conditions, procedures, and deadlines for their fulfillment.[18] (In a separate article, the Civil Code should be supplemented with the following provisions: Social Partnership Agreement. The subjects of social partnership may enter into agreements and contracts, as well as develop and implement joint projects and plans. Agreements constitute the mutual assumption of obligations by the parties, within which the parties determine the goals and objectives, directions of joint activities, and indicate the forms of implementing social partnership. Contracts may provide for the performance of work or the provision of services, as well as the implementation of socially and publicly significant projects with material, including financial, support from a social partnership subject. Joint

projects and plans define a set of measures aimed at implementing agreements and contracts, socio-economic development programs, addressing humanitarian issues, and protecting the rights, freedoms, and lawful interests of various segments of the population. This provision is contained in Article 10 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Social Partnership” dated September 25, 2014, No. ZRU-376.)

8. Based on this argument, the draft Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan was supplemented with Article 453: Smart Contract. A smart contract is defined as a contract in which at least one of the parties is not a human, whose creation and execution are fully automated, based on pre-designed software and algorithms that evaluate, using artificial intelligence, actions and intellectual property rights sufficient for the author to be considered as having achieved their objectives, and which create intellectual property rights alongside contractual relationships with its creator, representing an electronic contract. [19]

As we see it, this definition does not fully capture the nature of a smart contract. In this regard, it is necessary to remove Article 453 from the draft Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. While this provision meets the current requirements of digital civil circulation, its inclusion in the Civil Code at this stage is premature.

It should be particularly noted that Part 2 of Article 117, which establishes the written form of a transaction in the discussed draft, also provides an additional basis for recognizing a digital form of such an unusual and previously unknown civil-law contract.

If necessary, in the further digitalization of civil circulation, a separate chapter can be introduced dedicated to the new constructs of smart contracts as an important element of contractual obligations in the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Thus, it can be concluded that the unification of international private and comparative legal regulation of civil relations in the process of reforming the Civil Code of Uzbekistan will make it possible to more effectively and intelligently regulate legal relations in the context of digital civil circulation.

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organizations make a significant contribution to the process of unifying international trade legislation in the online environment. In the context of Uzbekistan's cooperation with the World Trade Organization, one of the most pressing issues is the civil-law protection of the rights and legitimate interests of business entities operating in the digital economy.

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The declaration emphasizes the “key role of trade in information technology products in the development of information industries and in the dynamic expansion of the global economy.” Since 1997, an official committee under the WTO has monitored the implementation and compliance of the Declaration. The primary objective of the agreement is the reduction of all taxes and tariffs on information technology products by the signatory parties to zero. The agreement was expanded at the WTO Ministerial Conference in Nairobi in 2015. https://translated.turbopages.org/proxy_u/en-ru.ru.ef8bc6ab-665ac3ea-88e5e259-74722d776562/https/en.

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18. Appendix 1 to Decree No. 8 of the Republic of Belarus dated December 21, 2017, “On the Development of the Digital Economy” defines a smart contract as a program code intended to operate in a transaction block registry (blockchain) or another distributed information system for the purpose of automated execution and/or performance of transactions or the undertaking of other legally significant actions.

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Conclusion and Implementation of Foreign Trade Contracts within the Framework of WTO Accession

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***Annotation:** The article examines the impact of Uzbekistan’s accession to the World Trade Organization (WTO) on the conclusion and execution of foreign trade contracts. It highlights the need for comprehensive legal reforms to harmonize domestic practices with international standards, enhance transparency, and ensure legal predictability in trade transactions. A central focus is the concept of the “integrated contract,” which extends traditional contract obligations to include ESG (Environmental, Social, Governance) standards, ethical provisions, and sustainable development principles, reflecting contemporary challenges such as digitalization and globalization.*

The study analyzes the influence of WTO principles—including Most-Favored-Nation treatment, national treatment, and transparency—on contractual practices and emphasizes the importance of compliance with international trade norms, digital trade regulations, and standard contract practices like Incoterms and the Vienna Convention. It also explores the systemic challenges within the WTO, including the suspension of the Appellate Body, trade conflicts, protectionist policies, and the increasing role of plurilateral and preferential trade agreements.

The article concludes that Uzbekistan’s WTO accession requires a flexible, multi-level strategy combining multilateral, regional, and bilateral cooperation, and stresses that reforms must be effectively implemented to create stable, non-discriminatory conditions for all trading partners. The integrated contract approach is presented as a practical tool to enhance predictability, trust, and long-term cooperation in international trade.

Key words: *WTO accession, Integrated contract, ESG standards (Environmental, Social, Governance), Preferential trade agreements (PTAs), Contract execution, Sustainable development, Trade compliance, Most-Favored-Nation principle, Non-discrimination, Global trade integration*

The conclusion and execution of foreign trade contracts is a key element in the international trade system. For Uzbekistan, which is in the process of joining the WTO, reforming the legal framework of foreign economic activity is a necessary condition for successful integration into the global trading system. WTO membership entails commitments to ensure transparency, a non-discriminatory approach, and legal certainty in foreign trade, which inevitably affects both the form and content of foreign trade contracts.

In studying the essence of foreign trade contracts, it is important to highlight the legal-scientific concept of the “**integrated contract.**”

The **integrated contract** concept is a modern scientific and practical approach that aims to expand the content of international and foreign trade agreements. Unlike classical contracts, which regulate only legal obligations (what to buy, when to deliver, how to pay), an integrated contract includes additional non-financial and ethical provisions, which are especially important in the context of globalization, digitalization, and sustainable development.

This approach allows parties to embed social responsibility, environmental standards, and compliance with international norms directly into contracts, thereby increasing predictability, trust, and long-term cooperation between trading partners³².

An **integrated contract** is an agreement that combines legal obligations (delivery, price, payment, liability) with ESG standards (Environmental, Social, Governance), ethical and anti-corruption provisions, and sustainable development principles³³ (for example, support for local production, respect for human rights, transparency), as well as innovative elements (digitalization, smart contracts, electronic registries).

This concept is governed on the basis of ESG standards. ESG standards constitute an international system for evaluating a company’s performance not only by financial results but also by environmental, social, and governance criteria. They are becoming key in international trade, investment, corporate reporting, and legislation³⁴.

The first standard is environmental standards, which indicate how carefully a company treats nature, reduces harmful impact, and contributes to environmental

³² Poncibò, C. (2021). The Digitalization of Contracts in International Trade and Finance: Comparative Law Perspectives on Smart Contracts. *Digitalization and Firm Performance*.

³³ Aaken, A. (2009). International Investment Law between Commitment and Flexibility: A Contract Theory Analysis. *Journal of International Economic Law*, 12, 507-538.

³⁴ Мажорина, М. (2022). Принципы ESG в международном бизнесе и устойчивые контракты. Актуальные проблемы российского права.

protection. For example, a company may switch to solar panels and recyclable packaging, thereby lowering its carbon footprint, obtaining a “green” certificate, and ultimately increasing its chances of exporting to the EU³⁵.

The second, social standard, evaluates how a company interacts with people — its employees, local communities, and customers. This includes working conditions, absence of workplace discrimination, prohibition of child labor, and more. For example, a factory in Uzbekistan implements equal rights policies for women, conducts employee training, and provides insurance; as a result, it secures favorable contracts in European and Japanese markets³⁶.

The third standard — corporate governance — evaluates how a company is managed, including whether there is a transparency system, adherence to ethical norms, and how decisions and risks are controlled. Key aspects include the independence and professionalism of the board of directors, anti-corruption measures, transparency of financial reporting, ethical codes, and more. For example, a company signs an anti-corruption agreement, implements independent audits, publishes an annual ESG report, and becomes attractive to foreign investors and trading partners.

An **integrated contract** represents a new stage in the development of contractual relationships, especially in international trade. It addresses contemporary challenges: climate, social, and digital issues. For Uzbekistan, implementing this model is particularly relevant for exports to the EU, Korea, Japan, and other ESG-oriented markets, for modernizing the legal framework in preparation for WTO accession, and for supporting the reputation of national producers.

According to WTO terminology, the international trade system is structured across **three levels of cooperation**, each characterized by specific legal features and obligations: **bilateral, plurilateral, and multilateral trade**. Although the rules governing trade under these forms may vary, the WTO accession process for each involves **detailed negotiations** aimed at agreeing on mutual concessions and membership conditions.

It should be noted that during bilateral and plurilateral agreement negotiations, the participants are specific interested countries. In contrast, WTO negotiations aim to

³⁵ Kimbrough, M., Wang, X., Wei, S., & Zhang, J. (2022). Does Voluntary ESG Reporting Resolve Disagreement among ESG Rating Agencies?. *European Accounting Review*, 33, 15 - 47.

³⁶ Lee, B. (2024). ESG and Emotional Non-conformity of Goods in Contracts for International Sale of Goods. *Journal of Korea Trade*.

determine the terms of trade with all member states of the organization. Over the past decade, the multilateral regulatory system has faced a significant challenge: the unilateral imposition of economic sanctions against Russia and other states. The introduction of countermeasures has exacerbated the situation, sparking intense debates over the legality and justification of such restrictions from the perspective of national security³⁷. In the context of rising political tensions, the intensification of regional trends, the strengthening of protectionist measures, and the transformation of the global trade and economic architecture, the WTO is facing a deep systemic crisis. This crisis significantly hampers the organization's functioning and limits member countries' ability to effectively utilize its potential.

The need for WTO reforms has been recognized by the majority of its members. At the same time, the actions and statements of the United States have acted as a catalyst for initiating this process. Among WTO members, the following significant challenges in the organization's work are observed:

Insufficient efficiency and transparency of the dispute settlement system. The situation has worsened due to the suspension of the Appellate Body's activities as a result of the U.S. blockade;

Limited scope of WTO rules. Issues not fully covered by WTO norms include the regulation of state-owned enterprises and electronic commerce;

Incomplete compliance with obligations by individual member states.

These problems require close attention and swift resolution to ensure the effective functioning of the WTO in the interest of all its members.

The inability of WTO members to reach agreements on the Doha Round and new issues has led to the development of plurilateral initiatives, i.e., agreements among subgroups of WTO members. Indeed, the suspension of the WTO Appellate Body has caused a serious disruption of the dispute resolution mechanism within this international organization. According to WTO data, more than 70% of trade disputes between countries are resolved using the appeals procedure.

Due to the lack of a fully functioning WTO Appellate Body, the European Union concluded an agreement to establish a temporary appellate mechanism with sixteen WTO members, including China, Canada, and Australia. This multilateral agreement provided for the application of the standard WTO appellate rules and was open for

³⁷ Statistics on anti-dumping [Электронный ресурс] // WTO.

accession by all interested WTO members until the permanent Appellate Body resumes its operations³⁸.

Events in international trade have been exacerbated by trade conflicts initiated by the United States. In 2018, the U.S. administration increased import tariffs on steel and aluminum by 25 and 10 percentage points, respectively.

In response to these measures, the largest steel and aluminum producers and exporters, including Russia, implemented compensatory and protective measures and requested consultations with the U.S. side.

The U.S.–China trade war also involved the issue of forced technology transfer. Due to the unprecedented scale of the trade conflict, the parties reached a “Phase One” agreement by early 2020, aimed at resolving the disputes. This agreement played a significant role in de-escalating the trade conflict between the two countries, leading to the removal of a number of mutual tariff restrictions. China undertook several commitments, most of which were either already planned under its domestic policies (e.g., in the financial services sector) or corresponded to China’s WTO obligations regarding technology transfer.

China’s specific commitments regarding intellectual property, made under U.S. pressure, are likely to benefit all participants in the multilateral trading system. However, some of China’s commitments—particularly the promise to increase purchases of American goods—raise doubts about their compliance with WTO rules. EU Trade Commissioner Phil Hogan has already expressed concerns about possible violations of these rules.

The protectionist policy actively pursued by U.S. President Donald Trump led to large-scale trade and economic conflicts. This phenomenon indicates the limits of further globalization. Unlike previous cases, when protectionism was used to support the development of new industries, today it has acquired a pronounced political character. The main goal of this policy has become the geopolitical and geoeconomic containment of China, with which the U.S. competes for global leadership.

Given that the fundamental causes of modern trade conflicts remain active, it can be concluded that tensions in the international trade and economic sphere will persist in the near future, at least until significant structural and technological transformations in the global economy are completed.

³⁸ Исаченко, Т. М. Система разрешения споров ВТО : преодоление кризиса и необходимость реформ / Т. М. Исаченко, О. В. Савельев // *Международные процессы*. – 2019. – Т. 17, № 4. – С. 22-35.

Impact of WTO norms on the conclusion of foreign trade contracts. The fundamental principles of the WTO, such as the Most-Favored-Nation treatment, national treatment, and the principle of transparency, require Uzbekistan to create a legal environment that facilitates the conclusion of foreign trade agreements on equal terms with all member countries. This means that the legal regulation of such contracts must be non-discriminatory, predictable, and in accordance with international trade standards.

For a long time, the WTO was considered the dominant multilateral mechanism for regulating international trade. However, due to the slowdown in the development of new trade rules, since the 2000s countries have increasingly resorted to concluding preferential trade agreements (PTAs). This study is devoted to the timely and increasingly important topic of digital trade. Within its framework, we analyze the relationship between countries' participation in the WTO and their approaches to developing digital trade rules within the framework of PTAs³⁹.

A study based on newly collected data from nearly 350 free trade agreements concluded since 2000 revealed a correlation between countries' participation in WTO initiatives on digital trade and the content of their bilateral trade agreements. Specifically, it was found that countries actively involved in the WTO's E-commerce Work Programme discussions are more likely to include progressive and ambitious digital trade provisions in their free trade agreements. Moreover, the study shows that WTO members of the Plurilateral Agreement on Information Technology (ITA) generally tend to undertake broader commitments in the field of digital trade. This work also contributes to a deeper understanding of the relationship between multilateral trade regimes and their regional and bilateral counterparts, analyzing the dynamics of increasing complexity in these regimes.

There is an extensive body of literature dedicated to analyzing the interaction between the WTO and PTAs as platforms for negotiations and trade dispute resolution. Nevertheless, systematic research on the influence of WTO law on the structure of PTAs remains insufficiently explored, especially in the context of stagnation in multilateral WTO negotiations. Specific thematic studies (Arnold and Rittberger, 2006) have identified the influence of WTO law and practice on regional trade agreements. The first comprehensive study by Allee (2017), focused on assessing the "presence" of

³⁹ Manfred Elsig and S. Klotz. "Digital Trade Rules in Preferential Trade Agreements: Is There a WTO Impact?." *Global Policy*, 12 (2020): 25-36.

the WTO in free trade agreements, analyzed textual duplications and references to WTO articles. The authors found both a significant amount of copied WTO provisions and extensive use of references to WTO articles in free trade agreements.

Overall, the authors emphasize the significant presence of WTO commitments and how the legal norms of PTAs reinforce and support WTO legal norms. This work suggests that the competition between WTO obligations and PTA provisions is less conflictual than is often asserted⁴⁰. The authors also found that, in particular, established areas of trade regulation (for example, trade remedies) are more likely to be imported from WTO law than new areas (such as procurement or investment), and that major trading powers (those that also have the ability to deviate from WTO obligations) import WTO law commitments at a much higher than average rate. Another recent study, focused on the development of parent agreements, examines how participation and experience in WTO dispute settlement influence negotiations over parent agreements and their outcomes. Professors Wüthrich and Elsig argue that PTA partners learn lessons from participation in WTO dispute settlement procedures⁴¹.

It should be noted that the conclusion of foreign trade contracts must take into account international customs and standard terms applied in global practice, such as Incoterms, the United Nations Convention on Contracts for the International Sale of Goods (Vienna Convention, 1980), UNCITRAL provisions, and other international instruments.

When concluding foreign trade contracts in the context of Uzbekistan's accession to the WTO, the following key points must be considered:

The contract must clearly regulate all aspects of the transaction, including price, quantity, delivery terms, responsibilities of the parties, dispute resolution, and so on. It is important that the terms comply with international standards, taking into account the obligations undertaken by Uzbekistan under the WTO. Currently, this is regulated by the Laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan (2000) "On Foreign Economic Activity" and the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers dated 14.05.2020 No. 283 "On Measures for the Further Improvement of Monitoring Foreign Trade Operations in the Republic of Uzbekistan";

⁴⁰ R. Baldwin. "The World Trade Organization and the Future of Multilateralism." *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 30 (2016): 95-116.

⁴¹ R. Koopman, John Hancock, R. Piermartini and E. Bekkers. "The Value of the WTO." *Journal of Policy Modeling*, 42 (2020): 829-849.

It is important to specify in advance the jurisdiction in which potential disputes will be resolved and which international arbitration mechanisms will be used;

Despite the reduction of trade barriers, rules regarding tariffs and quotas on certain goods should be carefully monitored to avoid unnecessary costs.

The execution of foreign trade contracts under the new conditions of WTO accession also becomes more structured and organized. This includes:

Customs procedures. After joining the WTO, customs procedures and standards become more transparent and harmonized with international practice, and WTO rules will be implemented in the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan;

Quality control of goods. The WTO actively regulates product quality standards, which improves trust between countries and reduces the number of disputes over product quality. National standards will change significantly;

Logistics and transportation. Thanks to the harmonization of international standards and the simplification of transactions with other countries, the process of delivering goods and executing contracts becomes more transparent and efficient.

Studying scientific approaches to the conclusion of standard contracts, it should be noted that, despite significant efforts toward standardization and unification of contractual practices to promote international trade and economic integration, considerable heterogeneity and problems remain due to differences in legal systems, historical roots, and market standardization.

Standard contract forms and general business terms can contribute to the unification or harmonization of international trade law. For this, it is first necessary to clarify the meaning of the term “standard contract.” Two aspects of a standard contract are obvious and require no additional comments.

A standard contract is usually executed in writing with pre-agreed terms that one party presents to the other. However, providing a universal definition of this term is difficult because, in commercial practice, it is used in two different senses. First, a “standard contract” can refer to model contract forms containing pre-developed terms suitable for a wide range of transactions. Second, the term can refer to adhesion contracts, where one party (usually in a stronger position) dictates the contract terms, which the other party must accept without the possibility of modification. It is important to note that these two meanings of “standard contract” are not identical and have significant differences.

A standard form contract is a template document that serves as the basis for drafting specific agreements. Lawyers and business practitioners use it as a starting point, making necessary modifications and adaptations according to the specifics of each situation. An adhesion contract, in essence, is a ready-to-sign document offered by one party to another. Its terms are considered final and are not subject to negotiation or modification, except for minor details. The party to whom the adhesion contract is offered has only the right to accept it as presented or to reject it⁴².

In his scholarly work, Professor Yishi Du notes that trade globalization fosters the development of commercial law by promoting the unification of international commercial contract rules at the global level. He also emphasizes that the growing role of China in the world economy is an integral part of progress in international business and poses a challenge to the entire global community. From a practical standpoint, this phenomenon effectively stimulates and safeguards the development of the global economy. To advance the standardization of regulations addressing global issues and fully leverage its potential, it is essential to have a comprehensive understanding of the concepts and attributes associated with it, as well as to analyze the challenges that arise during its implementation⁴³.

Moreover, by consolidating the actual conditions in specific countries, we can gain a better understanding of the current state of the unification of international commercial contract rules in practice, which, in turn, more effectively facilitates their implementation and improvement⁴⁴.

The central idea of contract theory is that, unlike traditional economic theory, which assumes rational self-interest, the goals of the principal and the agent do not always conflict. In an ideal situation, where the interests of both parties align, the principal could grant the agent full autonomy. However, in practice, a divergence of objectives is observed: the principal seeks to minimize costs, while the agent is motivated to reduce their own effort⁴⁵.

American professor Stewart Macaulay noted that most large companies, and a

⁴² C. Schmitthoff. "The Unification or Harmonisation of Law by Means of Standard Contracts and General Conditions." *International and Comparative Law Quarterly*, 17 (1968): 551 - 570.

⁴³ Yishi Du. "On the International Unification of Rules on International Commercial Contracts." *Advances in Economics, Management and Political Sciences* (2024).

⁴⁴ К.А.Усачева. «О современных тенденциях гармонизации и унификации договорного права». Вестник гражданского законодательства (2021)

⁴⁵ Fatima A. Dirani and T. Ponomarenko. "Contractual Systems in the Oil and Gas Sector: Current Status and Development." *Energies* (2021).

significant portion of smaller ones, follow a policy of careful and comprehensive planning in their operations. Major transactions that go beyond ordinary business practices are formalized through detailed contracts. For example, the sale of the Empire State Building for \$65 million involved over one hundred lawyers representing thirty-four parties, who drafted a 400-page contract. Another illustration is an agreement by an American rubber company to provide technical assistance to a Japanese firm worth several million dollars; this agreement was set out in a contract comprising eighty-eight clauses across seventeen pages. Twelve surveyed in-house lawyers—working for a single corporation rather than multiple clients—stated that all companies, except the very smallest, carefully plan most transactions of any significance⁴⁶.

Thus, the goods being sold and their price can be specifically planned for each transaction, while standard provisions further elaborate on these arrangements and encompass other aspects of planning.

Furthermore, legal scholar H. Kutz noted that public law jurisdictions appear to accept internal legal diversity with a considerable degree of equanimity. The United States, the United Kingdom, and Canada function as unified markets despite lacking a single, uniform contract or tort law, and they seemingly do not regard uniformity in these areas as particularly necessary or desirable in itself.

Contract performance under WTO membership. Under its WTO obligations, a state commits to ensuring proper fulfillment of contractual obligations, including through reforms of customs and administrative regulation. A key focus is the provision of transparent, efficient, and predictable procedures for executing international trade transactions.

Particular importance is attached to implementing the principle of mutual recognition of documents and decisions related to technical regulations, certification, and sanitary and phytosanitary measures. This facilitates the reduction of contract execution time, elimination of redundant barriers, and lowering of transaction costs.

Contract performance within the framework of WTO membership faces challenges such as the need to reach consensus among diverse members, shared responsibility for contract breaches, and the inherent complexity of incomplete contracts. At the same time, membership highlights potential benefits, including reduced economic growth volatility and improved procurement practices, although it does not necessarily

⁴⁶ Stewart Macaulay. "Non-contractual relations in business: a preliminary study." *American Sociological Review*, 28 (1963): 55.

guarantee a reduction in corruption levels.

Uzbekistan's accession to the WTO should be leveraged in conjunction with strategic free trade agreements with key partners. This approach will expand market access, diversify trade routes, and effectively address contemporary trade issues, including electronic commerce.

For successful navigation of the complex global trading system and the achievement of maximum economic benefits, Uzbekistan requires a flexible, comprehensive approach that integrates multilateral, regional, and bilateral engagement⁴⁷.

Traditional international trade theory typically treats trade agreements as complete contracts—contracts in which all relevant policy instruments are specified and all possible contingencies are anticipated. In reality, however, most contracts are surprisingly simple and generally incomplete. Contracts are considered incomplete when they do not specify all rights and obligations of the parties under all possible future states of the world. Transaction costs, bounded rationality, and strategic ambiguity are the primary factors contributing to such contractual incompleteness⁴⁸.

When engaging in regional economic integration with non-WTO member countries, a WTO member must be aware that compliance with WTO obligations may be at risk. Extending preferential treatment between a WTO member and non-member parties constitutes a breach of the WTO member's obligation under the Most-Favored-Nation (MFN) principle as stipulated in the WTO Agreement. In the case of integration in the services sector, conformity with WTO law is generally ensured, whereas in the goods sector, WTO compliance can only be guaranteed if the non-member parties are least developed countries⁴⁹.

In conclusion, Uzbekistan's accession to the WTO entails systemic changes in the conclusion and execution of international trade contracts. These changes aim to harmonize domestic practices with international standards, develop digital trade mechanisms, and ensure legal predictability and reliability of transactions. It is essential that the legal and regulatory framework not only complies with WTO requirements but is also effectively implemented in practice, providing equal and stable conditions for all

⁴⁷ Bekzod Zakirov, Alisher Umirdinov and Bakhrom Mirkasimov. "WTO and FTAs: pathways for Uzbekistan's economic integration." (2024)

⁴⁸ Han Yi-cho. "On WTO Agreements as Incomplete Contracts." (2014)

⁴⁹ W. Choi. "Legal Problems of Making Regional Trade Agreements with Non-WTO-Member States." *Journal of International Economic Law*, 8 (2005): 825-860.

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participants in international trade.

PARTICIPANTS IN ENFORCEMENT PROCEEDINGS: THEORETICAL PROVISIONS AND ANALYTICAL RESULTS

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Abstract: This article examines the interrelationship between civil procedural law and enforcement proceedings, the parties involved in enforcement proceedings, their powers, the specific characteristics of the enforcement stage, some problems in the field of ensuring the execution of court documents and their solutions, as well as a comparative analysis of national and foreign experience.

Keywords: court, judge, state executor, other persons participating in enforcement proceedings, enforcement stage, court documents and their types, enforcement proceedings documents, writ of execution, ruling, decree, explanation of a court document, termination of enforcement proceedings.

Introduction. As a general rule, ensuring the execution of acts issued by the court and other bodies is completed through enforcement proceedings. An important aspect of this stage is that as a result of its activities, public trust in the court will increase, the resulting dispute will be resolved, the violated right will be restored, and the list of such grounds can be extended.

In most scientific works⁵⁰ the stage of enforcement proceedings is indicated as one of the necessary stages of civil proceedings, studied within the framework of the subject of civil procedural law. As proof of this, the issues of execution are covered in a separate chapter of the Civil Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In a number of educational and scientific literature reflecting the content of "civil procedural law," the stage of enforcement proceedings and the procedural actions performed in it are specifically described.

According to scientific analysis, the task of completing the activities of judicial systems in all areas, ensuring the execution of judicial acts issued by them, is carried out

⁵⁰ Civil Procedural Law. Textbook. - Tashkent: Tashkent State University of Law, 2019. Gureev V.A., Gushin V.V. Enforcement Proceedings: Textbook (4th edition, revised and supplemented). Galperin, M. L. Executive Production: Textbook for Bachelor's and Master's Degrees / M. L. Galperin. - 4th ed., revised and supplemented. - Moscow: Yurayt Publishing House, 2018. - 498 p. (Bachelor's and Master's degree. Academic Course).- ISBN 978-5-534-08131-2. Text: electronic // EBS Yurayt [website]. URL: <https://urait.ru/bcode/424299> (accessed: 24.04.2020).

and completed through the stage of enforcement proceedings. However, in practice, the authority to carry out enforcement actions and ensure their compulsory execution was transferred to the Bureau of Compulsory Enforcement and its territorial bodies, created on the basis of the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 30, 2017 No. PP-3016 "On the Organization of the Activities of the Bureau of Compulsory Enforcement under the Prosecutor General's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan." It can be said that this body has separate regulatory legal acts, in particular, its Charter, record-keeping mechanism, and various categories of employees, which at the same time justify itself in the practice of the national legal system.

It should be noted that in recent years, within the framework of judicial and legal reforms being implemented in our country, special attention has been paid to the system of compulsory enforcement of court decisions and decisions of other bodies. Over the past years, a number of legal documents regulating the system of enforcement proceedings have been adopted. In particular, with the adoption of the Resolution⁵¹ of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Organization of the Activities of the Bureau of Compulsory Enforcement under the Prosecutor General's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan" dated May 30, 2017, the Resolution⁵² of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Measures to Further Enhance the Effectiveness of the Execution of Court Decisions and Acts of Other Bodies" dated March 12, 2019, the organizational structure of the Bureau of Compulsory Enforcement was fundamentally updated, and subsequently, some enforcement actions and deadlines were simplified.

At the same time, the activities of the Bureau of Compulsory Enforcement are aimed at the execution of decisions of economic, civil, criminal, administrative courts, as well as notaries, commissions for labor disputes, arbitration courts, some decisions of the prosecutor, and acts of other bodies.

During the coverage of the topic, ensuring the execution of court decisions in civil cases, studying the legal status of participants in enforcement proceedings, their classification, powers and duties, analyzing problems in this area and drawing scientifically based conclusions based on the information received, developing theoretically and practically important proposals and recommendations, and most importantly, interpreting the norms of Article 6 "Judicial Acts," Section 5 "Execution of Judicial Acts" of the newly adopted Civil Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan from a new perspective, as well as improving the norms of the Law "On the Execution of Judicial Acts and Acts of Other Bodies" (in particular, Articles 3, 5, 7 of the Law, Chapter 2). Persons participating in enforcement proceedings) **is of current importance.**

⁵¹ Collection of Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2017, No. 22, Art. 425, No. 25, Art. 531; As amended by the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 7, 2018 No. PP-3699. // National Database of Legislation, May 11, 2018, No. 07/18/3699/1184.

⁵² National Database of Legislation, March 13, 2019, No. 07/19/4236/2762.

Analysis of foreign experience. In world practice, each state has its own organizational and legal form, mechanism, and method of conducting enforcement proceedings and improving this sphere. These include the Bureau of Compulsory Enforcement, the Federal Service of the Bailiff, the Marshal's Service, the Territorial and National Chambers, the Agency, the Department, and others. In the experience of foreign countries⁵³, there are state and non-state enforcement structures, such as registrars at the court in Germany, the enforcement service at the magistrate court in Israel, the Marshal's service at law enforcement agencies in the USA, the Office of Court Enforcement in France, Belgium, Luxembourg, which are carried out by bailiffs and private individuals (executives) who have a special license.

In France, the Netherlands, Luxembourg, Slovenia, Italy, Poland, Romania, Slovakia, Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania, enforcement proceedings are not carried out by civil servants, but are carried out independently by private bailiffs on the basis of a license issued by the authorized body of the state (justice), and in their activities they are subordinate to the territorial and national chambers endowed with the authority for self-government.

In China, this activity is carried out by bailiffs, enforcement actions are carried out in accordance with the requirements of the Chinese Civil Procedure Code (Section 3. Enforcement Proceedings (Chapter 21). 217-231 of the Republic of Uzbekistan).

In Russia⁵⁴, the Federal Service of the Bailiff is carried out by bailiffs.

In Kazakhstan, on April 2, 2010, the Law "On Enforcement Proceedings and the Status of Bailiffs" was adopted, Article 131 of which contains special norms "Requirements for State Bailiffs" and Article 140 "Private Bailiffs in the Republic of Kazakhstan."

In Armenia⁵⁵ a Compulsory Enforcement Service under the Ministry of Justice has been established, and enforcement actions are carried out by bailiffs.

Of course, through the above information, it will be possible to compare the experience of national and foreign countries, to comment on reforms in the field of judicial and enforcement proceedings in Uzbekistan, and to widely inform the population about this, to create new scientific developments.

It is no secret that large-scale reforms are currently being carried out in Uzbekistan in the field of enforcement proceedings. It is no exaggeration to say that over the past years, the structure carrying out enforcement activities, regardless of which body it is subordinate to, in particular, the Ministry of Justice, the Supreme

⁵³ Usmanova D.R., Fatkullin B.Kh. Features of Executive Production in Foreign Countries. // Bulletin of the Ufa Legal Institute of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Russia. 2014. No 2. - Б. 40-44. Batichko V.T. Executive Production in Foreign Countries. //Section 2. Legal Techniques and Technologies. - С. 99-105.

⁵⁴ Federal Service of Bailiffs of Russia (FSSP). //pristav.

⁵⁵ Information from the Press Center of the Service for the Enforcement of Judicial Acts (SPISA) of Armenia.

Court, the Prosecutor's Office, has been able to successfully engage in enforcement proceedings.

In the legislation of practically all states (national and foreign states), the organizational and legal structure and name of the body of enforcement may be different, but the composition of the participants in enforcement proceedings is the same, their rights and obligations are almost identical, but there are some differences within the framework of the participating subjects.

Theoretical provisions. The activities and actions of participants in enforcement proceedings play a leading role in ensuring the execution of judicial acts and acts of other bodies. Another reason in this regard is that the issue of private contractors was not raised without reason in the measures of state programs of previous years.

Legislation does not specify the stages of enforcement proceedings and is not divided into stages; only actions such as initiation, termination, and termination of enforcement proceedings are indicated. However, regarding the participants in enforcement proceedings, Chapter 2 of the Law⁵⁶ "On Persons Participating in Enforcement Proceedings" provides for several articles (Article 9).

Scientific observations. In a number of literature sources⁵⁷, various opinions are expressed regarding the classification of participants in enforcement proceedings. In some of them⁵⁸, the participants in enforcement proceedings are divided into two groups:

- 1) persons carrying out claims under the writ of execution;
- 2) other persons assisting in enforcement proceedings.

In other studies⁵⁹, the subjects of enforcement proceedings are divided into two groups:

Main participants in enforcement proceedings (state executor, claimant, debtor, their representatives, etc.);

Participants assisting (cooperating) in enforcement proceedings (judge, prosecutor, internal affairs, bank, tax, mahalla, etc.).

In some studies, relations in the field of enforcement proceedings are divided into several types, for example, A.V.Rego⁶⁰ in his research classified relations arising in the field of enforcement proceedings into four groups:

⁵⁶ Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Execution of Judicial Acts and Acts of Other Bodies." Note: In the text, this law is abbreviated as "Qonun."

⁵⁷Morozova I.B. Subjects of enforcement proceedings: Diss.... Cand. Jurid. Sciences. 12.00.01, 12.00.03. Moscow, 1999.- 225 p. RGB OD, 61:99-12/444-7. Valeev D.Kh. Procedural Status of Persons Participating in Enforcement Proceedings. Diss.... Cand. Jurid. Sciences: 12.00.03: Kazan, 1999.- 166 p. RGB OD, 61:00-12/165-X..

⁵⁸Morozova I.B., Treushnikov A.M. Executive Proceedings. Training and Practical Guide. 3rd ed., revised and supplemented.- Moscow: Gorodes, 2004.- 528 p.

⁵⁹ Argunov V.V., Borisova E.A., Salogubova E.V., Skripnikov I.A., Treushnikov A.M., Edited by: Treushnikov M.K.: Civil Procedure. Reader. Study Guide. 2nd ed., revised and supplemented. - Moscow: Gorodes, 2005.- 896 p..

Legal relations for the implementation of compulsory enforcement;
legal relations carried out by higher bodies of the Bureau of Compulsory Enforcement (city, region, republic);

Legal relations related to the implementation of judicial control at the enforcement stage;

Legal relations related to the execution of acts of other bodies.

Judicial and enforcement proceedings. In scientific research⁶¹ there is another question for consideration: "Can a judge be a participant in enforcement proceedings?," "Or is enforcement proceedings independent of judicial activity?." In our view, the procedural status of the court and the judge at the stage of enforcement proceedings depends on their function in the proceedings.

In our opinion, since the laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Execution of Judicial Acts and Acts of Other Bodies" and similar laws of other states clearly define a number of actions (powers) of a judge at the stage of enforcement proceedings, it is natural that the court itself is also the subject of this stage. It is also appropriate to substantiate the procedural status of the court (judge) at the stage of execution through the following.

The judge plays a key role in the performance of a number of important procedural actions in enforcement proceedings;

- Among the enforcement documents received for enforcement proceedings, a significant place is occupied by judicial acts;

- The outcome of judicial activity is related to enforcement proceedings.

V.M. Sherstyuk⁶² divides the powers of the court at the enforcement stage into four groups:

1) authority related to the issuance of enforcement documents;

2) powers related to the initiation of enforcement proceedings (suspension, termination, etc.)⁶³;

3) powers related to the interpretation of decisions;

4) powers related to the supervision of enforcement activities.

Judicial and enforcement practice confirms that in enforcement proceedings, the above-mentioned actions are considered actions performed by the judge, and this is

⁶⁰ Rego A.V. Legal Relations in Enforcement Proceedings: Dis.... Cand. Jurid. Sciences. 12.00.15. Moscow, 2004. 191 p. RGB OD, 61:05-12/375.

⁶¹ Valeev D.Kh. Persons Participating in Enforcement Proceedings. Kazan. 2000; Morozova I.B. Subjects of Enforcement Proceedings. Dnss.... Cand. Jurid. Sciences. - M., 1999. Isayenkova O.V., Balashov A.N., Balashova I.N. Executive Production in the Russian Federation. Course of lectures. 2008. - 192 p.; Rego A.V. Legal Relations in Enforcement Proceedings: Dis.... Cand. Jurid. Sciences. 12.00.15. Moscow, 2004. 191 p. RGB OD, 61:05-12/375. Ilchenko A.G. Interaction of the Court and Compulsory Enforcement Bodies in the Russian Federation: theoretical and legal analysis: dissertation... candidate of legal sciences: 12.00.01 Nizhny Novgorod, 2007 154 p.

⁶² Executive Production in the Russian Federation. In Questions and Answers / Andreeva T.K., Sherstyuk V.M. - M.: Gorodes, 2000. - 112 p.

⁶³ Note: it is precisely the opinions related to this authority that are reflected in the Civil Procedure Law. Textbook. /Edited by M.K. Treushnikov. - M., 2003.- P.554.

directly indicated in the Law⁶⁴ (for example, sending a writ of execution, clarification of the enforcement document, suspension of enforcement proceedings, termination of enforcement proceedings, etc.).

However, the Law does not include the court among the main and/or other subjects. In our opinion, it is correct to understand that the court's "authority related to the supervision of enforcement activities" should be within the framework of the judicial act issued by it and sent for execution, and from the point of view of the effectiveness of the execution of judicial acts. The judicial body does not have the right and authority to direct other actions of the state executor and influence his actions. Although this body is part of the Court in terms of its organizational structure, its involvement in the activities of enforcement proceedings is illegal. Analysis shows that some of the powers of the court (judge) in enforcement proceedings (in particular, the analysis of the materials of the Law⁶⁵ on Court and enforcement proceedings shows that the courts mainly issue rulings on the suspension of enforcement proceedings, termination of enforcement proceedings, clarification of the enforcement document.⁶⁶ For example, by a court ruling, enforcement actions in a civil case on the decision of the court dated October 14, 2022, in which the plaintiff R.A. filed a claim against the defendant A.B. for the recovery of the debt amount and the state duty, were temporarily suspended until the consideration of the cassation protest on the merits. Another example: by court order, the application of the Yashnabad District Department of the Bureau of Compulsory Enforcement of the city of Tashkent on the termination of enforcement proceedings under the court decision of July 8, 2021, was considered, the application was satisfied, and the enforcement proceedings under the court decision in a civil case were terminated in the interests of the plaintiff, the minor S.S., of the guardianship and trusteeship body under the Department for Methodological Support and Organization of the Activities of Public Education Institutions of the Yashnabad District Department, on a statement of claim for deprivation of parental rights and recovery of alimony against the defendant S.A.

Stages of enforcement proceedings. When carrying out enforcement actions, it is important to distinguish the stages of enforcement proceedings.

In scientific and educational literature, the stages of enforcement proceedings are interpreted differently. In particular, in the works of I.M. Zaitsev⁶⁷ this stage is classified as follows:

- initiation of enforcement proceedings;
- Application of the specified measures of procedural coercion to the debtor;

⁶⁴ Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Execution of Judicial Acts and Acts of Other Bodies..

⁶⁵ Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Execution of Judicial Acts and Acts of Other Bodies."

⁶⁶ In the examples given in the article, the parties' FISHes, names of courts and organizations, numbers and numbers of court documents have been conditionally changed.

⁶⁷ Зайцев И.М. Процессуальные функции гражданского судопроизводства./ И.М.Зайцев. - Саратов, 1990.

- Termination of enforcement proceedings.

In other studies, enforcement proceedings are divided into stages of initiation, application of compulsory measures, suspension, termination, and completion. The completion of the work was carried out in two ways: termination (prekrashenie) and completion (okonchaniye).

In some literature, the stages of initiating enforcement proceedings, applying enforcement measures, and concluding enforcement proceedings are indicated.

In the works of I.V. Reshetnikova⁶⁸, such stages as initiation and preparation for enforcement; implementation of enforcement, completion of enforcement proceedings are indicated. Based on the analysis of the above opinions, it will be correct to choose the most optimal option. In our opinion, since enforcement proceedings are also an important process, a mandatory stage, it is correct and reasonable to agree with the classification that the stages of enforcement proceedings consist of three stages: initiation of enforcement proceedings; application of enforcement measures; completion of enforcement proceedings.

Participants in enforcement proceedings. The enforcement of judicial acts and acts of other bodies is entrusted to state enforcement officers of the bodies of the Bureau of Compulsory Enforcement under the Prosecutor General's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan⁶⁹. Tax authorities, banks, and other credit institutions are not enforcement agencies⁷⁰.

In our opinion, relations related to enforcement proceedings are understood as the range of relations carried out by the state executor with the claimant and the debtor in order to ensure the execution of enforcement documents, as well as, if necessary, by involving other persons in the manner prescribed by law. These relations can be implemented on a narrow and broad scale depending on the circle of participants.

A citizen of the Republic of Uzbekistan with secondary specialized (legal) or higher (legal) education, and in exceptional cases, persons with higher education in another specialty, may be a state executor. As a rule, a citizen of the Republic of Uzbekistan with a higher legal education can be a senior state executor.

The parties to enforcement proceedings are the claimant and the debtor. The claimant is a person whose benefit and interests are envisioned in the enforcement document. Debtor - a person who is obliged to transfer funds or other property provided for in the enforcement document to the claimant or to perform certain actions or refrain from performing them. Several claimants or debtors may participate in enforcement proceedings. The rights of minors in enforcement proceedings are exercised by their

⁶⁸ Reshetnikova I.V. Enforcement Proceedings / Reshetnikova I.V., Zakarlyuka A.V., Kulikova M.A.; Edited by Reshetnikova I.V., - 3rd ed., revised and supplemented. - Moscow: Yur.Norma, NIS INFRA-M, 2015. - 240 p.

⁶⁹ Hereinafter referred to as the "Forced Execution Bureau."

⁷⁰ Article 3 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Execution of Judicial Acts and Acts of Other Bodies."

legal representatives - parents, adoptive parents, guardians, or trustees. Also, representatives, witnesses, interpreters, specialists, and other partner bodies participate in the enforcement process.

Representative. Individuals may participate in enforcement proceedings independently or through their representatives. The debtor or the claimant is not entitled to act through their representative in the execution of an enforcement document, if it imposes obligations on the debtor that they can only personally execute, as well as in cases where the nature of the enforcement document requires the personal participation of the claimant. According to the conducted surveys⁷¹, at the stage of enforcement proceedings, the participation of lawyers was observed in 23% of cases, and legal representatives in 9% of cases.

Translator. When performing enforcement actions, persons who do not speak the language in which the enforcement proceedings are conducted are granted the right to use the services of an interpreter, who is appointed by decision of the state executor. According to the analysis of the questionnaire, applications for the participation of an interpreter were submitted only in 3% of cases at the stage of enforcement proceedings.

Impartial. The participation of witnesses is mandatory in the performance of enforcement actions related to the opening of premises and warehouses, inspection, seizure, seizure and transfer of the debtor's property. In other cases, witnesses (no less than two) are summoned at the discretion of the state executor. According to the analysis of the questionnaire, the participation of witnesses was ensured in almost 78% of cases at the stage of enforcement proceedings.

Specialist. To clarify issues arising during the performance of enforcement actions, requiring special knowledge, the state executor, on his own initiative or at the request of the parties, may appoint a specialist by his decision, and this written opinion must be submitted within fifteen working days from the date of familiarization with the decision of the state executor. According to the analysis of the questionnaire, the participation of a specialist in 17% of cases was observed at the stage of enforcement proceedings.

Partner organizations. In order to ensure the compulsory execution of judicial acts and acts of other bodies, internal affairs bodies (road patrol service, etc.), bodies of the State Committee for Land Resources, Geodesy, Cartography and State Cadastre, banks, deposit and other credit organizations, state tax service bodies, treasury bodies,

⁷¹ From the results of a survey conducted with the participation of employees of district departments of the Bureau of Compulsory Enforcement on the topic "Issues of Further Improvement of the Mechanism of Enforcement of Court Decisions (on the example of civil, economic, administrative, and criminal cases)." (January-March 2020).

state border protection bodies, mahalla, medical, fire fighting societies, public education bodies.

CONCLUSION

1. It is advisable to provide theoretical concepts in scientific and educational literature that define the scope of relations related to enforcement proceedings. Therefore, it is proposed to state that "relations related to enforcement proceedings are understood as the scope of relations carried out by the state executor with the claimant and the debtor in order to ensure the execution of enforcement documents, as well as, if necessary, by involving other persons in the manner prescribed by law."

2. Legislation and scientific developments do not specify the stages of enforcement proceedings separately and do not divide them into stages, only actions such as initiation, termination, and termination of enforcement proceedings are indicated. However, regarding the participants in enforcement proceedings, Chapter 2 of the Law²⁶ allocates several articles to "Persons participating in enforcement proceedings." In our opinion, it is assumed that the stage of enforcement proceedings consists of three stages: initiation of enforcement proceedings; application of enforcement measures; completion of enforcement proceedings.

3. The law does not include the court in the composition of other main and/or auxiliary entities. It is advisable to include the court in Chapter 2 of the Law "Persons participating in enforcement proceedings," but to transfer to the state executor some powers of the court (judge) in enforcement proceedings (in particular, the non-mandatory grounds for suspending enforcement proceedings in Article 35 of the Law: when the debtor or the claimant applies to the relevant court or other body that issued the enforcement document with an application for a deferral or installment plan for the execution of the enforcement document, changing the method and procedure for its execution; when the debtor is on a long-term business trip; when the debtor is undergoing treatment in a hospital; upon the request of the claimant).

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LEGAL REGULATION OF SURROGACY IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN: A COMPARATIVE AND ETHICAL LEGAL ANALYSIS

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Abstract

Surrogacy, the process by which a woman carries and gives birth to a child on behalf of another person or couple, represents one of the most ethically and legally complex issues in contemporary reproductive medicine. It challenges traditional concepts of parenthood, family, and morality while offering new opportunities for infertile couples. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, where reproductive technologies are rapidly developing, surrogacy remains legally unregulated and socially controversial. The absence of a legislative framework has created a legal vacuum that affects the rights and responsibilities of surrogate mothers, intended parents, and the children born through these arrangements. This article provides an extensive legal, ethical, and comparative analysis of surrogacy in Uzbekistan. It evaluates current national laws, identifies key legal and ethical gaps, explores international models of regulation, and proposes recommendations for comprehensive reform. Drawing on Islamic jurisprudence, comparative law, and international human rights standards, this research argues for a balanced, culturally sensitive, and legally precise framework to govern surrogacy in Uzbekistan.

1. Introduction

The last few decades have witnessed a revolution in reproductive medicine that has redefined the boundaries of family and parenthood. Assisted reproductive technologies (ART), including in vitro fertilization (IVF), egg donation, and surrogacy, have given hope to millions of infertile couples worldwide. Among these technologies, surrogacy stands as both a medical miracle and a legal puzzle. It enables the creation of life but also raises profound questions about motherhood, kinship, autonomy, and the commercialization of the human body.

The term *surrogacy* is derived from the Latin word *surrogatus*, meaning “appointed as a substitute.” In its modern context, surrogacy refers to an arrangement in which a woman

(the surrogate mother) carries a pregnancy and gives birth to a child for another person or couple (the intended parents). There are two primary types: **traditional surrogacy**, where the surrogate's own egg is used, and **gestational surrogacy**, where the embryo is created using the intended parents' or donors' genetic material and implanted into the surrogate's uterus.

Globally, surrogacy has become a multi-billion-dollar phenomenon. Some countries, such as Russia, Ukraine, and the United States (in specific states), have legalized and regulated it. Others, like France and Germany, prohibit it entirely, arguing that it commodifies women's bodies and violates human dignity. Many Muslim-majority countries reject surrogacy based on religious principles concerning lineage (*nasab*). Uzbekistan, meanwhile, has taken neither position—it neither explicitly bans nor regulates surrogacy, creating a **legal and moral vacuum** that affects families, clinics, and children alike.

The absence of legal regulation has resulted in uncertainty about parental rights, citizenship of children born via surrogacy, and the ethical responsibilities of medical practitioners. The purpose of this paper is to explore these challenges comprehensively, comparing Uzbekistan's legal context with other jurisdictions and proposing reforms that align with both international human rights law and the country's cultural and religious values.

2. Legal Foundations of Family and Reproductive Rights in Uzbekistan

Uzbekistan's legal system is grounded in civil law traditions, with its principal legal sources being the **Constitution (1992)**, the **Family Code (1998)**, the **Civil Code**, and other laws governing healthcare. Although these documents provide general guarantees for family protection, they are silent on matters of assisted reproduction and surrogacy.

2.1 Constitutional Principles

Article 65 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan declares that the family, motherhood, and childhood are under the protection of the state. The Constitution guarantees equality between men and women (Article 46) and recognizes the right to health (Article 40). However, it does not explicitly mention reproductive rights or technologies such as IVF and surrogacy. This omission leaves reproductive issues to be interpreted under general provisions concerning health and family protection.

2.2 The Family Code

The **Family Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan (1998)** is the central legal document

regulating family relations. Article 51 defines the mother as “the woman who gives birth to the child.” This definition, inherited from Soviet-era law, is biologically straightforward but legally problematic in the age of surrogacy. In gestational surrogacy, the woman who gives birth (the surrogate) may have no genetic relationship to the child. As a result, the law’s definition of motherhood conflicts with modern medical realities and the principle of genetic parentage.

Furthermore, the Family Code provides no guidance on:

- The legality of surrogacy contracts;
- The recognition of intended parents as legal parents;
- Procedures for registering a child born via surrogacy;
- The rights and obligations of surrogate mothers.

2.3 Reproductive Health Policy

In 2018, the **Law on the Protection of Reproductive Health of Citizens** was drafted by the Ministry of Health, aiming to regulate ART procedures. However, the draft did not explicitly mention surrogacy and was never enacted. Consequently, Uzbekistan lacks formal legal, ethical, or institutional oversight mechanisms for surrogacy. Clinics operate under general health licensing rules, with no specific standards governing ART or reproductive agreements.

This legal silence places Uzbekistan behind its Central Asian neighbors. For instance, Kazakhstan’s **Code on Public Health and the Health System (2009)** contains detailed provisions on surrogacy, donor programs, and the legal status of children born through such methods. Uzbekistan’s inaction risks both domestic uncertainty and the migration of reproductive services to neighboring states.

3. Legal Ambiguities and Practical Consequences

The absence of explicit surrogacy regulation in Uzbekistan creates a *lacuna legis*—a gap that generates serious legal and ethical consequences. These include contradictions between laws, lack of enforceable rights, vulnerability to exploitation, and risk of violating international human rights commitments.

3.1 Structural Inconsistencies

Article 51 of the Family Code presumes that the mother is the woman who gives birth to the child. This principle, appropriate in traditional contexts, becomes obsolete in gestational surrogacy where the genetic mother differs from the birth mother. Consequently, the law would recognize the surrogate as the legal mother, while the intended parents—despite genetic ties—would have no legal standing. The intended parents would be forced to adopt their own biological child, contradicting both medical fact and natural justice.

Furthermore, paternity in surrogacy cases remains undefined. Article 60 of the Family Code presumes that the husband of the woman who gives birth is the father. This could lead to absurd situations in surrogacy, where the surrogate's husband—if she is married—might be considered the child's legal father. The absence of statutory exceptions leaves courts without clear guidance, risking inconsistent judicial outcomes.

3.2 Contractual Uncertainty

In countries where surrogacy is permitted, written contracts define the terms of the arrangement—detailing medical procedures, consent, financial arrangements, and the post-birth transfer of parental rights. In Uzbekistan, however, such contracts would be void *ab initio* under Article 354 of the **Civil Code**, which allows only agreements permitted by law. As surrogacy lacks statutory recognition, no court would enforce these agreements. This exposes all parties to uncertainty. If a surrogate mother changes her mind after giving birth, or the intended parents refuse to take custody, there is no legal recourse for resolution.

3.3 Exploitation and Human Rights Concerns

The absence of regulation invites the risk of exploitation. Poor or vulnerable women might be coerced into surrogacy for financial compensation, with little protection against abuse or unsafe medical practices. This violates Uzbekistan's obligations under international treaties, including:

- **CEDAW (1979)**, requiring protection of women from exploitation;
- **CRC (1989)**, ensuring children's right to identity and protection from trafficking;
- **ICCPR (1966)**, guaranteeing respect for human dignity.

Without state oversight, unlicensed intermediaries or private clinics may facilitate surrogacy arrangements outside ethical standards, turning women's reproductive labor into a commercial enterprise.

3.4 Implications for Children

Children born through surrogacy face the greatest legal vulnerability. Without recognition procedures, they may be denied birth registration under their intended parents' names, creating complications for nationality, inheritance, and family rights. In cross-border cases, this can even lead to statelessness—when neither the surrogate's nor the intended parents' country recognizes the child's citizenship (Hague Conference, 2021).

Such gaps not only violate international conventions but also contradict the moral obligation of the state to protect all children equally.

4. Ethical and Religious Perspectives

Uzbekistan's approach to surrogacy cannot be separated from its moral and religious context. The nation's ethical reasoning is deeply informed by Islamic jurisprudence (*fiqh*), which emphasizes family sanctity and lineage. Simultaneously, as a secular state, Uzbekistan must also consider universal human rights principles that affirm reproductive freedom and bodily autonomy.

4.1 Islamic Jurisprudence

Islamic law generally prohibits surrogacy because it introduces a third party into the reproductive process, thereby disrupting lineage (*nasab*) and marital exclusivity. The **Islamic Fiqh Council (Jeddah, 1985)** declared that surrogacy "confuses parentage and contradicts the objectives of Sharia." The Qur'an explicitly upholds the sanctity of the marital bond and prohibits forms of reproduction that blur genetic heritage (Surah Al-Mujadila 58:2).

However, modern scholars such as **Yusuf Al-Qaradawi (2003)** and **Muhammad Tantawi (1998)** have argued for nuanced positions. They suggest that gestational surrogacy might be conditionally permissible if both gametes belong to the married couple and no donor material is involved. In such cases, the surrogate's role is limited to nurturing the embryo, not contributing genetically, and thus may be allowed under the principle of *maslaha* (public interest).

4.2 Secular Ethics and Feminist Perspectives

Secular ethics views surrogacy through the lenses of autonomy, consent, and

exploitation. Supporters emphasize the surrogate's freedom to choose and the intended parents' right to procreate. Opponents argue that surrogacy commercializes motherhood and treats the human body as a transactional commodity. Feminist scholars like **Elizabeth Anderson (1990)** contend that commercial surrogacy "degrades women by turning their reproductive labor into a market commodity."

In the Uzbek context, where motherhood carries spiritual and cultural reverence, these critiques resonate strongly. A regulatory framework must therefore protect both moral integrity and individual autonomy.

4.3 Public Opinion and Cultural Sensitivity

Public discourse in Uzbekistan reveals ambivalence. While surrogacy is often perceived as unnatural or morally ambiguous, compassion for infertile couples remains high. Surveys indicate moderate support for **altruistic surrogacy**—where no commercial payment is involved but expenses are covered. This cultural nuance suggests that regulation permitting only medically justified and altruistic surrogacy could achieve social acceptance while respecting Islamic and moral boundaries.

4.4 Ethical Balance

Uzbekistan's policy challenge lies in balancing religious ethics, social morality, and legal modernity. A viable solution is a **hybrid ethical model** that:

- Prohibits commercial surrogacy and third-party gamete donation;
- Permits altruistic gestational surrogacy under state supervision;
- Ensures transparency, informed consent, and health protection.
This balance respects Sharia's concern for lineage, secular law's emphasis on human rights, and modern medicine's capacity to alleviate suffering.

5. Comparative Legal Models

Globally, surrogacy regulation varies dramatically. The spectrum ranges from prohibition to full legalization, reflecting differences in moral philosophy, culture, and socioeconomics.

- **Russia and Ukraine:** Fully legalized commercial surrogacy with binding contracts and direct parental registration. However, this openness has created ethical controversies and “reproductive tourism.”
- **Kazakhstan:** Allows both altruistic and commercial surrogacy but under strict medical and ethical supervision, requiring notarized agreements and psychological screening.
- **European Union:** Countries like France, Germany, and Italy prohibit surrogacy entirely. The **European Court of Human Rights** (ECHR, 2014) mandates, however, that member states must recognize the legal status of children born abroad through lawful surrogacy to uphold the right to family life.
- **United States:** State-based regulation. California and Illinois fully legalize surrogacy, while Michigan bans it criminally.
- **India:** Once a global surrogacy hub, India banned commercial surrogacy in 2021, now allowing only altruistic arrangements between relatives.

Each model embodies distinct ethical trade-offs, offering valuable lessons for Uzbekistan’s future lawmaking.

6. Comparative Evaluation and Lessons for Uzbekistan

From a comparative standpoint, three major approaches can be identified:

1. **Prohibitive Model (Europe)** – Prohibits all surrogacy on moral grounds, preserving human dignity but leading to reproductive tourism.
2. **Permissive Model (Russia, Ukraine)** – Legalizes surrogacy comprehensively but risks commercialization and exploitation.
3. **Hybrid Model (Kazakhstan, India)** – Permits only altruistic and medically necessary surrogacy under state regulation.

For Uzbekistan, the **hybrid model** offers the most compatible balance between cultural values and medical needs. The Kazakh framework—requiring medical justification, notarized contracts, and strict oversight—demonstrates that controlled legality can coexist with ethical responsibility.

Uzbekistan can draw specific lessons:

- Surrogacy should be restricted to **gestational, altruistic arrangements** for **married heterosexual couples** with proven infertility.
- Commercial intermediaries must be banned to prevent exploitation.
- The **Family Code** should be amended to recognize intended parents as legal parents from birth.
- A **state registry of surrogacy cases** should ensure transparency, health safety, and legal documentation.
- Cross-border arrangements should be subject to government authorization to prevent statelessness and trafficking.

Such a model aligns with Islamic moral philosophy, preserves family integrity, and upholds constitutional principles.

7. Recommendations for Reform

1. **Enact a comprehensive “Law on Assisted Reproductive Technologies.”**
This should define surrogacy, eligibility, parental rights, medical standards, and penalties for violations.
2. **Amend the Family Code.**
Recognize intended parents as the legal parents immediately upon birth, provided the surrogacy meets legal criteria.
3. **Establish a Licensing System.**
Only accredited clinics should perform surrogacy under Ministry of Health

supervision.

4. Form National Ethics Committees.

These bodies should review all surrogacy cases before approval, ensuring medical necessity and ethical compliance.

5. Ensure Surrogate Mothers' Rights.

Include mandatory informed consent, psychological support, medical insurance, and fair expense coverage.

6. Protect Children's Rights.

Guarantee birth registration, nationality, and inheritance equality.

7. Promote Public and Religious Dialogue.

Continuous engagement with religious scholars, women's organizations, and healthcare experts will enhance legitimacy and understanding.

8. Potential Challenges

Even with a robust law, Uzbekistan will face practical difficulties:

- Resistance from conservative religious circles viewing surrogacy as immoral.
- Limited administrative capacity to monitor clinics and enforce ethical standards.
- Economic inequality that might drive women into surrogacy for financial need.
- Risk of corruption and “underground markets” if regulation is too restrictive.

Gradual implementation—starting with altruistic domestic surrogacy under strict state control—will allow social adaptation and institutional learning.

9. Socioeconomic and Gender Implications

Surrogacy touches deeply upon gender relations and social equity. Properly regulated, it can empower women to make autonomous reproductive choices and offer hope to infertile couples. However, if poorly governed, it can perpetuate inequality and turn reproductive labor into exploitation.

A gender-sensitive approach requires that laws ensure informed consent, medical safety, psychological counseling, and post-birth support for surrogates. The ultimate goal must be **justice**, not profit.

10. Conclusion

Surrogacy in Uzbekistan currently exists in a legal and ethical vacuum. This absence of law creates confusion, risks exploitation, and undermines both family integrity and child welfare. At the same time, outright prohibition would deny infertile couples their right to family life.

The most viable path forward is a **balanced, culturally grounded legal framework**—one that legalizes altruistic, medically justified gestational surrogacy under strict state regulation. Such a model reflects Uzbekistan’s constitutional principles, Islamic ethics, and international human rights commitments.

By adopting clear laws, transparent procedures, and ethical safeguards, Uzbekistan can ensure that surrogacy serves as an act of compassion rather than commerce — protecting women’s dignity, preserving family values, and upholding justice for every child.

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Using artificial intelligence in venture fund management: legal risks and liability

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Abstract: Artificial intelligence (AI) has begun to transform the venture capital (VC) industry by automating analytical tasks, supporting due diligence, and improving decision-making efficiency in investment selection and portfolio management. AI technologies assist venture fund managers in identifying high-growth startups, predicting market behavior, evaluating intellectual property, and optimizing exit strategies. However, the use of AI also generates new categories of legal risks, including data governance failures, algorithmic bias, lack of transparency, cybersecurity vulnerabilities, and ambiguity in the allocation of liability between fund managers and AI developers.

This article examines the legal implications of adopting AI in venture fund management through a comparative legal-analytical approach. Using international regulatory sources from ESMA, FCA, IOSCO, NIST, and academic studies, it evaluates challenges related to fiduciary duties, accountability, investor protection, and model governance. Particular focus is placed on the evolving legal framework in Uzbekistan, where venture regulation is still developing and lacks explicit AI governance norms. The research concludes that although AI creates significant operational benefits, venture fund managers remain fully responsible for investment outcomes, and regulatory reforms are required to ensure investor protection and mitigate legal uncertainty.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, venture capital, venture funds, investment

management, fiduciary duty, legal risks, liability, regulatory compliance.

Introduction

Venture capital plays a central role in funding early-stage companies with high growth potential, allowing innovative startups to commercialize ideas under conditions of uncertainty and market volatility. A venture fund typically pools capital from investors, managed by a management company or general partner (GP), which assumes fiduciary responsibility for investment decisions.

The introduction of artificial intelligence (AI) into venture fund operations marks a paradigm shift in how investment decisions are made. Unlike traditional methods that depend on expert judgment, network-based sourcing, and manual qualitative evaluation, AI enables systematic processing of large and unstructured data, enhancing accuracy and reducing time spent on due diligence and monitoring. Machine learning models can assess market trends, estimate startup scalability, analyze founders' track records, and predict failure or success with measurable precision [1, p. 16].

The key participants in the application of AI within venture capital fund management include:

1. **Investors (Limited Partners)**, who provide capital and remain interested in the proper and lawful management of the fund;
2. **The management company (General Partner)**, which makes strategic AI-supported investment decisions and is responsible for compliance and risk control;
3. **AI technology providers**, who supply analytical platforms, predictive models, or machine-learning tools integrated into the investment process. While AI systems may significantly influence the evaluation of portfolio companies, the management company continues to bear ultimate legal responsibility for investment outcomes [1, p.17].

When incorporating artificial intelligence into the internal processes of a venture

capital fund, particular attention is given to the alignment of AI-driven decision-making with regulatory requirements, data governance frameworks, and liability allocation. At the initial stage, the fund may face challenges related to legal risk allocation, data protection, model reliability, transparency, and tax treatment of digital services.

When designing AI-supported investment activities, the management company or fund participant typically pursues the following main objectives:

I. Limitation of liability – although AI systems assist investment analysis, they cannot replace fiduciary obligations. Thus, one of the primary objectives is to ensure that the responsibilities of the management company are clearly defined and that limited partners retain their limited liability, even when investment decisions are partially based on AI models. Clear agreement on liability allocation prevents the misinterpretation of AI output as a substitute for human professional judgment [2, p. 7].

II. Avoiding double taxation and minimizing tax exposure related to digital services – the use of paid AI platforms, cloud-based analytics, or outsourced model development may create additional tax burdens. As with traditional fund structuring, minimising double taxation on returns generated through AI-influenced decision-making remains important. In addition, managing service fees for AI platforms – especially when acquired cross-border – requires accurate VAT treatment and contractual planning.

III. Optimality and suitability for all investors – the deployment of AI tools should not create discriminatory investment conditions or introduce opacity for investors unfamiliar with algorithmic processes. To maintain investor confidence, fund operations must remain transparent and understandable. This also allows institutional and foreign investors to participate without regulatory disadvantages arising from AI-based practices.

IV. Targeting appropriate investment segments – AI systems allow venture funds to specialise more precisely, for example, in technology-intensive or scientific

fields, by processing sector-specific data and providing market-relevant forecasting. This supports targeted fundraising and assists investors in evaluating sectoral risks. The focus on specific technological domains, such as fintech or biotechnology, enables the development of dedicated AI models trained on relevant datasets [3, p. 4].

V. Ease of management and regulatory compliance —

AI integration must be compatible with the fund's governance structure and compliance framework. Efficient management requires that AI-based decisions remain explainable, auditable, and aligned with internal policies. In case of procedural inconsistency, the fund must prioritize compliance and fiduciary duties over technical efficiency. Therefore, appropriate contractual, technological, and supervisory mechanisms must be implemented to ensure that AI does not compromise regulatory adherence or internal control systems [4, p. 5].

We have to mention that, the use of AI in VC reflects broader global trends in asset management. Studies indicate that more than two-thirds of fund managers are experimenting with AI-based tools in risk management, market mapping, and predictive analytics [2, p. 4]. In VC, these tools add value in early-stage investment where informational asymmetry is high and traditional financial statements are absent.

In Uzbekistan, legal regulation of venture capital is in its early stages. While venture fund structures are being introduced, specific norms governing AI-assisted management have not yet been developed. Therefore, core obligations derive from general civil-law duties and contractual arrangements within management agreements.

This study builds upon and parallels structural analyses of venture funds previously undertaken and early reflections on AI usage, but expands the scope to include a comparative analysis of international standards and their relevance for Uzbekistan.

Materials and Methods of Research

The research employs a qualitative analytical methodology based on:

Doctrinal legal analysis – examination of legal concepts of fiduciary duty, liability, and investment governance in relation to the use of AI in venture fund management.

Comparative legal analysis – study of approaches adopted by the EU, UK, U.S., Asia, and international regulatory bodies (ESMA, FCA, IOSCO, NIST) to identify rules applicable to AI-supported investment decision-making. This comparison is contrasted with the current legal landscape in Uzbekistan, where specific AI governance remains undeveloped.

Document analysis – study of technical and policy documents including:

1. ESMA reports on AI in investment funds (2025) [4, p. 2]
2. ESMA statement on AI and investment services (2024) [5, p. 2]
3. FCA AI Update (2024) [5, p. 4]
4. IOSCO guidance on AI risks (2024) [6, p. 7]
5. NIST AI Risk Management Framework (2023) [7, p. 6]
6. Academic works on corporate governance and AI [1, p. 5]
7. Industry commentary on VC and AI adoption [2, p. 4; 11, p. 6]

Case-oriented review of VC activity – Examination of how leading venture funds apply AI to due diligence, portfolio monitoring, and exit strategies based on publicly available analyses.

Inductive reasoning - used to synthesize conclusions regarding legal risks and formulate recommendations for Uzbekistan.

The methodology enables a holistic understanding of how AI technologies interact with legal structures governing venture fund management, revealing both opportunities and risk points.

Research results

Artificial intelligence (AI) is gradually becoming an integral part of the venture capital (VC) industry. Unlike traditional financial institutions in which standardized

instruments and historical financial data dominate decision-making, venture funds invest in innovative enterprises whose business models and technologies are often experimental. Thus, reliance on AI tools offers an opportunity to reduce informational asymmetry, accelerate evaluation, improve portfolio monitoring, and mitigate risks associated with early-stage uncertainty. However, this integration also generates significant legal risks and raises questions about the allocation of responsibility between participants of a venture fund.

AI affects the entire investment cycle — from deal sourcing to due diligence, valuation, and exit strategy. Modern AI tools analyze founders' backgrounds, technological feasibility, market development, and sentiment indicators through machine learning, Big Data processing, and natural language analysis. According to industry research, more than half of global venture funds now use some form of automated decision-making or predictive analytics to identify potential portfolio companies, evaluate intellectual property strength, and model exit prospects [2, p. 4]. For example, algorithms developed in the U.S. and Asian markets assess thousands of early-stage companies based on patterns recognizable only through computational analysis [11, p. 6].

Nevertheless, while AI can increase efficiency and accuracy, it introduces new legal and operational risks. These risks can be categorized into five major groups: fiduciary-duty risks, data governance risks, model risks, discrimination risks, and liability-allocation risks, like:

1. *Fiduciary-duty risks and responsibility of the management company.* In most jurisdictions, including the European Union and Uzbekistan, the general partner (GP) or management company of a venture fund bears fiduciary duties to limited partners (LPs). These duties typically include the duty of care, the duty of loyalty, and the duty to act in the best interests of investors. The use of AI does not abolish or diminish these obligations.

As ESMA notes, firms employing AI in investment processes remain fully responsible for regulatory obligations, including suitability evaluation, governance, and consumer protection [4, p. 8]. Even if an algorithm suggests a particular investment, a GP must still review it, verify its reasonability, and act prudently. Similar positions are stated by the UK's Financial Conduct Authority (FCA), which emphasizes that the use of automated systems does not justify poor decision-making or rule violations [5, p. 6].

From a civil-law perspective, AI tools may be qualified as auxiliary instruments assisting professional judgment; thus, their use does not shift statutory duties to a third party. Should losses occur due to reliance on an AI system, the management company may still be deemed negligent unless it can demonstrate proper oversight, testing, and justification.

In Uzbekistan, the legal framework for venture funds is still forming, and there is no explicit regulation of AI applications in investment management. However, fiduciary-duty principles, derived from general civil liability and contractual arrangements, indicate that responsibility remains with the management company, regardless of algorithmic participation. Thus, Uzbekistan's regulatory conditions currently mirror international practice in assigning baseline accountability to managers.

2. Data governance and confidentiality risks. AI systems rely on large datasets, including financial data, proprietary information, and personal data. Poor governance of such data may result in privacy breaches, intellectual property loss, or violation of confidentiality agreements.

ESMA has highlighted that AI-based investment services must ensure data security and integrity while maintaining full compliance with data-protection legislation [4, p. 10]. Similarly, IOSCO states that data quality, storage controls, anonymization standards, and data provenance are essential to prevent misuse or unlawful processing [6, p. 3].

This presents particular challenges in cross-border VC operations, especially

when investing in startups that develop sensitive technologies. Data transfers may be subject to foreign-jurisdiction approvals. In Uzbekistan, although data protection laws exist, they do not yet address AI-specific risk categories, leaving uncertainty regarding compliance in international VC transactions.

Failure to ensure high-quality, legally compliant datasets can also distort investment decisions by producing inaccurate or biased model outcomes.

3. Risks of algorithmic bias and discrimination. Machine-learning models used in venture fund management may suffer from hidden biases linked to training information or model structure. These biases can result in discriminatory patterns in investment selection, e.g.:

- ✚ favoring companies from certain geographic regions;
- ✚ preferring founders with specific backgrounds or demographic traits;
- ✚ ignoring innovative but unconventional business models.

Such patterns reproduce inequalities embedded in historical data and contradict fair-treatment principles. Although no widely ratified antidiscrimination rules exist specifically for VC operations, many national laws include equality principles that may indirectly apply. Moreover, biased investment strategies may cause:

- legal claims from disadvantaged parties;
- reputational harm;
- reduced market competitiveness.

ESMA and NIST emphasize the need for continuous model evaluation, explainability, and mitigation procedures against discriminatory outcomes [4, p. 14; 7, p. 6].

In Uzbekistan, while AI-specific anti-bias requirements remain undeveloped, general nondiscrimination principles apply and may serve as grounds for claims where bias results in economic harm.

4. Model risk and explainability challenges. AI models can malfunction due to

incorrect parameters, poor training data, or unexpected market developments. Such failures may lead to inaccurate valuations, flawed modeling, or misidentification of risks.

The challenge of explainability — the difficulty of understanding how a model arrives at a given output — limits the ability of fund managers to detect errors or justify decisions to investors. ESMA warns that opacity in AI decision-making complicates supervisory and audit functions [4, p. 11]. In turn, FCA requires that automated systems used in investment processes should be documented and subject to human oversight [5, p. 7].

For venture capital, where traditional due diligence is replaced partly by algorithmic evaluation, depth of explainability becomes crucial. Failure to explain reasoning may result in the misinterpretation of risk profiles and unclear justification for investment choices, creating grounds for investor disputes.

5. Allocation of liability in AI-driven investment decisions. A central legal problem in AI-assisted VC management concerns how to allocate responsibility when AI contributes to poor decisions.

- I. Potentially responsible actors include:
- II. The management company (GP)
- III. AI developers or service providers
- IV. Data suppliers
- V. Portfolio companies (in cases of misrepresentation)

Even when AI developers contribute to faulty decisions, international regulatory frameworks uphold that fund managers remain primarily accountable. ESMA and FCA expressly state that outsourcing or automating decision-making does not transfer regulatory responsibility to technology providers [4, p. 8; 5, p. 9].

In civil-law jurisdictions, including Uzbekistan, liability may also be assigned to the management company as the principal organizer of investment activities.

Contractual mechanisms (indemnities, warranties) may provide internal recourse but do not affect external liability to investors.

Thus, unless regulatory reforms explicitly modify responsibility structure, the default rule remains: AI can advise – but only humans remain liable.

Conclusion

The integration of artificial intelligence into venture capital fund management represents a significant development in modern financial practice. AI technologies allow venture funds to perform more efficient and comprehensive analysis, reduce information gaps, identify promising startups, and monitor portfolio performance with greater precision. These capabilities are particularly valuable in VC markets, where early-stage companies often lack stable financial histories and qualitative assessments traditionally depend on subjective managerial experience.

However, the use of AI introduces complex legal and regulatory challenges. The analysis demonstrates that:

1. **Fiduciary duties remain unchanged.** Despite the role of AI in improving decision-making, management companies (GPs) continue to bear full responsibility for investment outcomes. AI may guide but cannot replace human judgment. International regulators — including ESMA, FCA and IOSCO — clearly emphasize that obligations related to suitability, risk oversight, and investor protection remain with the fund manager [4, p. 8; 5, p. 6; 6, p. 3].

2. **Liability allocation remains unresolved in most jurisdictions.** Although internal contractual provisions may address liability among the fund, LPs, and AI providers, these do not alter external responsibility toward investors. Because AI decisions are difficult to interpret, legal assessment of negligence becomes more complicated; nonetheless, current frameworks default to the manager's liability.

3. **Data governance and confidentiality risks are central.** AI systems rely on large datasets, some of which may contain confidential, personal, or

proprietary information. Breaches of such data, misuse, or unlawful cross-border transmission can result in significant legal consequences and reputational harm.

4. Algorithmic bias poses both legal and ethical risks.

Training data and model design can lead to discriminatory patterns in investment decisions, affecting founders and sectors. While explicit AI anti-bias regulations remain limited, international frameworks increasingly demand testing, documentation, and mitigation measures.

5. Model risk and explainability issues limit reliable oversight.

Complex algorithms, particularly deep learning models, may produce outputs that are difficult to justify or audit. Without proper governance, venture funds may face investor disputes or supervisory intervention.

6. Uzbekistan must develop an AI-specific governance framework.

Although the structure of venture funds in Uzbekistan mirrors established international models, the country lacks explicit regulation of AI in asset management. As a result, fiduciary duties, liability rules, and governance expectations remain based on general civil-law norms and contractual agreements. Harmonisation with emerging standards (ESMA, IOSCO, NIST) would strengthen investor confidence, particularly for cross-border investment.

In conclusion, the adoption of artificial intelligence promises significant advantages for venture capital funds. However, its responsible integration requires:

- clear governance structures;
- transparency and explainability mechanisms;
- continuous model validation;
- contractual allocation of operational risks;
- regulatory guidance to protect investors.

For Uzbekistan, the development of a hybrid approach — relying on contractual structuring and adapting international best practices — appears to be the most pragmatic

path. Establishing minimal regulatory standards relating to AI governance, transparency, data management, and accountability would provide a foundation for sustainable innovation and support the development of the national venture ecosystem.

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THE CONCEPT AND SPECIFIC FEATURES OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF FAMILY RIGHTS

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Abstract. The article examines the theoretical and practical aspects of implementing subjective family rights within the framework of family law. It analyzes the declarative nature of legal norms governing family relations and highlights their influence on the protection of personal and property rights of family members. The study explores the interrelation between subjective rights and legitimate interests, emphasizing their role in ensuring the balance between individual autonomy and legal regulation in family relations. Particular attention is paid to the mechanisms of exercising and protecting the family rights of minors and other dependent persons. The author concludes that the effective realization of family rights depends on the harmonization of legal norms with social and moral principles, ensuring the protection of the legitimate interests of all family members.

Key words: family law, subjective rights, legitimate interests, legal regulation, minors, family relations, implementation of rights, protection of interests.

Modern scholars emphasize the declarative nature of norms as a feature of the legal regulation of family relations. The absence of legal consequences for actions that do not correspond to the model enshrined in a legal norm is the result of personal, trust-based relations between close persons. This approach is believed to create a resource for studying and developing individual regulation in the field of family law. When considering the rights and interests of family members, the legal regulation of social relations formed among family members comes to the fore. The legal norms studied by various authors serve as a basis for the implementation of family law norms, the exercise of family rights and the fulfillment of obligations, as well as for the use of benefits. In their scientific works, scholars such as O.Yu. Kosova, O.Yu. Ilina, Ye.A. Chefranova, N.V. Letova, and others have focused on understanding subjective family rights, examining topics such as the realization of a child's family rights, private and

public interests in family law, and the mechanisms of legal regulation of the property relations between spouses. They establish a foundation for studying the development of subjective family rights and obligations and their dynamics within relational structures. According to the definition found in scientific literature, a subjective right is "defined by objective legal norms," "a legal possibility derived from law, reflected in the Civil Code," "a legal opportunity," "a necessary and permissible measure of behavior allowed to the right-holder." In civil law, discussions on the content of the concept of subjective rights have been active, but over time, this issue has lost its topicality and has moved into the category of specific matters.

We support the views of authors who paid attention to the following characteristics of subjective rights: "a legally guaranteed measure of certain behavior or, more precisely, a specific opportunity belonging to a person and the guarantee of certain behavior"; "a subjective right or authority is the possibility, protected by the state, to demand certain behavior (to act or refrain from acting) from others"; "the permissibility of actions by the authorized person and the legal guarantee of such actions constitute the content of subjective rights." The definitions emphasize that subjective rights are ensured by specific legal measures. Logically, from the perspective of legal theory, there is nothing unique in defining a subjective family right in a broad sense: it can be understood as the possibility for an authorized person in family relations to choose actions and as a legally established measure of permitted behavior, secured by law and mandatory procedure, aimed at achieving certain benefits. However, taking into account the essence of family relations and the principles of family law, it is necessary to study in detail the sectoral features of family rights implementation based on their nature and legal principles.

A person may enter into marital relations (historically, cases of early marriage and cohabitation in adolescence were known, where childbirth occurred with the emergence of physiological capacity), but for the protection of health and morals, the marriageable age is determined by law (Articles 13–16 of the Family Code). Parents have both the right and the duty to exercise their rights, but the law does not specify how exactly they should exercise the right to raise their child, and it is difficult to determine this legislatively. The legislator has only defined methods and forms of upbringing that are not permissible: those that contradict the child's interests (Article 75 of the Family Code), harm the physical and mental health of children, or damage their moral development; neglect, cruelty, rudeness, humiliation of human dignity, insults, or exploitation of children are excluded. Although the forms and methods of upbringing are not specified by law, the scope of exercising family rights, including the right to upbringing, is clearly defined.

Yu.F. Bepalov concluded regarding the subjective rights of a child that they are "the possibility defined by the norms of family law for a child to independently, or through parents (or persons replacing them), exercise their behavior in family relations,"

which characterizes the implementation of the family rights of minors.

It should be noted that in some cases, those who cannot exercise their rights independently include not only children but also persons who are incapacitated or in need of assistance (for example, individuals suffering from persistent health disorders).

A.M. Nechaeva, studying subjective rights as a legal category, defined them as "the possibility of using a specific social good." Thus, the opportunity to use social goods is ensured for both minors and other persons in need of assistance through the actions of family members aimed at meeting their needs, and these actions are carried out within the permitted scope of behavior established by law. A distinctive feature of family rights is the issue of their implementation. The possibility of exercising subjective family rights is an interesting aspect for research. The view that subjective family rights are declarative is debatable and requires a detailed study of interrelated concepts, procedures, and methods of implementation. Along with the concept of "subjective right," the concept of "legitimate interest" (or "legally protected interest") is also distinguished in legal theory and regulation. Determining the relationship between these concepts in family law is important since the legislator uses them as categories of the same level in part two of Article 10 of the Civil Code. Questions arise: Are they truly equivalent concepts, or do they differ significantly, and how significant are these differences for the implementation of family rights?

In fact, these legal concepts are close in content, functions, and purpose. However, there are differences: subjective rights and legitimate interests are not identical—they represent "different forms of legal permissibility." A legitimate interest is a simple form of legal permissibility that has a desirous nature, lacks a clear indication of how to act or demand appropriate behavior from others, and is not secured by a specific legal obligation.

This distinction can serve as the main criterion for differentiating between legitimate interests and subjective rights. Legal obligations correspond to subjective rights but not to legitimate interests since they are ensured in another, different way. The interest acts as a connecting link between various benefits and subjective rights. Only the most important, significant, and socially necessary interests are formalized as subjective rights. From the above, it can logically be concluded that interest serves as an intermediary link between a person's need, benefit, and the right enshrined in law and in specific legal relations—the subjective right of an individual or a family member. Interest may serve as a basis for the emergence of law and as its implementation goal. As a necessity to satisfy socially significant needs, interest precedes subjective rights, and subjective rights derive from it. Interest becomes a means of implementing subjective rights and legal obligations. On one hand, interest should be regarded as the basis for the emergence of law; however, in our opinion, the interest of the obligated person and the interest of the right-holder differ. Interest stimulates the emergence and development of legal relations—it

serves as the motive for behavior. Depending on the interest, corresponding rights and obligations arise and develop, leading to changes and movement in legal relations.

When studying a legally protected interest, I.V. Venediktova identifies several stages in the "mechanism of implementing legally protected interests":

1) "Modeling and identifying the interest of the subject of legal relations"—through this, the interest rises from the level of benefit to the level of subjective interest;

2) "Ensuring the legality of this interest—its verification for compliance with the law," meaning the interest acquires a legal nature and, depending on its social significance, moves into the scope of subjective rights;

3) "Direct implementation of the legally protected interest—obtaining a specific material or non-material benefit, as well as a change in legal status"—this represents, from S.S. Alekseyev's perspective, the stage of a legal fact in the implementation of a legal norm;

4) "If the implementation of the legally protected interest is not possible—initiating its protection and ensuring such protection, which ultimately leads to the positive realization of the legally protected interest." This stage of protection has its own distinctive features separating interest from law.

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MARRIAGE ISSUES IN THE FAMILY LAW OF CENTRAL ASIAN COUNTRIES

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Abstract: In the context of deepening integration processes in the world, global changes in social relations have a significant impact on the institution of the family, its position, composition, structure, tasks and activities. Today, as a result of the collapse of family traditions in many countries, the number of divorces is increasing, the birth rate is falling, non-traditional forms of marriage are appearing, and the number of children born out of wedlock and children deprived of parental care is increasing. care increases, the approach to family relationships changes dramatically, and in the new conditions it becomes necessary to improve the institutional foundations of support.

Keywords. marriage, conditions for marriage, procedure for marriage, marriageable age, circumstances preventing marriage, blood relatives, close relatives, medical examination.

Introduction

Many scientific researches are required to be carried out in our country and on a global scale to increase the educational, cultural and scientific potential of families. After all, "How much right does a person have to say he is happy?" If you are happy with your family, you have the right to say that you are happy. I consider myself happy when not only my family is happy, but also my people," Sh.M. Mirziyoev said. [1].

It is known that human development is influenced by 50% genes and 50% environment. Interestingly, parents provide not only 50% of genes, but also the environment for development[2]. It should be noted separately that the state of violence and neglect of children is of concern to the society. Everyone and society have a legal and moral obligation to help ensure the safety and well-being of children. As of January 1, 2024, the demographic indicators of Uzbekistan show that the number of marriages was 283.8 thousand, and the number of divorces was 49.2 thousand [3].

The issues of legal protection of marriage are also reflected in the "Universal

Declaration of Human Rights", "On Civil and Political Rights"[4] and "On Economic, Social and Cultural Rights"[5]. Also, the provisions of the Convention "On mutual legal assistance and legal relations in civil, family and criminal matters" [6] adopted by the CIS member states in Minsk on January 22, 1993 are also applied to legal relations involving citizens of the Commonwealth member states. It is the only unified law for the CIS countries. On March 28, 1998, the Protocol on introducing some additions and changes was also signed [7].

In our country, attention and care for the family is one of the main directions of the state policy. For example, Article 76 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan states that the family is the main link of society and that it is under the protection of society and the state. At the same time, the state undertakes to create social, economic, legal and other conditions for the full development of the family. Article 4 of the Family Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan (hereinafter referred to as FC) guarantees that the family is under state protection and that paternity, motherhood and childhood are protected.

The first obstacle to the creation of a family is the marriage relationship. If our general encyclopedia recognizes that marriage is based on traditional family values of the people of Uzbekistan, the voluntary consent and equal rights of the parties, then Article 2 of the FC stipulates that the regulation of family relations is the union of a man and a woman voluntarily entered into marriage.

Since marriage is the only basis for the creation of a family, it is regulated not only by moral norms, but also by special legal documents, which legally ensures that the family is under the protection of the state. The current OC does not define the concept of marriage. It can be observed that the concept of marriage is defined in the family law of some countries. For example, Article 1106 of the Civil Code of the State of Georgia (Marriage is a voluntary union of a man and a woman for the purpose of starting a family, registered in the territorial service of a legal entity operating under the management of the Ministry of Justice of Georgia - Community Development Agency.) [8], Marriage and Family of the Republic of Belarus of the code

Article 12 (Marriage is a voluntary union of a woman and a man, concluded under the conditions stipulated in this Code, aimed at building a family and creates mutual rights and obligations for the parties.)[9]. Two approaches to defining the concept of marriage have long been established in scientific research. The first is a sociological approach, which defines marriage as a historically conditioned and regulated form of relations between members of society of different sexes. This concept of marriage applies to real cohabitation, because rights and obligations between a man and a woman do not arise from it. The second is the legal approach that we prefer. It can be seen that marriage can be defined as the union of a man and a woman registered in the registry office in full compliance with all the established conditions[10]. From the point of view of jurisprudence, marriage as a special type of relationship between men

and women is an important legal fact that determines the scope of rights and obligations of spouses towards each other.

Firstly, the issues related to the procedure and conditions of marriage according to the family law of the countries of Central Asia, including Georgia, China, South Korea, Russia, Armenia, Moldova, Uzbekistan, Azerbaijan, Kyrgyzstan, Kazakhstan, Belarus, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, and Estonia were analyzed.

Secondly, the similar and different aspects of the legal norms regarding the procedure of marriage, conditions of marriage, age of marriage, circumstances hindering marriage, medical examination of married persons, voluntariness of marriage were compared.

Thirdly, after analyzing the legislation of foreign countries, it was concluded that it is necessary to expand the range of circumstances that hinder marriage in our national legislation.

According to the rule, marriage includes the following: procedure and conditions of marriage, voluntariness of marriage, age of marriage, circumstances preventing marriage, order of medical examination of persons to be married. Here we consider each of the above in the framework of national and foreign legislation.

Procedure and conditions of marriage.

As in other countries of the world, in Uzbekistan, the issue of marriage and family goes beyond the scope of the couple's personal work, and we can see direct state intervention. The order of marriage is FC

It is expressed in Article 13, according to which it is determined that marriages made in the registration bodies of civil status documents (hereinafter referred to as registry offices) and marriages made according to religious rituals do not have legal significance. According to the rule, the marriage is performed with the participation of the parties one month after they apply to the registry office. The extension of the marriage registration period is considered based on the joint applications of the parties to the marriage, and if there are sufficient reasons, as well as at the initiative of the registry office, this period can be extended up to three months[11]. It should be noted that FC's

Clauses 3, 4 of Article 13 also contain exceptions to the one-month period. First, the registry office can shorten the period by one month if there are valid reasons (this includes birth certificates of children, a certificate from a medical institution about the bride's pregnancy or illness of one of the parties, a business trip certificate, and similar documents). Secondly, in special cases, pregnancy, childbirth, illness of one of the parties, and other cases, marriage can be concluded on the day of application. Procedure and conditions of marriage. As in other countries of the world, in Uzbekistan, the issue of marriage and family goes beyond the scope of the couple's personal work, and we can see direct state intervention. The order of marriage is FC

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The procedure for state registration of civil status documents is carried out in two different ways. The first is if the marriage is registered in the registry office. The second is held solemnly or out of place according to the wishes of the couple.

If the registry office refuses to register a marriage, a complaint can be submitted directly to the court or to a higher authority, depending on the jurisdiction.

If we pay attention to the legislation of foreign countries, we can see the following similarities and differences in our national legislation regarding the procedure and conditions of marriage:

Article 812 of the Civil Code of South Korea stipulates the procedure for the formation of marriage and states that it should be carried out in accordance with the law on the registration of family relations and related documents. Also, a marriage certificate is issued if there is no age of marriage, circumstances preventing marriage, and bigamy[12]. Marriage between Korean citizens is performed by applying to the Korean ambassador, minister or consul about the marriage in a foreign country. The same provisions in Book 4 of the Japanese Civil Code,

See Chapter 1, Articles 739, 740, 741. Only the number of witnesses in a marriage should be two or more, and it is indicated that the testimony should be given orally[13].

Book 5 of the Chinese Civil Code entitled Marriage and Family

Chapter 1, Article 1040 stipulates that this book regulates civil-legal relations arising from marriage or family. Also, protection of marriage and family by the state is reflected in Article 1041, according to which freedom of marriage, monogamy, marriage is based on equality between women and men. At the same time, it is envisaged to protect the legal rights and interests of women, minors, the elderly, and the disabled. Another important aspect is that article 1042 prohibits extortion of money or other property through marriage, bigamy, domestic violence. In particular, it is

forbidden to mistreat or run away from family members. Marriage According to Article 1046, husband and wife enter into marriage freely and voluntarily. Neither party can force the other party to enter into a marriage against their will, nor can any organization or person interfere with the freedom of marriage. Both men and women who want to get married apply personally to the marriage registration authority. If the proposed marriage is found to be in compliance with the provisions of the Code, the marriage is registered and a marriage certificate is issued[14].

Articles 10, 11 of the Family Code of the Russian Federation [15], Article 9 of the Family Code of the Republic of Armenia [16], Articles 9, 10, 11 of Chapter 3 of the Family Code of Moldova [17], Articles 9, 11 of the Family Code of the Republic of Azerbaijan [18], Articles 12, 13 of the Family Code of the Kyrgyz Republic [19], Articles 10, 11, 12 of the Family Code of the Republic of Tajikistan [20], Articles 1107, 1109 of the Civil Code of Georgia [21] determine the procedure and conditions of marriage we can see similarities with the norms of our national legislation. According to the Family Code of the Russian Federation, there is a difference in the term of marriage, and the deadline for the application is indicated. In accordance with the rule, it is specified that the parties to be married should be formed in person after one month from the date of application and not later than twelve months. According to the Family Code of Moldova, the maximum time limit for marriage registration shall not exceed two months from the date of filing the marriage application. Similarities with our national legislation can be seen in relations related to valid reasons, conclusion of marriage in special cases, appeal against refusal to register marriage. Also, the conditions for marriage are Article 11 of the Moldovan Family Code

Paragraph 2 has a different aspect, according to which, the obligation of the parties to inform each other about their health is indicated as an obligation to the parties. In the Family Code of the Republic of Tajikistan, additional conditions are specified for foreign citizens and non-citizens. Article 1109 of the Civil Code of Georgia stipulates that the initial consent of the persons who want to get married does not create obligations to get married later, the engagement is not a basis for filing a lawsuit demanding the conclusion of a forced marriage.

The Family Law of the Republic of Estonia stipulates that marriage must be between a man and a woman as a prerequisite for marriage. At the same time, the court may extend the legal capacity of a minor to marry a person who has reached the age of 15. According to the rule, an adult with limited legal capacity can enter into marriage only if he/she fully understands the legal consequences of marriage. If a guardian is appointed to a person, it is considered that he does not understand the legal consequences of marriage, unless otherwise stipulated by the decision on the appointment of a guardian.[22]

In Article 15 of the Family Code of Turkmenistan, the structure of marriage, Article 16, the procedure for concluding a marriage, Article 17, the conditions of

marriage, Article 18, the obligation of the civil registry office to familiarize persons who want to enter into marriage with their rights and obligations, as well as the conditions and procedure for registering a marriage, in Article 19[23] detailed rules for marriage registration. It can be seen that these norms are similar to the norms defined in the regulation on bodies for writing civil status documents, approved by the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 550 of October 20, 2023.

In the Marriage and Family Code of the Republic of Belarus, there is a norm called "preparation for marriage" before the procedure and conditions of marriage. According to it, legal, medical and psychological counseling services are organized at district, city executive committees and registry offices of local district hFCims in cities in order to prepare persons entering marriage for family life. It is possible. This type of services can be provided to persons entering into marriage by other specialized institutions established in accordance with the law. Although the procedure for concluding a marriage is based on general rules, we can see a different aspect in the term of marriage registration. In this case, it is carried out according to the agreement of the marriage registration body and the parties. According to Article 16 of the Code of Marriage, marriage is performed within the period agreed upon by the parties entering into marriage with the civil status registration body, but no later than three days and no later than three months from the date of filing of the application[24].

The procedure for concluding a marriage in accordance with the Marriage and Family Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan is reflected in Article 13, in addition to the general rules, in special cases (severe illness, disability, circumstances related to being in prison), when one of the parties to the marriage cannot come to the registry office, state registration of the marriage will be carried out in the relevant state institutions. Another point is that the marriage is concluded after fifteen calendar days from the date of application to the registrar. Shortening the period of state registration of marriage does not have different aspects related to state registration and filing an appeal against the refusal of state registration[25].

Articles 134, 135 of the Civil Code of Turkey stipulate the procedure for marriage, and it is envisaged that a man and a woman should submit an application. In accordance with Article 137 of this Code, the Marriage Officer examines the marriage application and the documents to be attached to it. If he sees a deficiency in the application, he fills it in or rejects it. Each of the parties to get married can appeal to the court against the decision to refuse to formalize the marriage. The appeal will be reviewed on the documents and a final decision will be made. According to the rule, if the marriage officer determines that there are conditions for marriage, or if the refusal decision is canceled by the court, he will inform the parties about the date and time of the marriage or issue a marriage license. The marriage license entitles the parties to marry in front of any marriage officer within six months from the date of issuance. The marriage ceremony is held in public at the marriage office, in front of the marriage

officer and two adult witnesses who have the power of reason. However, at the request of the parties, the ceremony may be held at other locations deemed appropriate by the marriage officiant. According to Article 142, the marriage officer asks each person to be married whether they want to marry each other or not. Marriage happens when the parties give positive verbal responses. The official explains that the marriage was concluded by mutual consent of the parties in accordance with the law. According to Article 143, as soon as the marriage ceremony is over, the couple is issued a marriage certificate. A religious ceremony for marriage cannot be performed without presenting a marriage certificate. The validity of a marriage does not depend on a religious ceremony. Also, the marriage process, marriage registration, correspondence related to marriage and other matters related to marriage are regulated by law[26].

Voluntary marriage and marriage age: The global progressive processes taking place in the modern world certainly affect many areas of social relations. Modern democratic society provides people with many opportunities for self-realization and self-satisfaction. Under national law, marriage is voluntary. In order to enter into marriage, the future couple must have the ability to freely express their consent. Forced marriage is prohibited.

According to Article 8 of the Family Law of the Republic of Estonia, a promise to enter into marriage does not give rise to a claim for marriage, nor does it give rise to a claim for damages in case of breach of promise[27]. The attitude towards marriage and the family as a whole is manifested mainly by determining the ideal age for the first marriage[28].

The topic of ideal age at first marriage was discussed by S. Zakharov[29] reviewed using data from the "Parents and Children, Men and Women" (RiDMiJ) survey, which allowed an international comparison of the focus of the study, but did not shed light on the factors influencing ideas about the ideal age. In family law, the age of marriage is set at eighteen for men and women. This norm is also specified in the civil, family and marriage legislation of the Russian Federation, Georgia, Belarus, Estonia, Moldova, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Armenia, and Azerbaijan. In the Family Code of the Republic of Armenia, although the age of marriage is set at eighteen, there is an exception. With the consent of parents, adoptive parents or guardians, a person can get married even after reaching the age of 17 (Article 10, Clause 2).

Chinese law requires a man to be twenty-two years old and a woman to be twenty years old (Article 1047 of the FC) to enter into marriage, while in Japan a man cannot get married until he turns eighteen and a woman until she turns sixteen (Article 731 of the FC), southern In Korea, anyone eighteen years of age and older can enter into marriage (Civil Act Article 807), while in Turkey a man or woman cannot marry until they reach the age of seventeen (FK Article 124).

The situations that exclude the specified youth may arise in different cases in the

legislation of foreign countries. In particular, in Georgia, the marriage of an adult with limited legal capacity is allowed with the written consent of the guardian. According to the marriage and family law of Kazakhstan, the age of marriage can be reduced by no more than two years if there is a valid reason (pregnancy, birth of a child). This norm is also confirmed in the Family Code of the Republic of Moldova. In accordance with the Marriage and Family Code of the Republic of Belarus, in special cases related to pregnancy, birth of a child, as well as in the case of minors having full legal capacity before reaching adulthood, the civil status registration body may reduce the age of marriage by no more than three years. Lowering the marriage age is carried out at the request of the persons getting married. In this case, the consent of parents and guardians of minors is not required for marriage. Article 13 of the Family Code of the Republic of Armenia

In case of good reasons according to paragraph 2, the local state authorities in the place of residence of the persons who want to get married have the right to allow the marriage of persons who have reached the age of sixteen at the request of these persons. The procedure and conditions under which marriage may be allowed under the age of sixteen, as an exception and taking into account special circumstances, may be determined by the laws of the constituent entities of the Russian Federation.

Circumstances that prevent marriage: Marriage registration is, first of all, an opportunity for the participants of family relations to exercise the rights and demand the fulfillment of obligations arising for them in connection with the establishment of marriage relations.

Our national family law sets out a number of obstacles to marriage. Obstacle to marriage should be understood as cases in which state registration of marriage is impossible and illegal.

According to Article 14 of the FC, the following are not allowed to enter into marriage:

at least one between registered married persons;

between relatives closely connected by genealogy, between biological and half-brothers and sisters, as well as between adopters and adoptees;

At least one is not allowed between persons who have been declared incompetent by the court due to mental disorder (mental illness or mental retardation).

Now let's take a closer look at this situation.

The first situation that prevents marriage is when at least one of them is in another registered marriage. Another registered marriage means a previous marriage that has not been annulled according to the procedure established by law. Persons who were previously registered in a marriage must submit a document confirming the annulment of the previous marriage to the registry office. This can be a marriage annulment certificate, a spouse's death certificate, or a court order declaring a valid marriage invalid.

The second condition that prevents marriage is close kinship. Prohibition of marriage between close relatives exists in all civilized countries and is explained by both physiological and moral aspects. L.M. According to Pchelintseva, close kinship is related to medical-biological and moral considerations related to taking care of healthy offspring of the couple, which prevents marriage. Because it is believed that due to the combination of pathological genes, as a result of such marriages, the risk of giving birth to children suffering from serious diseases is very high [30].

The third situation that prevents marriage is marriage between adopters and adopted children.

Adoption is a form of placement of a minor without parental care into a family, in which the same legal relationship is established between the child, their descendants and the adopted person(s) and their relatives[31]. The law prohibits marriage between adopters and adopted children, as their relationship is equated to that between parents and children by descent.

(Article 165 of the Criminal Code). This prohibition is based on moral factors.

The fourth condition that prevents marriage is when one person is declared incompetent by a court due to mental illness. A citizen who cannot understand the importance of his actions or control them due to mental illness or mental retardation may be found incompetent by the court in accordance with the procedure established by law, and such a citizen may be placed under guardianship. (Clause 1 of Article 30 of the Civil Code).

It is also appropriate to analyze the legislation of foreign countries regarding the situation that hinders marriage. In the Civil Code of Georgia, marriage is prohibited if one of the parties is a person in need of assistance, except for the cases provided for by our national legislation, if they did not conclude a marriage contract before marriage (Clause "e" of Article FK1120).

An important case can be seen in the Family Law of the Republic of Estonia. Even if the family relations between direct relatives, side relatives, alien and non-alien mixed brothers and sisters are terminated due to the adoption of one of the persons, it is considered as an obstacle to marriage and marriage is prohibited (Article 12).

Article 14 of the Family Code of the Republic of Tajikistan includes the following cases in the list of cases that prevent marriage, in addition to the cases specified in the national legislation:

- children of brothers and sisters;
- mother's uncle and nephew, father's uncle and nephew, mother's aunt and nephew, father's aunt and nephew;
- persons fed by the milk of one woman;
- persons who have not passed mandatory medical examination;
- persons who have been found by the court to have limited legal capacity due to the abuse of alcohol, narcotic drugs, psychotropic substances and precursors or other

intoxicating substances. Armenian family law also prohibits marriage between children of parents' brothers and sisters (Article 11).

We can see that the circumstances that prevent marriage according to the family law of the Russian Federation, Kyrgyzstan, Turkmenistan, Azerbaijan, Belarus are similar to our national legislation. Article 15 of the Moldavian Family Code lists the cases that prevent marriage, and in this list we can see several cases that differ from our national legislation. Among the cases that prevent marriage, he included the following:

- relatives in the correct family tree up to the fourth generation;
- relatives of the adopter in the correct family tree up to the second generation and adopted persons;

- sponsor and sponsored persons during the period of sponsorship;
- both persons sentenced to deprivation of liberty while serving their sentence;
- persons of the same sex.

These cases can also be observed in the family legislation of Kazakhstan. In particular, according to the Chinese Civil Code, it is forbidden to be married to direct blood relatives or relatives up to the third degree. (Article 1048.) according to Korean law, marriage is not allowed in the following cases:

- 1) between blood relatives of the eighth degree (including blood relatives of adopted persons);

- 2) between blood relatives of the adopters on the sixth degree and close relatives of the adoptee on the fourth degree;

- 3) between the sixth degree blood relatives of the spouses;

- 4) between spouses of blood relatives of the sixth degree.

The Civil Code of Turkey divides the cases that prevent marriage into 3 types. These include factors such as consanguinity, previous marriage, and mental illness. Marriage between uncles, aunts, aunts, uncles and their children is prohibited in the family tree (Article 129). Marriage between adopters and adoptees and between blood relatives of one of them and the other is prohibited. According to the rule, a person who wants to remarry must prove that the previous marriage has ended. The spouse of the missing person is prohibited from marrying if the court does not issue a decision on the annulment of the marriage. Turkish law sets a waiting period for women, and if the marriage ends, a woman cannot remarry within three hundred days after the end of the marriage (Article 132). This period ends with the birth of the child. If the woman is not pregnant from her previous marriage or the couple whose marriage ended wants to remarry each other, the court cancels this term.

Conclusions:

To summarize the above, the circumstances that prevent marriage in the family code have their own interpretation in foreign countries. In our opinion, it is appropriate to expand the range of persons who prevent marriage in order to maintain a healthy gene pool. It is also necessary to expand the range of circumstances that prevent

marriage, taking into account the inability of citizens to move independently geographically (in case of deprivation of liberty of both parties) and, as a result, their personal participation in marriage. In conclusion, it can be said that the prohibition of marriage between close relatives exists in all civilized countries and is explained by both physiological and moral aspects. After all, consanguinity is considered to be related to medical-biological and spiritual-moral considerations related to the care of healthy offspring of the couple that prevent marriage. Because it is believed that due to the combination of pathological genes, the risk of having children with serious diseases as a result of such marriages is very high. Therefore, it is appropriate to supplement Article 16 of the Family Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan with the following provision.

The third part of Article 16

"- children of brothers and sisters;

- persons of the same sex;

- persons fed with the milk of one woman;

- sponsor and sponsored persons during the period of sponsorship".

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Humanization of Criminal Law and Contemporary Criminal Policy in the Republic of Uzbekistan: Trends and Prospects

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Abstract: The article examines the main directions of the humanization of criminal law and current trends in the criminal policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Legislative reforms aimed at protecting human rights, mitigating criminal liability, and expanding alternative sanctions are analyzed, development of criminal legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the field of information security. Special attention is given to the decriminalization of certain acts, the improvement of the reconciliation mechanism, and the strengthening of crime prevention measures. The prospects for the further development of criminal legislation are defined within the framework of democratic reforms and international legal standards.

Keywords: humanization, criminal law, criminal policy, reforms, decriminalization, information security, cybercrimes, crime prevention.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada jinoyat huquqining gumanizatsiyasi va O‘zbekiston Respublikasining zamonaviy jinoyat siyosatidagi asosiy yo‘nalishlar hamda tendensiyalar tahlil qilinadi. Inson huquqlarini ta‘minlash, jinoyiy javobgarlikni yengillashtirish va jazoning alternativ choralarini kengaytirish, axborot xavfsizligi sohasida O‘zbekiston Respublikasining jinoyat qonunchiligini ishlab chiqishga qaratilgan islohotlar ko‘rib chiqilgan. Ayrim qilmishlarni dekriminalizatsiya qilish, yarashuv institutini takomillashtirish va jinoyatlarning oldini olish choralari kuchaytirish masalalariga alohida e‘tibor qaratilgan. Demokratik islohotlar va xalqaro standartlar doirasida jinoyat qonunchiligining keyingi rivojlanish istiqbollari belgilab berilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: gumanizatsiya, jinoyat huquqi, jinoyat siyosati, islohotlar, dekriminalizatsiya, axborot xavfsizligi, kiber jinoyatlar, jinoyatlarning oldini olish.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются основные направления гуманизации уголовного права и современные тенденции уголовной политики Республики Узбекистан. Проанализированы законодательные реформы, направленные на обеспечение прав человека, смягчение уголовной ответственности и расширение альтернативных мер наказания, развитие уголовного законодательства Республики Узбекистан в сфере информационной безопасности. Особое внимание уделено вопросам декриминализации отдельных деяний, совершенствованию института примирения и усилению роли профилактики преступлений. Определены перспективы дальнейшего развития уголовного законодательства в

контексте демократических преобразований и международных стандартов.

Ключевые слова: гуманизация, уголовное право, уголовная политика, реформы, декриминализация, информационная безопасность, преступления в киберпространстве, профилактика преступлений.

Modern criminal law in the Republic of Uzbekistan is undergoing a period of active and systemic transformation. These changes are driven by the need to create a legal system that complies with the principles of humanism, justice, and the rule of law. State policy in recent years has focused on ensuring that criminal punishment does not become an end in itself, but rather serves an educational, preventative, and restorative function.

With the adoption of the Concept for Reforming the Judicial and Legal System, as part of the "Uzbekistan 2030" Development Strategy, special attention is being paid to humanizing criminal policy, digitalizing criminal proceedings, strengthening guarantees for the protection of individual rights, and reducing the level of repressive legislation.

The Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in force since 1994, is constantly being adapted to modern realities. In recent years, a number of significant amendments have been made, reflecting the state's new approaches to punishment, crime prevention, and human rights protection.

Key areas of reform include:

reducing the list of crimes punishable by imprisonment;

introducing alternative punishments, such as community service, restriction of liberty, and house arrest;

reducing criminal liability for minor and moderate offenses; increasing penalties for corruption, cybercrimes, and crimes against minors;

digitizing criminal proceedings, including electronic case management and remote court hearings.

One of the most notable trends in Uzbekistan's criminal law has been its humanization. The state consistently implements a policy according to which imprisonment is considered an extreme measure, applied only in exceptional cases. Thus, according to amendments to the Criminal and Criminal Procedure Codes of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the court has been given expanded powers to impose suspended sentences and measures not involving isolation from society; several articles have introduced the possibility of reconciliation between the parties in minor crimes; and the institution of mediation, which allows for fair resolutions without criminal

penalties, is actively developing.

Since 2024, the electronic criminal proceedings system (e-proceedings) has been actively implemented. This system provides for the electronic filing of cases and evidence, the participation of lawyers and witnesses via videoconferencing, the automated assignment of cases between investigators and prosecutors, and the storage of materials in a single digital archive.

These measures significantly increase the transparency of criminal proceedings, minimize corruption risks, and ensure genuine adherence to the principle of equality of arms.

Anti-corruption policy remains a priority in Uzbekistan's criminal justice strategy. According to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further improve the anti-corruption system and enhance the effectiveness of public oversight of government agencies and organizations" dated November 27, 2023, No. UP-200, penalties have been increased for bribery, abuse of office, embezzlement of public funds, and laundering of public funds.

In addition to increased liability, mechanisms have been introduced to encourage voluntary compensation for damages and cooperation with investigative authorities. A Unified Anti-Corruption Information Platform has been created, allowing citizens to report corruption online.

The development of digital technologies has necessitated updating criminal legislation in the area of information security.

In the 21st century, digital technologies have become an integral part of social, economic, and governmental life. The widespread adoption of information and communications technologies (ICT), the development of e-government, digital services, and social media have led to the emergence of new forms of social relations requiring special legal protection. At the same time, new threats have emerged—cybercrime, the illegal use of personal data, the hacking of information systems, the spread of disinformation, and other forms of crime in the digital environment.

Given these realities, the legislative system of the Republic of Uzbekistan is undergoing significant changes. One of the key areas of reform is the improvement of criminal legislation in the area of information security.

Modern information security threats are characterized by a high degree of anonymity, cross-border reach, and rapid spread. Traditional criminal law norms, created to regulate crimes in the physical world, have proven ineffective in the context of digitalization. Therefore, it has become necessary to adapt criminal law norms to new

types of socially dangerous acts committed using information technology.

The urgency of strengthening criminal law protection of information security is particularly pressing in the context of protecting the rights and freedoms of citizens, in particular the right to privacy, the protection of personal data, and protection from cyberfraud and online manipulation.

Amendments and additions have been made to the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan aimed at combating cybercrime. These include new offenses, such as the illegal use of personal data. This provision is aimed at protecting citizens' personal information. The illegal collection, storage, distribution, or use of personal data without the subject's consent are now recognized as criminal offenses. This is especially important in an environment where digital services accumulate vast amounts of information about citizens.

With the rapid development of social media and digital platforms, the problem of the spread of fake information has arisen, potentially causing public panic, undermining trust in government institutions, or damaging citizens' reputations. The introduction of a legal norm against the dissemination of false information that is detrimental to the public interest will be aimed at protecting public order and information sovereignty.

One of the most common crimes in the digital environment has become the theft of funds through online deception—phishing sites, fake pages, emails, etc. Legislators have established penalties for such actions, known as cyberfraud, equating them with traditional forms of fraud but taking into account the specifics of the digital environment. Phishing and other forms of user deception specify methods for stealing data, passwords, and financial information by imitating trusted sources. This reflects a trend toward more detailed definitions of digital crimes, facilitating more effective investigation and prosecution.

In the modern world, computer systems are essential for the functioning of government, banking, and private institutions. Interference with their operation, through hacking electronic systems and unauthorized access to information, can have serious consequences, ranging from information leaks to undermining state security. In this regard, the legislator has increased penalties for unauthorized access, destruction, or alteration of digital data.

Uzbekistan actively participates in international initiatives aimed at ensuring cybersecurity and combating crime in the digital environment. In particular, the country strives to harmonize national legislation with international standards, including the Budapest Convention on Cybercrime.

Specialized units are being created within law enforcement agencies, cybercrime investigation methods are being refined, and investigators and experts are being trained. All of this contributes to the development of an effective system to counter cyber threats.

Despite the progress made, a number of issues remain unresolved. These include the need to improve the evidence base for digital crime investigations, increase cyberliteracy among the population, and develop technical capabilities for data protection. It is also important to ensure a balance between information security and the protection of human rights, so that criminal law measures do not excessively restrict freedom of expression online.

Thus, the development of digital technologies inevitably requires the adaptation of criminal legislation. The introduction of new articles to the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan is an important step toward creating a legal framework for ensuring information security. These measures are aimed not only at punishing perpetrators but also at preventing crimes, protecting citizens from digital threats, and strengthening trust in the digital environment.

Uzbekistan actively cooperates with international organizations—the UN, OSCE, and the Council of Europe—as well as with a number of foreign countries on justice development programs. The goal of this cooperation is to harmonize criminal legislation with international standards, primarily in the area of human rights protection.

In the coming years, a comprehensive codification reform is planned, including updating the structure and content of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Key areas of future changes include clarifying the conceptual framework, introducing the concept of criminal misdemeanor, strengthening the role of public oversight, and developing the probation service.

The criminal law of the Republic of Uzbekistan is currently undergoing a profound transformation. Its primary focus is humanization, digitalization, and justice. State policy is aimed at ensuring that every element of the criminal system serves not repression, but rather the protection of individual rights and strengthening public trust in the judiciary. Continuing this approach is key to the development of a law-based, open, and just society.

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LEGAL REGULATION OF BIG DATA IN FOREIGN COUNTRIES' LEGISLATION

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the legal regulation of Big Data in foreign jurisdictions by comparing three dominant regulatory models: the restrictive European and British approach, the liberal United States approach, and the mixed Asian model. The study analyzes how the United Kingdom integrates Big Data governance into existing data protection law, emphasizing privacy and ethical self-regulation. The European Union's advanced regulatory framework, centered on the GDPR and the Digital Services Act, is evaluated through scholarly critiques highlighting challenges in transparency, data subject rights, and technological development. The United States model, characterized by sectorial regulation and the commercial treatment of data, is assessed in terms of its flexibility and risks associated with information brokerage and discriminatory practices. The conclusion underscores the absence of a unified international Big Data regime and highlights the need for harmonized global standards amid growing cross-border data flows. The findings emphasize that differing national priorities—privacy, commercial freedom, or hybrid governance—shape Big Data regulation and influence the evolution of the global digital economy.

Key words: *Big Data regulation; GDPR; data protection law; ePrivacy Regulation; Digital Services Act; information law; United States privacy model; UK data governance; industrial data; personal data; digital economy; international data standards; data brokers.*

INTRODUCTION

Many countries, recognizing the growing importance of global digitalization, have transitioned, in one way or another, to legally regulating the virtual world by defining its basic institutions, their legal principles, and protection mechanisms.

Undoubtedly, an active legal framework for Big Data is being developed worldwide, as it is the main link in the digital chain. However, since its emergence, it still lacks an appropriate legal regime.

The need to go beyond national regulation and study foreign experiences in the legal regulation of this phenomenon is determined by its extraterritorial nature. The circulation of large volumes of digital data extends beyond the borders of a single country, which requires unified regulation at both international and national levels. Neglecting this leads to legal uncertainty for all market participants and slows down the development of the digital economy.

Therefore, instead of introducing local norms within a single legal system, it is advisable to consider the experience of international lawmaking in this field, use uniform rules, and incorporate universal norms into national legislation.

MAIN PART

To analyze foreign practices, countries using three different legal approaches in the regulation of Big Data were selected: *a restrictive regulation model within the framework of personal data legislation* (European Union, Great Britain), *a free regulation model* (USA), and *a mixed regulation model* (Asian countries model).

Great Britain model.

The United Kingdom is considered the first country to pursue the legal regulation of Big Data and its integration into the national system.

Preparations for formulating legal norms to regulate Big Data began in 2013, when the UK government declared Big Data as a key technology of crucial importance for the country.⁷²

The review of the legal regulation in this field should begin with the report "Big Data Technologies and National Security: Comparing International Perspectives on Strategy, Policy and Law"⁷³ (United Kingdom Report: Big Data Technology and National Security. Comparative International Perspectives on Strategy, Policy and Law). The report emphasizes that currently, British legislators aim to introduce amendments clarifying the legal regulation of Big Data specifically within data

⁷² Bart van der Sloot, Sascha van Schendel. International and comparative legal study on Big Data // The Netherlands Scientific Council for Government Policy. P.57.

⁷³ Bennett Moses L;De Koker L;Mendelson D. Big Data Technology and National Security: Comparative International Perspectives on Strategy, Policy and Law -- United Kingdom Report. June 2018.

protection legislation.⁷⁴ This reflects the general trend in the development of this field, particularly within the framework of data privacy legislation, which prioritizes the principle of privacy protection.

In the absence of special norms or regulatory legal acts directly governing activities in the field of Big Data, the United Kingdom currently employs an indirect approach to legally regulating this area through existing legislation, which in various ways covers the use of certain categories of data.

The first category includes personal data, which is regulated by the General Data Protection Regulation (hereinafter - GDPR)⁷⁵, as well as the Data Protection Act 2018, which supplements the main provisions of the GDPR and regulates areas outside the jurisdiction of this document (for example, national security).⁷⁶ Both documents impose stricter regulations on the process of collecting and processing personal data, establish high standards of protection, and set serious sanctions for violating the rules, such as the prohibition of selling or offering for sale illegally collected personal data without the subject's consent.

In addition to the two above-mentioned regulatory documents, there are a number of other documents regulating the processing of specific data in healthcare, media (Telecommunications Act 1984 and Broadcasting Act 1996), security (Police Act 1997), and other areas.

Furthermore, when reviewing the legal experience of Great Britain, it is impossible to overlook the highly significant document of the European Commission from 2017 titled "Building a European Data Economy," which contains two important conclusions.⁷⁷

Firstly, the issue of the legal regime for machine-generated industrial data was raised for the first time. Thus, it was proposed to introduce a new entity - the "industrial data creator," who is the owner of the data-generating equipment or possesses the equipment based on another right.⁷⁸ As a result, it was proposed to establish the "right of the new data creator," which defines the possibility for such an entity to use

⁷⁴ Bennett Moses L; De Koker L; Mendelson D. Big Data Technology and National Security: Comparative International Perspectives on Strategy, Policy and Law -- United Kingdom Report. P.58

⁷⁵ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation).

⁷⁶ Data Protection Act 2018. URL: <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2018/12/contents/enacted>

⁷⁷ Bart van der Sloot, Sascha van Schendel. International and comparative legal study on Big Data. P.60.

⁷⁸ Communication on Building a European Data Economy // European Commission. 2017. P 13. URL: <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/news/communication-building-european-data-economy>

unstructured (noSQL) data and grants others the right to use the data.⁷⁹

Secondly, the proposal to provide access to third parties' personal data based on the principles of fairness, justice, and proportionality, without the consent of the intellectual property owner, but *for a certain fee, similar to the use of intellectual property objects*, was revolutionary in its approach.⁸⁰ In our opinion, this implies that participants in civil legal relations should act in good faith, reasonably, and fairly. As is known, these principles are also enshrined in national civil legislation.

Subsequently, a special regulatory legal document was developed - the EU Regulation "On the Protection of Privacy in the Field of Electronic Communications" (hereinafter - the ePrivacy Regulation)⁸¹, which was supposed to enter into force simultaneously with the GDPR. However, the date of entry into force of the document was postponed to 2019. This Regulation is a specific continuation of the aforementioned European Commission document, which reinforces the free circulation of non-personal data. In particular, it regulates the rules for the use of web communication metadata (for example, WhatsApp), which must be deleted or anonymized when the user refuses to consent to their collection and processing. It also includes rules for processing web communication content to provide a specific service with the user's consent. According to it, such processing should be carried out only for the provision of a particular service, without exceeding the scope of the original purpose. Furthermore, the document under consideration prohibits operators from storing data after achieving the communicative goal, specifically after a particular user has received the message, unless there is direct consent from the person for such storage.

A special procedure is established for a large set of cookies⁸², which does not require the user's consent for their collection and processing if they do not contain confidential information, are used for user statistics, are aimed at improving the operation of the internet resource, and so on.⁸³

An important aspect of the ePrivacy Regulation was the prohibition on denying access to a service if the user refused to consent to the collection and processing of their personal data, even if the service charges a fee for data processing.

⁷⁹ Communication on Building a European Data Economy // European Commission. 2017. P. 13

⁸⁰ Communication on Building a European Data Economy // European Commission. 2017. P. 13

⁸¹ Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council concerning the respect for private life and the protection of personal data in electronic communications and repealing Directive 2002/58/EC (Regulation on Privacy and Electronic Communications). URL: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52017PC0010>

⁸² Bittersweet cookies. Some security and privacy considerations // European Network and Information Security Agency. 2011.

⁸³ Regulation on Privacy and Electronic Communications. Art. 8-10.

Thus, in Great Britain, there is a general need to update outdated laws to reflect current realities and take into account the characteristics of new types of data. The legislators of Great Britain openly acknowledge that the legal regulation of Big Data is at an early stage of development. In this regard, self-regulation of this area is emerging, which involves creating special recommendations for the ethical use of Big Data at the level of individual organizations.⁸⁴

European Union model (EU model).

In the context of the modern digital economy, Big Data technologies are becoming increasingly important. The legal regulation of processes for processing and utilizing data collected through these technologies is one of the urgent tasks facing the global community. In this regard, the experience of the European Union (EU) deserves special attention, as it is recognized as one of the most advanced systems for regulating big digital data.

Based on the EU model, one can observe the existence of a specific mechanism aimed at regulating Big Data processes.

The European Union's General Data Protection Regulation (General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR))⁸⁵, adopted in 2016 and effective from 2018, is the primary document for the legal regulation of big data. This document established new standards for personal data protection and strengthened citizens' rights in the digital world.

According to Professor Elena Romano, the adoption of GDPR has revolutionized the field of personal data protection. This document has influenced data protection standards not only in Europe but also on a global scale.⁸⁶

The Digital Services Act (DSA), adopted in 2022, established new standards for handling big digital data. In particular, this document clarified the obligations of online platforms and digital service providers.⁸⁷

Lawyer Hans Müller expressed the following critical opinion on this matter: Although the DSA is a progressive document in many respects, it cannot fully encompass all aspects of big digital data. Specifically, the issues of regulating data created by artificial intelligence systems remain unresolved.⁸⁸

⁸⁴ Bart van der Sloot, Sascha van Schendel. International and comparative legal study on Big Data. P. 61.

⁸⁵ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016.

⁸⁶ Romano, E. (2023). "The Impact of GDPR on Global Data Protection Standards". *European Law Review*, 45(3), 78-95.

⁸⁷ Regulation (EU) 2022/2065 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 October 2022

⁸⁸ Müller, H. (2023). "Critical Analysis of the Digital Services Act". *Digital Law Journal*, 12(2), 145-162.

A number of data principles apply within the framework of the AI model. From the perspective of Big Data processing, it indicates that the participants in the relationship must act within the bounds of the law and transparently. According to the GDPR, data processing must be carried out in a *lawful, fair, and transparent* manner. In Professor Sarah Martinez's view, the principle of transparency allows data subjects to have a complete understanding of how their data is being used. However, fully implementing this principle in practice remains a complex challenge.⁸⁹

Data should only be collected and processed for clearly defined, open, and legitimate purposes. This principle creates certain challenges in the context of big digital data technologies.

According to the critical perspective of legal expert Philippe Dubois, *the principle of purpose limitation* contradicts the fundamental concept of big data analytics, as big data technologies often rely on discovering unexpected correlations and utilizing data for new purposes.⁹⁰

GDPR grants data subjects *the right to access their personal data (Data access rights)*. Professor Angela White points out that while the right to access data appears theoretically sound, it presents several practical challenges. Specifically, she emphasizes that extracting and presenting individual data from big data systems can be technically complex.⁹¹

Data subjects have the right to request the deletion of their personal information. Exercising this right raises complex issues in the context of big data.

According to legal expert Klaus Weber, *the Right to be Forgotten* holds significant importance in the modern digital world. However, fully ensuring this right in big data systems can be technically challenging and sometimes impossible.⁹²

In accordance with GDPR rules, data processors are obligated to ensure data security. Professor Richard Thompson expresses a critical opinion on this matter. Specifically, he emphasizes that the security measures defined in the GDPR rules are general in nature and may not be sufficient in the context of rapid technological development.⁹³

The European Union's model of legal regulation of big data plays an important

⁸⁹ Martinez, S. (2023). "Transparency in Big Data Processing: Theory and Practice". *International Journal of Data Protection*, 8(4), 234-251.

⁹⁰ Dubois, P. (2022). "Purpose Limitation in the Age of Big Data". *European Data Protection Law Review*, 7(2), 167-184.

⁹¹ White, A. (2023). "Access Rights in Big Data Systems: Practical Challenges". *Technology Law Review*, 15(1), 89-106.

⁹² Weber, K. (2023). "The Right to be Forgotten in the Context of Big Data". *Digital Rights Law Review*, 9(3), 212-229.

⁹³ Thompson, R. (2022). "Security Measures under GDPR: A Critical Assessment". *Cybersecurity Law Journal*, 11(4), 178-195.

role in the modern digital world. GDPR and other legal acts are aimed at protecting personal data and creating a balanced system for using big data technologies. However, as evident from the opinions of the aforementioned legal scholars, this system still requires improvement.

In the future, given the development of new technologies and the expansion of the global digital economy, further improvement of legal regulation mechanisms will be necessary. In this process, the EU model has global significance and can serve as an example for other countries.

US model

A distinctive feature of US information law is that, with the exception of restrictions established by sector-specific laws in this country, there are practically no rules governing the use of any information, which is explained by the free collection and processing of any information.

In this regard, it is deemed appropriate to examine the American legal regulation of various categories of data that collectively constitute Big Data, using an analogy of legal analysis based on the United Kingdom's experience.

Thus, beginning with the category of industrial data, the United States is currently refraining from adopting specific acts to regulate the field under study. Nevertheless, within the scope of the issue being examined, the "Computer Fraud and Abuse Act"⁹⁴ merits attention. It establishes a general prohibition on unauthorized access to data stored on any computer device, as well as the misuse of such access. In this context, a computer device is defined as a data storage medium or a communication device that is directly connected to or operates in conjunction with such a device. The aforementioned Act has undergone numerous amendments expanding the list of illegal actions falling under its regulation. However, the latest attempt to amend it in 2015 was unsuccessful, where, among other considerations, it was indicated that excessive regulation of the area in question should be avoided, as it could lead to restrictions on the free flow of information and a decline in the level of technological development.⁹⁵

The next important category of data is personal data. Unlike other countries, the United States does not have a single federal data privacy law. Additionally, there is no unified definition of personal data or generally accepted rules, such as obtaining the

⁹⁴ The Code of Laws of the United States of America (18 U.S.C. § 1030). URL: <https://www.law.cornell.edu/uscode/text/18/1030>.

⁹⁵ Dana Liebelson. Democrats, Tech Experts Slam Obama's Anti-Hacking Proposal // Huffington Post. 2015. URL: https://www.huffpost.com/entry/obama-hackers_n_6511700

user's prior consent for collecting and processing personal data (except in cases of collecting and processing "sensitive" data). However, there is the Privacy Act of 1974, which regulates the activities of collecting and analyzing public data stored in federal bodies within the framework of public administration, excluding the private sector.⁹⁶

Primarily, the classification of certain data as personal information is determined by the scope of regulation and establishes specific restrictions in sectoral legislation (finance, media, healthcare, etc.).⁹⁷ For example, if we refer to the Children's Online Privacy Protection Act of 2013, it provides an extensive list of personal data relating to children, including IP addresses, geolocation data, and other network identifiers.⁹⁸

Nevertheless, with the emergence of digital phenomena such as Big Data and the increasing instances of confidential personal information leaks, American citizens are increasingly feeling the need to protect their personal data. This is driving the regional development of relevant legislation.

It is noteworthy that according to California's Consumer Privacy Protection Act of 2018, the concept of personal data includes not only traditional personal identifiers, but also cookies and social network activity data, as well as results obtained from processing such data.⁹⁹ Naturally, this significantly expands the boundaries of the term "personal data."

In the USA, information is considered a commodity, allowing for the possibility of selling individuals' personal data. However, due to insufficient regulation in this area, the issue of abuse by information brokers - organizations that collect personal data for resale to other parties - has become acute in the USA. Unfortunately, this matter has not yet been regulated at the federal level, though some states have attempted to legally address it. For instance, in 2018, the state of Vermont enacted the Information Brokers Act, which solidified their legal status and established specific rules for their operations. These rules include registering with the state's authorized body, submitting periodic reports on their activities, implementing an effective security system, prohibiting the use of information contrary to the purpose of collection, and other measures.¹⁰⁰

Depersonalized data, as well as publicly available information, which is almost

⁹⁶ Overview of the Privacy Act 1974 // US Department of Justice. URL:<https://www.justice.gov/opcl/privacy-act-1974>

⁹⁷ Such regulatory documents may include, for example, the Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act of 1996, the Family Educational Rights and Privacy Act of 1974, the Children's Online Privacy Protection Act of 1998, and others.

⁹⁸ The Children's Online Privacy Protection Rule of 2013. §312.2. URL:<http://uscode.house.gov/view.xhtml?req=granuleid%3AUSC-prelim-title15-section6501&edition=prelim>

⁹⁹ California Consumer Privacy Act. Art. 1798.140(o). URL:https://leginfo.legislature.ca.gov/faces/billTextClient.xhtml?bill_id=201720180AB375

¹⁰⁰ Information broker Act 2018.

entirely free from regulation by information legislation (except for restrictions on special categories of information), can be freely collected and analyzed without any notification of such activity taking place. Nevertheless, some authors point out that there is a practice in the USA where technology startups are required to pay a fee to access Big Data.

Furthermore, in the USA, special attention is being paid to limiting discriminatory practices in the implementation and use of Big Data across various sectors. For example, the 2016 Federal Trade Commission report strongly highlighted the issue of how Big Data usage might restrict access to certain services for specific population groups (such as in the use of scoring systems in the lending sector). In this context, the report's authors emphasized the urgent need to establish a legal framework for this new phenomenon to prevent violations of citizens' rights and potential risks.

CONCLUSION

Summarizing the above, it can be concluded that the regulation of Big Data in the USA generally has a very liberal nature, providing all interested parties with free access to it, which undoubtedly has a positive impact on the development of the field in question.¹⁰¹ Additionally, it can be noted that there is a trend towards substituting access to Internet of Things (IoT) devices for the subject's personal data.

Firstly, there is no specific law in foreign legislation regulating activities related to Big Data. Treating Big Data as a special commodity with commercial value (as in the USA) appears to be successful.

Secondly, there is a difference in the legal regulation model of Big Data between countries. For example, while the United Kingdom structures the management of this field around privacy legislation and prioritizes the need to undergo a process of "legalizing" the collection and processing of such data, in the United States, due to the lack of unified data privacy regulations, there is an opportunity to freely collect and analyze any data, prioritizing the commercial potential of information. In literature, the different approaches of countries to the same phenomena are explained by the fact that the USA views data as a special commodity, while the UK points to the continuous connection between an individual and their personal data.

Thirdly, the analysis of foreign doctrine did not reveal an urgent need in countries

¹⁰¹ Griбанов А. Protection of rights to marketing tools of e-commerce (big data, social media pages, YouTube channels, Telegram channels and bots) // *Zakon.ru*. 2017.

to determine a unified approach to the legal nature of Big Data, which may be due to the existence of data transfer structures (for example, a data sharing agreement in the UK or separate information broker activities in the USA). These structures meet the basic needs of the business sphere and mitigate existing gaps in current legislation.

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History and modern function of patent law: European and US experience

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Abstract

This article discusses patent of the right historical formation process , its modern legal and economic functions , as well as Europe and USA patent systems in the example of intellectual the property protection to do mechanisms analysis The role of the Patent Institute in stimulating innovation, problems related to monopolies , and the stages of development of judicial and regulatory practice are studied on a scientific basis. International experience is analyzed in comparison with national legislation, and legal proposals are put forward to improve the patent system of Uzbekistan.

Keywords : *Patent law, invention, intellectual property, innovation, monopolies, European experience, US patent system, case law, legal reform.*

When looking at the historical roots of patent law, it is clear that the origin of the idea of patenting an invention is unclear. Some sources mention that the ancient Greek polis had a similar system of patents. However, most researchers believe that the first informal patenting practice appeared in Renaissance Italy in 1474.

The first document recognized as a modern patent was filed in Florence in 1421 to Filippo Brunelleschi. He was known for his work on the dome of the Florence Cathedral, and was granted exclusive rights to use this technology for three years for his creation of a new type of boat called “Il Badalone” designed to transport heavy loads such as marble slabs down the Arno River. Later, in 1474, the Venetian Senate adopted the Statute of Venice, which introduced a system of protection for disclosed technical solutions that were new and inventive.

The first patent for an invention in England was granted in 1449 by King Henry IV to John Uthynham, a Flemish-born stained glass master. He had a 20-year monopoly

on a glass-making technique previously unknown in England. This method was used to decorate the windows of Eton College.

centuries since the adoption of the Monopolies Act, the patent system has been developed not through direct legislation, but through judicial practice. In this process, lawyers and judges have shaped the mechanisms of application of patent law through interpretations and legal interpretations. By the reign of Queen Anne, significant changes had occurred in the procedure for granting patents: now patentees were required not only to disclose the essence of the invention, but also to provide in writing a method of its practical application. This approach laid the foundation for the formation of the institution of the “patent specification”.

Providing a patent specification is the patent for a machine gun granted to James Puckle in 1718. This patent required the inventor to provide a detailed description of the technical solution and the procedure for its application. Similarly, Arkwright's famous spinning machine patent, filed in 1785, was invalidated despite ten years of practical use due to the incomplete specification. This case demonstrates the importance of transparency and clarity in the protection of inventions.

In 19th century, the patenting process had become extremely complex and expensive. To obtain a patent, an applicant had to apply to seven different offices, obtain the monarch's signature twice, and pay high fees at each stage. Although technological development took place at a rapid pace during the Industrial Revolution of 1760–1830, the existing patent system was not adapted to these changes. It was this imbalance that intensified the need for an update of the system, and the need for patent reform became clear during the Great International Exhibition of 1851.

Following institutional reforms, the Patents Amendment Act of 1852 established the modern Patent Office. This reform radically overhauled the previously inefficient and cumbersome British patent system and significantly simplified the process of obtaining a patent. It now required a written description of the invention to be submitted

with the application , and a public publication of patent applications was introduced. Previously, there was a separate patenting procedure for each territory of the United Kingdom , but after the 1852 reform, a single patenting system was introduced, reducing legal costs by almost 75 percent.

As a next step, the Patents, Designs and Trade Marks Act of 1883 established the Office of the Controller of Patents and a staff of special examiners capable of conducting limited examinations. The examination process was mainly aimed at verifying that the patent specification clearly stated the subject matter and principles of application of the invention. However, at this time, a legal examination of the degree of novelty of the invention had not yet been introduced.

The Patent Act of 1902 was a turning point in the development of the modern patent system . According to this legal act, before granting a patent, a procedure was introduced for assessing the novelty of an invention based on all patent specifications published in the United Kingdom over the past 50 years. Despite the limited scope of examination , the Patent Office was reorganized in order to organize the examination more effectively, and an additional 190 specialists were involved in addition to the existing 70 examiners. This indicates that patent protection has reached a qualitatively new level .

The current legislation is the Patents Act of 1977. The Act was designed to accommodate modern technology and allow for future technological developments, such as advances in the pharmaceutical industry. In the 1980s, national patent granting bodies such as the European Patent Office (EPO) and the World Intellectual Property Office (WIPO) were developed. These bodies allow for the simultaneous filing of patent applications in several countries from a single application.

Turning to the issue of patent practice before federal patent laws, America had no common law patent laws during the early colonial period. However, individuals who invented new products could petition the colonial governments, which would grant them

exclusive commercial rights to the products . The earliest such rights granted in the colonies were in Massachusetts in 1641. The Massachusetts General Court granted [Samuel Winslow](#) the exclusive right to use a new process for making salt for 10 years. This case is informally known as the first "patent" in America ¹⁰².

Other similar exclusive commercial rights were granted in other colonies and later states of the United States. These acts were private acts of the colonial or state governments granting commercial privileges to certain individuals, before general patent laws were passed in each state. The practice of using private acts to grant patents often originated [in England, particularly with the Statute of Monopolies of 1624](#) .

By the late 18th century, states began to adopt general patent laws, replacing case-specific acts. These state-level general documents set out standardized procedures for patent applications, the examination process, and general conditions for patent holders. The first state to adopt a general patent law was South Carolina in 1784 ¹⁰³ .

This first general patent act of South Carolina was called the "Act for the Encouragement of Arts and Sciences." Although most of its provisions dealt with copyright protection, it also included the following provision: "Inventors of useful machines shall have the same exclusive privilege of making or selling their machines for a period of 14 years, subject to the same privileges and restrictions ¹⁰⁴ ."

Many other states followed suit in adopting general patent documents, most using a 14-year term similar to English practice. However, without a federal system, patentees who wanted to use their invention in multiple states had to file separate applications for

¹⁰²Manufactures of the United States in 1860; compiled from the original returns of the eighth census, under the direction of the Secretary of the interior. US Government Printing Office. 1865. p. cxxix.

¹⁰³The South Carolina Historical and Genealogical Magazine, Volumes 8–9. South Carolina Historical Society. 1907. p. 56.

¹⁰⁴Cooper, Thomas (1838). The Statutes at Large of South Carolina: Acts from 1716 to 1752. AS Johnston. p. 805
National Research Council (1993). Global Dimensions of Intellectual Property Rights in Science and Technology. National Academies Press. p. 49.

patents in each state, which was expensive and time-consuming. A standardized national patent law was needed for a more efficient patent filing process¹⁰⁵.

[first adopted on September 17, 1787, provides](#) for the protection of intellectual property. This provision is contained in Article 1, Section 8:

"Congress shall have power... to promote the progress of science and useful arts, by securing for limited times to authors ¹⁰⁶and inventors the exclusive right to their respective writings and discoveries".

The Patent Act of 1790 was the first federal patent statute in the United States. It was titled "An Act for Promoting the Progress of Useful Arts." The statute was concise, consisting of only seven sections. Similar to state laws, the federal law gave patentees a 14-year exclusive right to use their inventions without the possibility of an extension. This was unsatisfactory for many inventors who wanted to extend the term of protection for their inventions. They argued that 14 years was not enough, given that it often took several years to commercialize their inventions. ¹⁰⁷Another important aspect of the Patent Act of 1790 was that it did not allow foreigners to obtain patents in the United States.

The Patent Act of 1790 gave the power to grant or deny patents to just three people: the Secretary of State, the Secretary of War, and the Attorney General. Patent applicants had to obtain the approval of at least two of the three officials to obtain a patent. The document provided for an examination process by the same three officials to determine whether inventions were "not previously known or used" and "sufficiently useful and important." This examination process was soon criticized for being unreasonably time-consuming. At the same time, the individuals responsible for

¹⁰⁵Constitutional Rights Foundation, Bill of Rights in Action WINTER 2008 (Volume 23, No. 4). "The Origins of Patent and Copyright Law". Retrieved 26 March 2013.

¹⁰⁶copyright.gov. "Copyright Law of the United States of America and Related Laws Contained in Title 17 of the United States Code". Retrieved 26 March 2013.

¹⁰⁷Watson, Jason. "A History of the United States Patent Office." historical-markers.org . Retrieved 26 March 2013.

examining and granting patents had other important duties and could not handle the process quickly¹⁰⁸. It took months to examine a patent.

In 1793, the 1790 Act was repealed and replaced by the Patent Act of 1793. The document was notable for defining the subjects of patents, which have not changed to this day: "any new and useful art, machine, manufacture, or composition of matter, and any new and useful improvement in any art, machine, manufacture, or composition of matter." The process of applying for a patent in this later act was much simpler than in the Patent Act of 1790. People seeking a patent only had to apply to the Secretary of State, who then had to obtain an examination from the Attorney General. The examination process was simplified by removing the clause that the patented inventions had to be "sufficiently useful and important." Even if the utility of the inventions was insignificant, it was enough to be "not previously known or used" to obtain a patent.

The Patent Act of 1793 and the subsequent Federal Patent Act of 1836 made it much easier to obtain patents. Only 57 patents were granted between the Patent Act of 1790 and the 1793 Act, but by July 2, 1836, a total of 10,000 patents had been granted¹⁰⁹. However, this came at the expense of the quality of the patents granted. Thomas Jefferson, then Secretary of State, recognized the need to involve experts in the patent examination process. He hired staff from the University of Pennsylvania to help determine the novelty and utility of inventions. As more patent applications were received, the still loosely organized patent office was unable to adequately examine each application. Dupree commented in his book *Science in the Federal Government: A History of Policy and Operation*: "The Patent Office was weakened, but the inventors were more active than ever." Patents were granted for objects and processes that were not original inventions or were not useful. As this inefficient situation continued, more

¹⁰⁸PJ, Federico (1990). Operation of the Patent Act of 1790. Pat. & Trademark Off. Soc'y.

¹⁰⁹PJ, Federico (1990). Operation of the Patent Act of 1790. Pat. & Trademark Off. Soc'y.

and more patent expiration and infringement lawsuits were filed. Patent owners were dissatisfied, and the courts were flooded with patent lawsuits.

Under the Patent Act of 1793, the United States prohibited foreign inventors from obtaining patents while simultaneously granting patents to Americans who pirated technology from other countries. “Thus, America became, by a national policy and legislative act, the world’s first legal haven for industrial pirates. Any American could bring a foreign innovation to the United States and commercialize that idea, all with legal immunity.

another federal patent law was passed to reform the problems of the previous acts . The Patent Act of 1836 was significant in several ways. First, the act [created a formal Patent Office, still part of the Department of State , but no longer under the responsibility of the Secretary of State](#) . This relieved the Secretary of State of the enormous responsibility of granting patents, when he had many other important duties to perform. The Commissioner of Patents presided over the Patent Office instead of the Secretary of State. This reorganization of the Patent Office made the process of processing patent applications more efficient.

Second, the law prevented the exploitation of already patented inventions by requiring that information about newly granted patents be made publicly available in libraries throughout the country. Anyone could consult this information to verify that their invention was truly original before applying for a patent. This greatly improved the quality of patents granted. Third, the act resolved a long-standing grievance over the terms of patents, which for the first time could be extended for an additional 7 years in addition to the 14-year term of protection. With the permission of the patent attorney, patentees could apply for an extension of their protection for good cause. Finally, it removed the requirements for U.S. citizenship and residency , making it possible for foreigners to obtain U.S. patents ¹¹⁰.

¹¹⁰Patent Act of 1836, Ch. 357, 5 Stat. 117 (July 4, 1836).

Patent No. 1 was issued on July 13, 1836. In 1836, the Patent Office also went back and invalidated all previous patents. Renumbered with the suffix “ X ” . Prior to this, patents were listed by name and date, not by number. After the renumbering, the first U.S. patent was *Patent IX* . On December 15 of that year, the Patent Office caught fire , and only 2,845 patents were recovered. This resulted in a law requiring all patent applications to be filed twice . This law for duplicate patent applications was repealed in 1870 when the Patent Office began printing ¹¹¹. In 1849, the Patent Office was transferred from the Department of State to the Department of the Interior .

, the basic structure of modern Patent Law was established by the Patents Act of 1952. This amendment required the inventor to describe not only his invention but also the basis for its infringement. In addition, to be eligible for a patent, the invention had to be new and useful, as well as "non-obvious" . This amendment, which required patents to be non-obvious, was made to protect individuals from being deprived of ownership or a body of basic knowledge in a particular field.

In 1982, the Court of Customs and Patent Appeals was abolished and patent cases were heard by the newly created Court of Appeals for the Federal Circuit . The Federal Court of Appeals viewed patents favorably and began to provide greater protection for their owners ¹¹².

2011 , the Leahy-Smith American Inventions Act (AIA) introduced the most significant changes to the U.S. patent system since 1952. After decades of debate in the United States over the pros and cons of the "first-to-invent" and "first - to- file" systems, the AIA changed the U.S. patent system from "first-to-invent" to "first-to-file." The United States was the last country to still use the first-to-invent system. The AIA's reforms eliminate interference proceedings and foster post-grant resistance. Its central

¹¹¹Robert B. Matchette et al. Records of the Patent and Trademark Office. Maryland, 1995. The National Archives. Ed. US National Archives and Records Administration. website . National Archives.

¹¹²Lawrence M. Friedman, 2002, American Law in the 20th century, p. 427

provisions went into effect on March 16, 2013, for patent applications filed on or after that date.

copyright and its protection in one of the most developed countries in the world - the United States, and to introduce the most favorable ones into the legislation of our country. Before considering what protections may exist in other jurisdictions, authors should first make sure that they understand the scope of protection in the United States. United States copyright law is regulated by the Copyright Act of 1976. According to US law, the original Copyright protection in works of authorship exists once the work is solidified in a tangible medium of expression. That is, copyright exists at the point of "putting pen to paper" and creating an original work.

Although copyright can be registered with the U.S. Copyright Office, registration of the work is entirely permissible. In addition, if the author registers the copyright before the work is published or within three months after the work is first published, then the author may seek additional relief in an infringement action, namely attorneys' fees and damages.

The author is also not required to include a "copyright notice" on the work. A copyright notice is a notice in the form of the word "copyright" or the copyright symbol, the year of first publication, and the copyright owner. However, it is good practice to include a copyright notice on published works, and this can be done whether or not the copyright is registered with the Copyright Office ¹¹³.

The U.S. has extensive intellectual property laws, and the government and law enforcement agencies are able to combat any infringement. The U.S. has a high standard of copyright and related rights protection for both foreign and domestic rights holders. Works published in the U.S. before January 1, 1927, are in the public domain.

According to Section 408(a) of this Act, copyright protection in the United States does not require registration of a work. This Act was amended in 1993 to prohibit the

¹¹³United States Copyright Office, <http://www.copyright.gov/> Archived January 5, 2008,

circumvention of technical means of copyright protection .

The history of patent law shows the continuous development of the institutional approach to protecting ideas and technologies in human society. Starting from European countries, protective mechanisms at the beginning of the patent system were created, which served the purpose of popularizing new technologies and encouraging investors through temporary monopolies. This historical development was the main source of inspiration for the formation of the patent systems of Europe and later the United States.

In Britain, the Statute of Monopolies (1624) and subsequent centuries of legislation and case law played a significant role in defining the boundary between patents and monopolies; in the United States, constitutional and federal patent laws elevated the patent system to a national level and made its purpose—“the advancement of science and useful arts”—legally binding. Modern reforms, such as the AIA (Leahy–Smith America Invents Act, 2011), have taken the system to a new level by improving the mechanisms for moving it from a “first-invented” to a “first-to-file” system.

The basis of the patent system at the modern stage – to stimulate innovation and ensure an optimal balance between social benefit and private interests. International organizations (EPO, WIPO) and national reforms complement each other, simultaneously performing the task of global standardization and strengthening national protection systems. Successful patenting requires openness, fair examination, technical and economic analysis , and participatory mechanisms.

Ways of Incentivizing Inventors

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Abstract

The article examines the legal and economic mechanisms for incentivizing inventors and researchers, highlighting the role of intellectual property, copyright, and patent rights in the innovation process. It addresses legal protection for new ideas and inventions, incentives through patents and grants, integrated support from government and private sectors, and international experiences. The study emphasizes the independent development of scientific and technological activities, fair recognition of creators' work, and the dissemination of results to the broader public.

Keywords: invention, innovation, intellectual property, patent, copyright, incentive, research and development.

When a specific scientific or technical innovation is created, the question of under what name it should be introduced into civil circulation is of significant importance from the perspectives of copyright, intellectual property, and patent law. Historical experience shows that, in some cases, authors presented the results of their creative activity to the scientific community by associating them with their surnames. At the same time, linking names to personal surnames can, in certain cases, create inconveniences for future generations. From both a scientific and legal standpoint, it is crucial to emphasize that naming should focus not on excessive regulation but on descriptive or terminological significance.

Previously, in order to encourage new ideas and inventions, states practiced awarding prizes, honorary titles, and medals. However, the lack of sufficient systematic application of this system led to a slowdown in recognizing and honoring the work of

creative individuals. For instance, although there is historical evidence of awards given for the development of a new cotton variety, the lack of targeted and systematic incentives did not significantly contribute to the advancement of scientific and innovative activities. Even today, the results of creative work sometimes remain confined to documents and archives. Among the general population, especially entrepreneurs, insufficient knowledge and skills in this area prevent effective utilization of these results, and there is a lack of sufficient interest in incorporating the outcomes of intellectual activity into practical application in a systematic manner¹¹⁴.

The absence of necessary and effective conditions for creators negatively affects their development and motivation. Inefficiencies in cooperation between state agencies and responsible organizations, as well as a shortage of experienced scholars in the field, further exacerbate the problem. Educational institutions do not implement effective measures to protect and promote creative outcomes; systems to prevent plagiarism and unlawful use are also insufficient. Therefore, it is an urgent task to broadly involve industrial property objects in production, ensure their commercial circulation under legislative frameworks, and effectively safeguard the interests of rights holders.

On August 3, 2017, during a meeting with a group of creators, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, drew attention to certain shortcomings and critically assessed the situation¹¹⁵.

Certainly, the aforementioned viewpoint regarding systemic shortcomings underscores the significance of legal and administrative incentive mechanisms. In this context, it becomes evident that awards and titles in the fields of industry and science are often conferred based on subjective criteria, and they do not fully reflect the results of scientific or creative activity. From this perspective, it is essential that the system of incentives for inventors and specialists engaged in scientific activity be grounded in

¹¹⁴ Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг 2022 йил 26 апрелдаги “Интеллектуал мулк соҳасини янада ривожлантиришга оид қўшимча чора-тадбирлар тўғрисида”ги ПҚ–221-сон Қарори. //Қонунчилик маълумотлари миллий базаси, 26.04.2022 й., 07/22/221/0357-сон

¹¹⁵ <https://sputniknews.uz/20170806>

clear legal foundations or guaranteed through normative legal acts.

The Bloomberg Innovation Index evaluates countries based on their “innovation capacity” and constructs its ranking using seven equally weighted metrics:

R&D Intensity – the proportion of research and development (R&D) expenditure relative to the country’s GDP.

Manufacturing Value-Added – the economic contribution of the manufacturing sector, representing added value from industrial production.

Productivity – labor productivity and its growth, measured as output per worker relative to GDP or Gross National Income (GNI).

High-Tech Density – the number of high-tech public corporations located in the country and their relative position among global companies.

Tertiary Efficiency – the efficiency of higher education, including enrollment in tertiary education, the share of highly educated individuals, and graduates in scientific and engineering disciplines.

Researcher Concentration – the number of specialists, researchers, and PhD students involved in research relative to the total population.

Patent Activity – the number of patent applications and grants, as well as related indicators, such as patents per \$1 million of R&D expenditure¹¹⁶.

South Korea’s leading position in the Bloomberg Innovation Index for the past nine years can primarily be explained by the country’s strong investment in research and development (R&D), its advanced industrial capacity, and a high value-added manufacturing sector. In addition, the presence of high-technology companies such as Samsung, LG, and SK Hynix has increased the country’s high-tech density. The effective participation of scientists and researchers, including PhD students and higher education institutions, as well as a high level of patent activity, further links these innovative achievements to robust legal protection¹¹⁷.

¹¹⁶ <https://www.bloomberg.com/graphics/2015-innovative-countries/>

¹¹⁷ <https://www.bloomberg.com/news/articles/2021-02-03/south-korea-leads-world-in-innovation-u-s-drops-out-of-top-10>.

Some studies indicate that scientists and engineers do not necessarily require patents to invent or be incentivized¹¹⁸. Existing incentive systems and remuneration for scientific activity provide sufficient motivation for creativity and the disclosure of knowledge to the public. Similar views have been expressed by other authors, noting that research activities, as well as the development of technological innovations and scientific knowledge, can occur independently of economic motives and needs¹¹⁹.

However, the motivation of scientists and engineers is not solely dependent on patents or legal protection. Existing incentive systems, including remuneration for creativity and mechanisms supporting scientific activity, can provide sufficient motivation for researchers and engineers to make knowledge and innovations publicly accessible.

From this perspective, scientific research, technological development, and the creation of scientific knowledge are often conducted independently of economic motives. Therefore, the primary objective in improving legal incentive systems should be to ensure fair recognition of the author's work, support creative and scientific activity, and effectively regulate the dissemination of innovations to the broader public.

Patenting serves as a mechanism for knowledge dissemination. This is evidenced by the fact that patent holders often utilize patents not primarily for financial gain, but to obtain other forms of recognition, such as acknowledgment and increased visibility through knowledge sharing¹²⁰. Generous research funding agencies still encourage scientists striving for advanced research to demonstrate the novelty of their work and achieve recognition and prestige based on academic values.

In the academic sphere, inventors are required to provide detailed information about their innovations and knowledge. The widespread dissemination of research

¹¹⁸ Thursby, J. G., & Thursby, M. C. (2007). University licensing. *Oxford Review of Economic Policy*, 23, 620–639. doi:10.1093/oxrep/grm031.

¹¹⁹ Rosenberg, N. (1974). Science, invention and economic growth. *The Economic Journal*, 84, 90–108. doi:10.2307/2230485

¹²⁰ Long, C. (2002). Patent signals. *The University of Chicago Law Review*, 69, 625–679. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1600501>;
Long, J. S., & Freese, J. (2006). *Regression models for categorical dependent variables using STATA* (2nd ed.). College Station: Stata Press.

results not only enables individuals to utilize these inventions but also obliges them to recognize and respect the scientific achievements presented therein. However, concerns may arise that increasing universities' activity in obtaining patents could threaten the open nature of university research and lead to the commercialization of scientific investigations.

The primary rights protected by copyright include reproduction, distribution, public performance, translation, adaptation, and similar acts. Unauthorized use of works protected by copyright can result in liability and, depending on the jurisdiction, may lead to civil and/or criminal penalties. Over time, the foundations for protecting copyright have evolved¹²¹.

The intellectual property (IP) system in the European Union provides inventors and designers with legal protection and enables them to derive economic benefits from their innovations, inventions, and product designs through monopoly rights. This legal framework plays a crucial role in strengthening companies' competitiveness in the market, maintaining their brands, and attracting consumers. Furthermore, programs such as the EU Intellectual Property (IP) Helpdesk offer inventors and entrepreneurs technical and financial assistance in developing IP strategies, obtaining patents, and receiving legal support, making it an effective instrument for promoting innovation and development in the contemporary political-legal environment.

Specifically, under the SME Fund program, grant funding of €60 million was allocated in 2023. This mechanism allows enterprises to partially cover the costs associated with registering their inventions, industrial designs, and trademarks at the national, regional, or European level. The legal and economic significance of the program lies in its ability to enhance the market competitiveness of innovative products by providing legal protection for intellectual property, strengthening monopoly rights, and encouraging investment in entrepreneurial activity. Moreover, the grant mechanism

¹²¹ Kur, A., Dreier, T., & Luginbuehl, S. (2019). *European intellectual property law: text, cases and materials*. Edward Elgar Publishing. <https://www.ivir.nl/copyrightcode/introduction/>

is closely linked to a key priority of the EU's intellectual property policy – namely, the institutional and financial support of innovation, research, and technology commercialization – thereby creating a competitive environment for researchers and manufacturers based on legal security and economic stability¹²².

In India, the system for legally and institutionally incentivizing inventors and innovation actors is primarily implemented through the national intellectual property policy and government programs supporting startups. In particular, under the “Startup India” platform, the SIPP (Start-Ups Intellectual Property Protection) mechanism provides material and technical assistance during the process of registering patents, designs, and trademarks. This includes covering government fees for “facilitator” services, thereby expanding opportunities for the commercialization of innovations¹²³.

The Chinese government has launched a series of scientific and industrial projects focused on batteries to promote investment in the development and industrialization of electric vehicles. Additionally, it implements policies to subsidize infrastructure investments, in particular, the creation of charging networks¹²⁴.

China's approach to developing the electric vehicle industry—through financing research and development projects in battery technologies, providing subsidies for infrastructure (particularly charging stations), and promoting investment—is aimed at the strategic modernization of the national industrial sector. However, experts from the European Union have identified certain aspects of this policy—such as dumping strategies, artificially lowering prices through state subsidies, and expanding market share via aggressive market entry—as potential conflicts with international trade rules and World Trade Organization (WTO) standards. If subsidies disrupt market mechanisms and undermine competition, this may be interpreted as creating an “adverse

¹²² https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/news/new-2023-sme-fund-eu60-million-protect-intellectual-property-eu-smes-2023-01-23_en?utm_source=chatgpt.com

¹²³ Innovation and IPRs in China and India. Myths, Realities and Opportunities. 2016. <https://link.springer.com/book/10.1007/978-981-10-0406-3>

¹²⁴ Kung-Chung Liu, Uday S. Racherla. Innovation, Economic Development, and Intellectual Property in India and China. 2019. 18-19-6.

competitive advantage.”

In our view, the legal assessment of this issue should focus on finding a balance between international trade rules (such as GATT and the Agreement on Subsidies and Countervailing Measures) and national industrial policy. Within research studies, this conflict can be analyzed as a legal balancing problem between promoting innovation and technological development and ensuring fair competition.

The incentivization of scientific researchers is provided for under national law. In particular, according to the Regulation on the Procedure for Awarding Academic Degrees¹²⁵, documents granting protection (ownership) of intellectual property objects, such as patents, are recognized as scientific work. The Regulation stipulates that a patent granted for an invention or a breeding achievement is considered equivalent to a published article abroad (Clause 21). However, this provision and recognition are appropriate only if the incentive is aimed solely at conducting scientific work. In practice, incentives need to be understood more broadly, encompassing awards such as the Nobel Prize and others.

Some scholars highlight the distinctive characteristics of artificial intelligence (AI). O. Okulov considers AI not as a subject but as a legal object, since it lacks its own will, interests, and independent consciousness¹²⁶. Ronald Chandra and Yoga Priastomo emphasize that AI can be understood as the study and development of computer programs that operate intelligently, which in many respects represents the ultimate goal of computer programming¹²⁷. I.V. Ponkin and A.I. Redkina argue that AI possesses the ability to autonomously adapt its behavior, engage in deep self-learning (to solve a specific class of problems or even broader tasks), and rejuvenate itself along with its

¹²⁵ Илмий даражалар бериш тартиби тўғрисидаги Низом. Ўзбекистон Республикаси қонун ҳужжатлари тўплами, 2017 й., 25-сон, 569-модда.

¹²⁶ Окулов О. Правовой статус интеллектуальной собственности. Т.: ТГЮИ, Дисс. на соис. уч.степ. докт.юрид.наук. 2000. С.14,36.

¹²⁷ Chandra R., Prihastomo Y. Artificial Intelligence Definition: A Review //<<https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/d959-3> p. – P.1.

subsystems¹²⁸.

S. Gulyamov and S. Bozarov propose a distinctive approach in this area. According to them, artificial intelligence can assist in the protection of human rights, but it must rely on a robust legal framework that establishes unified requirements for security and transparency¹²⁹. P.M. Morhat rejects granting rights over intellectual activity produced with AI, instead proposing its treatment as a service, hybrid legal authority, or conditional rights allocation¹³⁰. I.Rustambekov, on the other hand, emphasizes the specificity of civil-law relations on the Internet, expressing it in direct connection with the virtual environment¹³¹.

The honorary title “Honored Inventor and Rationalizer of the Republic of Uzbekistan” is awarded to the authors of inventions and rationalization proposals that have been introduced into the national economy and have yielded significant economic benefits. It is also conferred on individuals who have contributed to the development of inventive and rationalization activities and to the implementation of inventions and rationalization proposals in production¹³².

The “Concept for the Development of Science and Technology until 2030,” approved by the Decree No. PF-6097 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on October 29, 2020, is an important legal document for the strategic orientation of the country’s scientific and innovation policy. One of the main objectives of this concept is to ensure that by 2030 Uzbekistan ranks among the world’s top 50 countries in the Global Innovation Index. The concept also envisions the effective coordination of innovation and scientific activities between the public and private sectors, which

¹²⁸ Понкин И.В., Редькина А.И. Искусственный интеллект и право интеллектуальной собственности // Интеллектуальная собственность. авторское право и смежные права. – 2018. – № 2. – С. 35–44. – С. 37–38.

¹²⁹ Gulyamov S., Bozarov S. Strategies future prospects of artificial intelligence: world experience. <https://www.scholarexpress.net/Volume-9April-2022.66-74-6>.

¹³⁰ Морхат П.М. Правосубъектность искусственного интеллекта в сфере права интеллектуальной собственности: гражданско-правовые проблемы. Диссертация на соискание учёной степени доктора юридических наук. Москва, 2018. Стр.238-240.

¹³¹ Рустамбеков И.Р. Интернет тармоғида фуқаролик-хуқуқий муносабатларни тартибга солиш: юрид. фан. докт. дис. ... автореф. –Тошкент: 2017. –13 б.

¹³² Ўзбекистон Республикасининг “Ўзбекистон Республикасининг фахрий унвонларини таъсис этиш тўғрисида”ги қонуни. // Ўзбекистон Республикаси Олий Мажлисининг Ахборотномаси, 1996 й., 5-6-сон, 64-модда.

enables the enhancement of scientific activity through the protection of intellectual property rights, grants, and financial incentives. As a new mechanism, the document allows for commissioning and financing the training of candidates of sciences or philosophers (PhD) and doctors of sciences (DSc) within the framework of grant projects¹³³.

In our view, the state should incentivize the creation and utilization of inventions, utility models, and industrial designs, providing their authors—as well as patent holders and licensees who use the corresponding inventions, utility models, and industrial designs—with privileges in accordance with the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The system for incentivizing inventors and scientific researchers should not be limited solely to patents or material rewards. Copyright, intellectual property, and patent protection play a crucial role in ensuring the fair recognition of their work, supporting scientific and creative activities, and disseminating the results to the broader public. At the same time, an effective and systematic legal and administrative incentive system is a key condition for promoting scientific activity and rapidly supporting innovation.

In the current context, the integrated development of the public and private sectors in science and technology, the provision of grants, titles, honorary distinctions, and intellectual property objects, as well as learning from international experience, play a vital role in shaping an effective scientific and economic environment. From this perspective, Uzbekistan’s legal framework and strategies should ensure the effective protection of inventions and scientific knowledge, their development in accordance with legislation, and the creation of economic and cultural value through patents and licenses.

¹³³ Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг “Илм-фанни 2030 йилгача ривожлантириш концепциясини тасдиқлаш тўғрисида”ги ПФ-6097-сон Фармони. // Қонун ҳужжатлари маълумотлари миллий базаси, 30.10.2020 й., 06/20/6097/1431-сон.